

ISMEC 2021

International Symposium on Thermodynamics of Metal Complexes

Białystok, June 16th-18th

Acta of the International Symposia on Thermodynamics of Metal Complexes

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**International Symposium on Thermodynamics of
Metal Complexes**

Białystok, June 16th – 18th, 2021

**UNIwersytet
w Białymstoku**

International Group of the Thermodynamics of Complexes

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Edited by:

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ISMEC GROUP SERIES

VOLUME: 10

YEAR: 2021

SYMPOSIUM EDITION: XXXI

<https://www.ismecgroup.org/ismec-acta/>

ISSN: 2239-2459

UNIwersytet
w BIAŁYMSTOKU

International Group of the Thermodynamics of Complexes

The

Acta of the International Symposia on Metal Complexes (ISSN: 2239-2459)

are published annually online by the **ISMEC Group** (<https://www.ismecgroup.org/ismec-acta/>)

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Foreword

ISMEC are the annual congresses of the International Group for the Thermodynamics of Complexes, the ISMEC Group (www.ismecgroup.org), an open group in which researchers freely meet to share info and ideas in the field of the Thermodynamics of Complexes, whose main scope is to take initiatives and organize events and activities to promote research, best practices, training and culture in that field.

ISMEC2021 has been the 47th edition of a series of meetings that begun in Florence in 1974 as the annual congress of the Italian group of “Gruppo di Termodinamica dei Complessi”.

The scientific program has been organised in plenary and keynote lectures, oral communications and poster sessions, focused on recent scientific advances in the thermodynamics and the kinetics of complexes in the fields of Analytical, Biomedical, Environmental, Inorganic and Physical Chemistry. Main topics included, but were not limited to:

- Complexation thermodynamics and kinetics
- Solution equilibria and coordination chemistry
- Complexation processes in supramolecular chemistry
- Metal-based reactivity and catalysis
- Metal-complex interactions with biomolecules
- Metals in diseases: transport, homeostasis and toxicity
- Metal-based drugs: diagnosis and therapy
- Metal complexes of environmental and biological interests
- Nanostructured metal complexes
- Analytical methods and sensors based on complexation equilibria
- Computer methods for equilibrium analysis

Since ISMEC 2011 ISMEC Group thought to provide a mechanism for publishing the acts of its symposia quickly and in a book form, creating this series. Its main purpose is to rapidly disclose the most recent advances of scientific research in the field of the thermodynamics of complexes, by publishing timely, comprehensive books developed from the ISMEC Symposia. Every book of the series is edited both by the President of the ISMEC Group in collaboration with all members of the International Scientific Committee, and by the Chair of the annual edition of the ISMEC Congress. Occasionally, other books of the series will be published, but always with the aim of providing readily accessible but accurate information both on the basic aspects and the new findings of chemical research in the same field.

Demetrio Milea
Sofia Gama
June 2021

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Università degli Studi di Messina, Italy
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ISMEC 2021 Programme				
	16 th June	17 th June	18 th June	
9:00 - 9:15	Opening Ceremony	PL3 Rita DELGADO	KN6 Iwona ŁAKOMSKA	
9:15 - 9:30				
9:30 - 9:45	PL1 Christophe DEN AUWER		OC14 Rosella MIGLIORE	Fernando Pulidori Award 2020 Ed. Denise BELLOTTI 2021 Ed. Marianna TOSATO János P. MÉSZÁROS
9:45 - 10:00				
10:00 - 10:15				
10:15 - 10:30			OC15 Salvador BLASCO	
10:30 - 10:45	OC1 Emanuele ZANDA	OC16 Jan KUBINEC		
10:45 - 11:00	OC2 Rosita CAPPAL			
11:00 - 11:30	Coffee Break			
11:30 - 11:45	KN1 José L. BARRIADA	KN4 Přemysl LUBAL	Memorial Session	
11:45 - 12:00				
12:00 - 12:15	OC3 Salvatore CATALDO	OC17 Martina SANADAR		
12:15 - 12:30	OC4 Azza A. HASSOON	OC18 Andreia LEITE		
12:30 - 12:45	OC5 Ágnes GRENÁCS	OC19 Daniele PADERNI	ISMEC 2022 Closing Ceremony	
12:45 - 13:00	OC6 Matteo TEGONI	OC20 Lisa Rita MAGNAGHI		
13:00 - 14:15	Lunch Break			
14:15 - 14:30	KN2 Alicia DOMINGUEZ-MARTIN	KN5 Matteo SAVASTANO		
14:30 - 14:45				
14:45 - 15:00	OC7 Isabel CORREIA	OC21 Sándor NAGY		
15:00 - 15:15	OC8 Gianluca FARINE	OC22 Carlos RICO-MORENO		
15:15 - 15:30	OC9 Sławomir POTOCKI	OC23 Francesca BINACCHI		
15:30 - 15:45	OC10 Olga IRANZO	OC24 Gabriele LANDO		
15:45 - 16:15	Coffee Break			
16:15 - 16:30	KN3 Andrea MELCHIOR	Virtual Posters Session		
16:30 - 16:45				
16:45 - 17:00	OC11 Sandra KOZIEŁ			
17:00 - 17:15	OC12 Natalia BUSTO			
17:15 - 17:30	OC13 Orsolya DÖMÖTÖR			
17:30 - 17:45	PL2 Alison BUTLER	ISMEC Group Meeting		
17:45 - 18:00				
18:00 - 18:15				
18:15 - 18:30				

CONFERENCE PROGRAMME

Wednesday 16th

09:00 - 09:30 **Opening Ceremony**

Chairperson: Antonio BIANCHI - *University of Florence, Italy*

09:30 - 10:30 **PL1** - Is speciation a really good tool for marine radioecology?
Christophe DEN AUWER - *Université Côte d'Azur, France*

Chairperson: Josep GALCERAN - *Universitat de Lleida, Spain*

10:30 - 10:45 **OC1** - Study of Th(IV) complexation with hydroxamic acids by affinity capillary electrophoresis
Emanuele ZANDA - *Université Paris-Saclay, France*

10:45 - 11:00 **OC2** - A low-cost kojic acid derivative: from biological to environmental applications
Rosita CAPPAL - *University of Cagliari, Italy*

11:00 - 11:30 *Coffee Break*

Chairperson: Raffaella BIESUZ - *Università di Pavia, Italy*

11:30 - 12:00 **KN1** - Biomass interactions with metals: from biosorption to nanoparticle synthesis
José L. BARRIADA - *Universidad de Coruña, Spain*

12:00 - 12:15 **OC3** - On the adsorption ability of cyclodextrin-calixarene nanosponges of lead ion from aqueous solution
Salvatore CATALDO - *Università di Palermo, Italy*

12:15 - 12:30 **OC4** - Copper(II) complexes of HPH-NH₂ and HPHPY-NH₂ as structural and functional models of lytic polysaccharide monooxygenases
Azza A. HASSOON - *University of Szeged, Hungary*

12:30 - 12:45 **OC5** - Influence of preceding serine residue(s) on the complex formation processes of histidine/cysteine peptides
Ágnes GRENÁCS - *University of Debrecen, Hungary*

12:45 - 13:00 **OC6** - New artificial copper protein based on the SpyCatcher/SpyTag construct
Matteo TEGONI - *University of Parma, Italy*

13:00 - 14:15 *Lunch Break*

Chairperson: Begoña GARCÍA, - *University of Burgos, Spain*

14:15 - 14:45 **KN2** - Comparative structural vs solution behaviour of metal-mediated base pairs
Alicia DOMINGUEZ-MARTIN - *University of Granada, Spain*

14:45 - 15:00 **OC7** - Exploring the aqueous solution behavior of copper(II) 8-hydroxyquinoline Schiff base complexes

Isabel CORREIA - *Universidade de Lisboa, Portugal*

15:00 - 15:15 **OC8** - Transition metal complexes of Schiff base ligands as selective G-quadruplex DNA binders

Gianluca FARINE - *Università degli Studi di Palermo, Italy*

15:15 - 15:30 **OC9** - Sometimes less is more – the impact of the number of His residues on the stability of Zn(II) – SmtB and BigR4 α -5 domain complexes

Sławomir POTOCKI - *University of Wrocław, Poland*

15:30 - 15:45 **OC10** - Copper removal from A β peptide: when less ligand is better and Zn helps

Olga IRANZO - *Aix Marseille University, France*

15:45 - 16:15 *Coffee Break*

Chairperson: Valeria M. NURCHI - *University of Cagliari, Italy*

16:15 - 16:45 **KN3** - Understanding the structure and reactivity of metal-anticancer compounds

Andrea MELCHIOR - *Università di Udine, Italy*

16:45 - 17:00 **OC11** - Anticancer potency of novel organometallic Ir(III) complexes with phosphines derived from fluoroquinolones encapsulated in polymeric micelles

Sandra KOZIEŁ - *University of Wrocław, Poland*

17:00 - 17:15 **OC12** - Study of the structure-activity relationships (SAR) of a family of half-sandwich Ir(III) complexes

Natalia BUSTO - *Universidad de Burgos, Spain*

17:15 - 17:30 **OC13** - A comprehensive study on the human serum albumin binding of half-sandwich organoruthenium and organorhodium complexes

Orsolya DÖMÖTÖR - *University of Szeged, Hungary*

Chairperson: Michel MEYER - *Université Bourgogne–Franche-Comté, France*

17:30 - 18:30 **PL2** - Metals, microbes, minerals, and mussels: the bioinorganic chemistry of siderophores

Alison BUTLER - *University of California, USA*

Thursday 17th

Chairperson: Enrique GARCÍA-ESPAÑA - *University of Valencia, Spain*

09:15 - 10:15 **PL3** - Molecular architectures for the recognition of bio-relevant anions

Rita DELGADO - *Universidade Nova de Lisboa, Portugal*

Chairperson: Marilena TOLAZZI - *Università di Udine, Italy*

10:15 - 10:30 **OC14** - Interaction of model antibiotics with calixarene-based micellar aggregates: an ITC study

Rossella MIGLIORE - *Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (CNR), Italy*

10:30 - 10:45 **OC15** - Microspeciation analysis of azacyclophanes by means of NMR data fitting with GEMS

Salvador BLASCO - *University of Valencia, Spain*

10:45 - 11:00 **OC16** - Properties of Cu²⁺ and Ga³⁺ NOTA-monoamide complexes

Jan KUBINEC - *Charles University, Czechia*

11:00 - 11:30 *Coffee Break*

Chairperson: Petr HERMANN - *Charles University, Czechia*

11:30 - 12:00 **KN4** - Ln(III) complexes of tetraazamacrocyclic ligands: from basic research to analytical chemosensors

Přemysl LUBAL - *Masaryk University, Czech Republic*

12:00 - 12:15 **OC17** - Luminescent Eu(III) complexes as probes for citrate sensing in complex matrix

Martina SANADAR - *Università di Udine, Italy*

12:15 - 12:30 **OC18** - Tuning the physicochemical properties of fluorescent sensors

Andreia LEITE - *Universidade do Porto, Portugal*

12:30 - 12:45 **OC19** - HNBO-based ligands as selective sensors for Mg(II)

Daniele PADERNI - *University of Urbino "Carlo Bo", Italy*

12:45 - 13:00 **OC20** - Multi-sensing-spot device for smart colorimetric measurements of pH from 1 to 13

Lisa Rita MAGNAGHI - *Università di Pavia, Italy*

13:00 - 14:15 *Lunch Break*

Chairperson: Katalin VÁRNAGY - *University of Debrecen, Hungary*

14:15 - 14:45 **KN5** - Polyiodide complexes: the thin line between coordination chemistry and crystal engineering

Matteo SAVASTANO - *University of Florence, Italy*

14:45 - 15:00 **OC21** - Interaction between platinum group metal ions and novel ambidentate (N,N) and (O,O) chelating ligands in aqueous solution

Sándor NAGY - *University of Debrecen, Hungary*

15:00 - 15:15 **OC22** - Dinuclear $\text{Cu}_2(\mu\text{-EDTA})(2\text{- or }4\text{-apmd})_2$ compounds with amino-pyrimidines related to 2-aminopurine or adenine
Carlos RICO-MORENO - *University of Granada, Spain*

15:15 - 15:30 **OC23** - Mechanistic studies on the binding of platinum, palladium and gold complexes with tetradentate aromatic ligands to biosubstrates: different features for different metal centres
Francesca BINACCHI - *University of Pisa, Italy*

15:30 - 15:45 **OC24** - A new approach in the critical evaluation of the hydrolysis constant of the Zn^{2+} cation
Gabriele LANDO - *Università degli Studi di Messina, Italy*

15:45 - 16:15 *Coffee Break*

Chairperson: Elzbieta GUMIENNA-KONTECKA - *University of Wroclaw, Poland*

16:15 - 17:30 **Virtual Poster Session**

17:30 - 18:30 **ISMEC Group Meeting**

Friday 18th

Chairperson: Maria Amélia SANTOS - *Universidade de Lisboa, Portugal*

09:15 - 09:45 **KN6** - Platinum(II) complexes with bulky disubstitute triazolopyrimidines as promising materials for anticancer agents

Iwona ŁAKOMSKA - *Nicolaus Copernicus University in Toruń, Poland*

Chairperson: Maurizio REMELLI - *University of Ferrara, Italy*

09:45 - 11:00 **Fernando Pulidori Award**

FP1 - Understanding the mechanism of ZnT-mediated metal acquisition: a thermodynamic study

Denise BELLOTTI - *University of Ferrara, Italy*

FP2 - Highly stable silver(I) complexes with cyclen-based ligands bearing sulfide arms: a step toward silver-111 labeled radiopharmaceuticals

Marianna TOSATO - *University of Padova, Italy*

FP3 - An 8-hydroxyquinoline–proline hybrid with multidrug resistance reversal activity and the solution chemistry of its half-sandwich organometallic Ru and Rh complexes

János P. MÉSZÁROS - *University of Szeged, Hungary*

11:00 - 11:30 *Coffee Break*

11:30 - 12:30 **Memorial Session**

12:30 - 13:00 **Presentation of ISMEC2022**

Closing Ceremony

PLENARY LECTURES

Is speciation a really good tool for marine radioecology?

Christophe DEN AUWER

Université Côte d'Azur, CNRS, ICN, 06108 Nice, France

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The mechanisms of dissemination of radionuclides resulting from an accidental release in the environment, in particular in sea water, is a scientific but above all political and social issue. Hence, the need for managing the risk, for controlling the environmental fate and transport of radionuclides, and for preventing human exposure through direct contact and indirectly through the food chain is essential. Among the different environmental matrices, seawater represents the largest proportion of the hydrosphere, it covers by itself about 71% of the earth's surface and it is the final repository of pollution. It is therefore crucial to understand the transfer and accumulation mechanisms of radionuclides in marine environment and to attempt to perform direct speciation analysis in seawater. Speciation is poorly described in seawater systems but also more generally in the environment because of its complexity and large dilution factors that preclude direct speciation. Therefore it is required to shift from a purely descriptive radioecology approach to a mechanistic approach and this can be performed with the use of speciation tools in model (eco)systems.

In 2012, we started to work on the impact of contamination of several actinides (uranium, neptunium, americium and surrogate europium), fission products (cesium) and activation products (cobalt) on marine species (sponge, sea urchin, mussels) in well-controlled marine systems. By describing the speciation of the above metallic radionuclides, we explored the speciation of soluble and insoluble species in seawater leading to potentially bioavailable and bio-transferred species. We have address this question by doping natural seawater with metallic radionuclides in order to be able to perform direct spectroscopic investigation and thus to decipher their molecular speciation. To do so, we have combined several spectroscopic techniques mostly based on X ray Absorption Spectroscopy (XAS) in bulk mode and spatially resolved mode (imaging); together with electron microscopy images, speciation modeling and quantum chemical models.

We have also monitored the uptake mechanisms of metallic radionuclides, *in vivo*. We have for instance selected sea urchins *Paracentrotus Lividus* known as a possible sentinel species for heavy metal accumulation. The accumulation mass balance inside the sea urchin organs has been determined as well as the localization and speciation using XAS.

This work was supported by CEA DAM DIF and CNRS MITI program.

Metals, microbes, minerals, and mussels: the bioinorganic chemistry of siderophores

Alison BUTLER

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The bioinorganic chemistry of the marine environment reflects the chemical composition in which organisms evolve and live. The transition metal ion composition of the surface ocean, differs remarkably from terrestrial environments. The most abundant transition metal ion in surface seawater is molybdenum followed by vanadium, and by contrast, iron is extremely low. Yet iron is essential to many marine organisms. Marine bacteria often produce suites of fatty acid-tailed siderophores that bind iron but also can self-assemble into micelles and vesicles. [Siderophores are microbially-produced ligands that facilitate Fe(III) transport into the bacterium]. Many marine siderophore also often contain an α -hydroxy carboxylic acid group, such as β -hydroxyaspartic acid, which when coordinated to Fe(III) is photoreactive. Catechol ligands in siderophores and proteins are also important in marine organisms, both as 2,3-dihydroxybenzoic acid (2,3-DHB) present in both marine and terrestrial siderophores, and as 3,4-dihydroxyphenylalanine (DOPA) present in mussel foot proteins (mfps) for surface adhesion. In some mfps the catechol content is as high as 30 mol percent and matched by an equally high content of Lys or Arg. The siderophore cyclic trichrysobactin (CTC, the macrolactone of tris-(2,3-DHB-L-Lys-L-Ser); see figure) also has a matched ratio of catechol to Lys [1]. This talk will cover the bioinorganic chemistry and coordination chemistry of siderophores, including the self-assembling acyl peptidic siderophores, and new diastereomeric tris catechol siderophores, as well as the chemistry of catechol adhesion to surfaces as employed by marine mussels [2-4; see figure (right side)]. New adhesive catechol compounds resembling siderophores and mussel foot proteins will be considered which further probe the importance of coupled catechol and cationic amine groups in aqueous wet adhesion.

References:

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- [2] G.P. Maier, M.V. Rapp, J.H. Waite, J.N. Israelachvili, A. Butler, *Science*, 2015, **349**, 628-632
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Molecular architectures for the recognition of bio-relevant anions

Rita DELGADO

Instituto de Tecnologia Química e Biológica António Xavier, Universidade Nova de Lisboa, Av. da República, 2780-157 Oeiras, Portugal
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Polyamine macrocyclic and macrobicyclic compounds are very versatile architectures, as their protonated forms can directly interact with anions, their neutral forms can coordinate metal ions, and both ammonium groups and metal centers combined can cooperatively bind anions.

Recognition of anions in water remains a key challenge in supramolecular chemistry, but is essential for applications in biology, medicine, and environment. In the chemistry of life processes, anion binding plays a central role. For instance, the recognition, signaling and transport of anions are crucial features in the metabolism and in cell function regulation. In addition, anions can also have a negative impact on the environment.

In our work we took advantage of the ease modification of the macrocyclic and macrobicyclic architectures and by small structural modifications we tried to rigidify their structure in order to increase the preorganization. Several families of almost unexplored macrocycles and macrobicycles were thoroughly studied by us as anion receptors, in aqueous solution and in the solid state. It was not only possible to achieve selectivity between inorganic substrates of similar size and shape but also build new compounds appropriate for the binding of more complicated substrates such as dicarboxylates, amino acids and peptides. Several examples will be presented.

KEYNOTE LECTURES

Biomass interactions with metals: from biosorption to nanoparticle synthesis

José L. BARRIADA

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Natural products constitute an interesting source of materials for use both in laboratory or in industrial applications. The use of natural products obtained from plants or animals has attracted science attention in a world where the circular economy concept is growing in these last years and the search of renewable resources is becoming a key factor. Many different applications of the so-called biomass can be found in the dedicated literature, and among these applications biosorption is one of the topics that has increased enormously in the last two decades [1,2].

Biosorption, defined as the passive sequestration of a sorbate (either an atom, a molecule, or in general any chemical species) by a biosorbent (any solid material of a biological origin), results in the accumulation of that species in the surface of the biosorbent. This very broad definition encompasses different types of interactions, which can include among others pure adsorption processes, ionic exchange, (micro)precipitation, redox processes, or chemical binding and in many cases several of them taking place simultaneously. As products used as biosorbents, examples can be found which show the used of many types of terrestrial plants, but also seaweeds or chitinous materials obtained from animals or fungi. These biomaterials have shown in some cases very strong interactions with metallic ions but also with other chemical species. The main objective in those biosorption studies is the determination of the isotherm of the biomaterial employed under certain experimental conditions. The study of effects such as the pH of the solution, contact time or sorbent concentration is completed with the analysis of competition with other species, the desorption of sorbate to regenerate the sorbent for further use or the study of the functioning of the biomaterial in a continuous flow regime [1,3]. A large number of cost-effective materials has been studied, yet the final, widely spread application at industrial scale remains as a point not fully developed.

At laboratory level, the main challenge with these materials is related to the non-completely defined structure of the materials themselves. Depending on the source employed, many different types of functional groups and chemical species can be found. Even though one of them can be predominant, like for example alginates in brown seaweeds, other functional groups are also present, and this fact complicates the understanding of the physico-chemical processes that are taking place during the sequestration of the adsorbates.

However, this complex nature of the biomaterials also provides new possibilities. For example, when terrestrial plants are used, many active compounds can be found among their constituents. From polyphenols, to terpenoids, flavonoids, alkaloids, etc. Some of these compounds interact strongly with metals present in solution and in some cases redox reactions can be observed. This feature can be used to promote the formation of nanoparticles in solution [4]. Plant residues can be used to prepare

extracts that are subsequently mixed with metallic salt solutions for the synthesis of nanoparticles. The use of these extracts constitutes an environmentally friendly approach to the bottom-up synthesis of nanoparticles, using renewable resources. These extracts also may contain substances that act as capping agents, that prevent further growth in the nanoparticles as well as aggregation. As it has been previously mentioned, the complex nature of the biomaterials hinders a complete knowledge of all the substances participating in the formation of nanoparticles, and more research must be developed in this topic.

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Comparative structural vs solution behaviour of metal-mediated base pairs

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X-ray diffraction has certainly revolutionized the study of biological systems. Indeed, the most recent advances on the understanding of folding and mechanisms of action of metalloproteins and nucleic acids are based on a crystal structure and the careful analysis of the intermolecular interactions present therein. However, biology happens in solution, and therefore a solid-state vision is not enough to comprehensively explain the equilibria that certainly exists in such systems. Hence, we need, whenever possible, to compare both approaches, solid-state and solution, to fully characterize their behaviour.

The self-recognition abilities of nucleobases in nucleic acids have called the attention of nanoscience and nanotechnology [1]. Interestingly, nucleic acids can be further modified to introduce specific functionalities in novel DNA-based materials. One of the most challenging and successful approaches to develop new, non-inherent, properties on novel DNA-based materials, without losing their self-assembly properties, is metalation, i.e., metal-mediated base pairs. In the context of our research on metal-mediated base pairs, a comparative view of our results using single crystal X-ray diffraction (XRD, solid-state) and Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR, solution technique) is provided, aiming to understand the intimate structure of our novel DNA-based materials.

In our first work [2], the formation of copper-mediated base pairs is characterized outside and inside DNA molecules (Figure 1). Unfortunately, despite metal coordination in the individual metal-mediated base pairs, including bond distances and angles, fitted quite nicely with the predicted structure, a stable metal-mediated DNA helix was not achieved in solution.

Figure 1: Scheme of the formation of copper-mediated base pairs. Adapted from reference [2].

In contrast, in our second work [3], the formation of palladium-mediated base pairs in a continuous DNA array was accomplished, although slight differences in the nature of the metal coordination were observed by NMR and XRD techniques (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Scheme of the formation of palladium-mediated base pairs. Adapted from reference [3].

The key aspects that drive metal ion coordination within the nucleoside moieties as well as the most relevant molecular recognition aspects in both examples will be discussed, trying to rationalize the rational design of future metal-based DNA nanowires.

Acknowledgements: Financial support from University of Granada-FEDER (A-FQM-465-UGR18 and PPIIA2019-03), and Junta de Andalucía (FQM-293 and FQM-283) is gratefully acknowledged. A.D.-M. acknowledges support from Cost Action CA18202 - Network for Equilibria and Chemical Thermodynamics Advanced Research.

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Understanding the structure and reactivity of metal-anticancer compounds

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Since the discovery of the first complex which exhibited anti-tumor properties, cisplatin, numerous Pt(II) complexes have been used as anti-cancer drugs, but only few have been approved for clinical use [1]. The accepted mechanism of action of cisplatin consists in two stages: intracellular activation by the hydrolysis of a ligand and formation of intra-strand cross-links in DNA which produces a bending that causes the generation of defective proteins and ultimately the cell death.

Several strategies have been applied to find new platinum drugs with an equivalent or improved range of activity and less toxic side effects[2]. The search for improvements requires also a detailed knowledge of the reaction mechanisms at molecular level. In this framework, computational modelling has been employed in the last two decades to achieve a clear understanding of the structure and reactivity of these metallodrugs.

In this contribution, complementary pieces of information on platinum compounds in solution, obtained through different theoretical approaches, will be presented [2-6]. In particular, the focus will be on complex hydration structure and dynamics; reaction energy profiles; modeling the interaction with DNA (Fig. 1).

Figure 1 Intercalation of a platinum compound and its aqua-derivative to a AA dimer model. Hydrogen bonds are highlighted in purple and non-covalent interactions are evidenced by green surfaces.

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Ln(III) complexes of tetraazamacrocyclic ligands: from basic research to analytical chemosensors

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Ln(III) complexes of tetraazamacrocyclic ligands based on cyclen rim (*e.g.* H₄dota and its derivatives) are utilized in preclinical research and many areas of medicine for diagnostics or cancer treatment (*e.g.* radioisotopes as ⁹⁰Y, ¹⁵³Sm, ¹⁶⁶Ho, ¹⁷⁷Lu in nuclear medicine, Gd(III)/Eu(II) complexes as MRI contrast agents, Eu(III) or Tb(III) complexes as luminescent probes) [1, 2]. Such Ln(III) complexes should exhibit a high thermodynamic stability as well as kinetic inertness under physiological conditions and therefore knowledge of these properties is important for any biomedical applications.

In the first part, the kinetic study of metal complexes with chosen tetraazamacrocyclic ligands will be presented to see the impact of ligand denticity or of kind of pendant arm(s) (*e.g.* phosphonic/phosphinic/carboxylic acid) on formation and dissociation of chosen Ln(III) complexes (mostly Ce(III)/Eu(III)/Tb(III) [2-11]). The results can be compared with Cu(II) complexes for the same ligands [12, 13]. The detailed reaction mechanism describing both formation and dissociation of Eu(III) and Tb(III) complexes was proposed by new methodology based on experimental data obtained by luminescence spectroscopy in steady-state or time-resolved mode [9, 11, 14, 15]. This general experimental procedure was recently also developed for determination of stability constants of Ln(III) complexes [11].

The binding of antenna functional group in binary or ternary Ln(III) complexes exhibits significant increase of brightness of luminescence due to the efficient transfer of absorbed energy from ligand to Ln(III) ion. In the second part, the development of new luminescent chemosensor for analysis of Ln(III) ions in mixture [16] or traces of water in organic solvents or ionic liquids [17, 18] will be shortly discussed. In addition, the dual chemosensor based on Eu(III) or Tb(III) complexes can be employed for direct detection of carbonate/carbon dioxide [19, 20]. The Ln(III) complexes can be also used for the proposal of biosensor using enzymes producing carbon dioxide (*e.g.* urease [21]) or utilizing redox pair NAD(P)⁺/NAD(P)H as co-factor (*e.g.* alcohol-dehydrogenase [22]).

Acknowledgement. This work was supported by Masaryk University (MUNI/A/1192/2020), Ministry of Education of the Czech Republic (LTC20044) and EU (COST CA18202 NECTAR Action).

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Polyiodide complexes: the thin line between coordination chemistry and crystal engineering

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Since the discovery of iodine, two centuries ago, polyiodide chemistry has been object of intense scientific curiosity [1,2]. In its various historical iterations, the field attracted experts with diverse interests, including bonding theories (easily challenged by hypervalent polyiodides), nature of I...I supramolecular interactions (eventually leading to concepts such as secondary/ σ -hole/halogen bonding), and solution thermodynamics (equilibria in I₂/I⁻ solutions have been long debated and their study remains experimentally challenging to these days) [1,2]. Nowadays, together with a renewed interest for novel media (ionic liquids, iodine-doped polymers, etc...), crystal engineering of polyiodides remains a lively field of study, allowing both for the prosecution of the elucidation of the basic properties of such systems and the simultaneous obtainment of crystalline phases with potential for application (especially as solid-state electrical conductors based on a Grotthuss-like mechanism) [1,2].

What we intend to discuss is the impossibility to address crystal engineering of polyiodide-based systems, or even to meaningfully obtain series of polyiodide crystals in the first place, without considering the serious, and challenging, speciation problem that arises when I₂, I⁻, and cations with systematic structural changes co-exist in solution. We will show how pre-emptive knowledge of cation and anion speciation in solution is required to ensure that observed polyiodide structural changes are truly function only of intended changes in the cations, and how strict control of crystallization conditions (accounting for solution equilibria) must be maintained to establish meaningful structure-properties relationships.

As incorporation of transition metals in iodine-dense polyiodide networks is of potential technological interest, we will focus on solution thermodynamics and coordination chemistry as necessary tools of the trade for the engineering of such crystalline phases.

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Platinum(II) complexes with bulky disubstitute triazolopyrimidines as promising materials for anticancer agents

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Inert square planar Pt(II) drugs currently used in the chemotherapy of some cancers suffer from lack of selectivity, toxicity, and poor aqueous solubility, and in many cases acquired or inherent resistance also develops during treatments [1,2]. To overcome these drawbacks, there is an urgent need to find more selective and low-concentration effective metal-based chemotherapeutics with improved pharmacological properties [3,4] and much fewer side effects than those of current drugs. These new strategies are currently in progress and often take advantage of the differences between healthy and cancer cells.

The main approach in the rational design of platinum(II) complexes focuses on modifications in either the carrier ligands or the leaving ligands. The dicarboxylato ligands have quite different advantages as leaving groups than those of chloride ligands. Additionally, the presence of the dicarboxylato moiety in the coordination sphere enhances the aqueous solubility of platinum(II) complexes [5], reduces side effects and increases the efficiency of platinum(II) anticancer drugs, and does not affect the mechanism of activation and interaction with DNA bases.

Herein, we present dicarboxylate platinum(II) complexes of the general formula [Pt(L')(dmsO)(L)] and [Pt(L')(L₂)], where L' is cyclobutane-1,1-dicarboxylato or malonato; L is dmtp -5,7-dimethyl-1,2,4-triazolo[1,5-*a*]pyrimidine; dbtp 5,7-ditertbutyl-1,2,4-triazolo[1,5-*a*]pyrimidine; ibmtp 7-isobutyl-5-methyl-1,2,4-triazolo[1,5-*a*]pyrimidine; dptp - 5,7-diphenyl-1,2,4-triazolo[1,5-*a*]pyrimidine), as prospective prodrugs. All platinum(II) compounds were characterized by FT-IR, and ¹H, ¹³C, ¹⁵N, ¹⁹⁵Pt NMR, X-ray, and their square planar geometry with monodentate N(3)-bonded 5,7-disubstituted-1,2,4-triazolo[1,5-*a*]pyrimidine and O,O-chelating malonato or O,O-chelating cyclobutane-1,1-dicarboxylato was determined [6-8]. In order to choose the compound(s) with the most promising therapeutic effectiveness, we estimated important biological parameters in a solution such as the hydrolysis rate, lipophilicity (logP parameter), *in vitro* antiproliferative activity and interactions with glutathione (GSH) and DNA, whose determination is important in planning a selective and effective anticancer therapy.

Finally, we can suggest, that **i)** the presence of the S-donor molecule of dmsO directly bonded with platinum(II) ion is responsible for low toxicity of platinum(II) complexes and their low reactivity towards other sulphur containing bioligands such as glutathione; **ii)** the size of 5,7-substituents in heterocycle ligands plays an important role in tuning the hydrolysis rate, the lipophilicity, reactivity towards GSH, and *in vitro* antiproliferative activity. Results obtained for two lipophilic complexes

[Pt(mal)(dmsO)(dptp)] and [Pt(CBDC)(dmsO)(dptp)], with bulky 5,7-diphenyl-1,2,4-triazolo [1,5-*a*]pyrimidine look promising, and demonstrate that modification of coordination sphere by insertion of S-donor ligand is a good direction for the design less toxic platinum(II) complexes.

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ORAL COMMUNICATIONS

Study of Th(IV) complexation with hydroxamic acids by affinity capillary electrophoresis

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The transfer of metal cations in soils and sediments is not only controlled by geological and physico-chemical parameters (clay and organic matter contents, pH, Eh, etc.) but also by microorganisms. The latter take part in the mobilization/immobilization of trace metals [1]. Therefore, the presence of actinide(IV) (Th, Pu) radionuclides after accidental discharges raises the question of their transfer in the environment and the resulting risk of food chain contamination. Siderophores, as natural iron-specific chelators, have to be considered in this context [2]. These low molecular weight, water-soluble compounds are excreted by bacteria and fungi to overcome the limited bioavailability of iron under aerobic conditions (ca. 10^{-18} M at neutral pH) by dissolving iron oxohydroxides present in the soils.

This work is devoted to the complexation study of Th(IV) with a number of commercially available simple hydroxamic acids (Figure 1a) and of (DFO(Me)PIPO)₄ (Figure 1b), a new tetrahydroxamic acid obtained by coupling the 6-membered 1-hydroxypiperidine-2-one moiety to the bacterial siderophore desferrioxamine B [3]. These compounds are effective ligands in capturing and transporting actinides [4].

Figure 1. a) General formula of simple hydroxamic acids; b) structure of (DFO(Me)PIPO)₄.

Affinity capillary electrophoresis (ACE), which requires only a few μ L of solutions, with UV detection was used to unravel the speciation of these systems. ACE is based on the change in the

electrophoretic mobility of the detected species due to the interaction with other species present in the electrolyte. Two sets of runs were performed using (H,Na)ClO₄ mixtures at constant pH and ionic strength. On a first approach, the background electrolyte (BGE) contained varying amounts of Th(IV), while the second approach consisted in analysing solutions containing increasing amounts of ligand in the BGE. The electrophoretic mobility changes with the increasing concentrations of the reagent dissolved in the BGE solution was used to assess the speciation and equilibrium constants. This method is fruitful for studying metal complex formation equilibria and gives valuable information for further modelling of their behaviour under environmental conditions [5].

Acknowledgments: The Agence Nationale de la Recherche (ANR project PLUTON, grant N° ANR-17-CE08-0053) is gratefully acknowledged for financial support.

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A low-cost kojic acid derivative: from biological to environmental applications

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Metal toxicity is a worldwide problem depending either on metal overload for genetic diseases or on environmental and occupational exposure. Based on the previous solution studies of kojic acid (KA) derivatives, we synthesized a low-cost tripodal chelator (6,6',6''-(((nitrilotris(ethane-2,1-diyl))tris(azanediy))tris(methylene))tris(3-hydroxy-4Hpyran-4-one)) (SC), characterized by three KA moieties attached to a tris(2-aminoethyl)amine (tren) backbone. Potentiometry, UV-vis spectrophotometry have been used to evaluate the coordination ability toward several metal ions. The presence of oxygen and nitrogen donor atoms allows the coordination of both hard and intermediate metal ions, such as Fe³⁺, Al³⁺, VO²⁺, Cu²⁺, Mn²⁺, Co²⁺, Cd²⁺, Ni²⁺ and Zn²⁺. Complexation studies show a metal affinity sequence Fe³⁺ > Al³⁺ > Mn²⁺ ~ Co²⁺ > Cu²⁺ > Ni²⁺ on the oxygen donor atoms of KA units, and Zn²⁺ ~ Cd²⁺ on the nitrogen donors of tren linker. Furthermore, SC presents the ability to chelate Zn²⁺ and Fe³⁺ ions at the same time. The very good complexation capacity for Fe³⁺, supports the potential use of SC in clinical chelation treatment for iron overload diseases, and the good capacity for Zn²⁺ and Cd²⁺ the potential use in analytical chemistry as well as in environmental application. For instance, to develop sorbents for toxic metal removal that promising KA derivative will be incorporated into mesostructured silicas or magnetic nanocomposites properly functionalized.

Figure 1: SC ligand with highlighted donor atoms.

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On the adsorption ability of cyclodextrin-calixarene nanosponges of lead ion from aqueous solution

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Recently, an increasing attention has been paid to composite materials based on cyclodextrins (CDs). These cyclic oligosaccharides gather several interesting and useful features since they are highly functionalized molecules, containing plenty of primary and secondary hydroxyl groups liable to undergo chemical transformation by quite simple organic reaction routes [1]. The reaction between native or chemically modified CDs with suitable reticulating agents allows accessing to a further class of potential sorbent materials referred to as “Nanosponges” (NSs). Nanosponges can be useful in many fields of applications: drug carrier/delivery, devices to sensors, environment remediation, active packaging [2,3].

Different pristine and chemically post-modified cyclodextrin - calixarene nanosponges (CyCaNSs) have been synthesized and, among that, four were chosen and characterized by means of FFC-NMR relaxometric techniques and used as adsorbent materials to remove Pb²⁺ from aqueous solutions [4].

The adsorption tests were performed under different operational conditions in order to simulate the different characteristics of polluted waters. The experiments were carried out on solutions without and with the addition of background salts, at different pH, ionic strengths and temperatures. NaNO₃ and NaCl were used, changing the ionic strength in the range 0.01 - 0.1 mol L⁻¹. The initial pH was fixed at 3.0 and 5.0, while the effect of temperature was studied in the range 283.15 - 323.15 K. The adsorption

capacity of the nanosponges towards Pb²⁺ were kinetically and thermodynamically investigated by measuring the metal ion concentration in the water samples of batch experiments by means of Inductively Coupled Plasma Emission Spectroscopy (ICP-OES) and Differential Pulse Anodic Stripping Voltammetry (DP-ASV). The acid-base properties of nanosponges and of metal ion as well as their interactions with the other interacting components of the systems have been considered in the evaluation of adsorption mechanism. Recycling and reuse experiments on the most efficient CyCaNSs were also performed.

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Copper(II) complexes of HPH-NH₂ and HPHPY-NH₂ as structural and functional models of lytic polysaccharide monoxygenases

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One of the most important industrial challenges for a low fossil fuel economy future is the conversion of biomass into fuels and other useful chemicals. First-generation biofuels are well-established, but their dependence on food source suitable for human consumption means that they should be substituted. Because of its low cost, abundance and renewability, the degradation of lignocellulosic biomass (LB) to produce fuels and other useful chemicals is a very promising perspective. One of the major obstacles of LB valorisation is its surprisingly high recalcitrance to enzymatic hydrolysis caused by the heterogeneous multi-scale structure of plant cell walls. Factors affecting LB recalcitrance are strongly interconnected and can be divided into structural factors (cellulose specific surface area, cellulose crystallinity, degree of polymerization, pore size and volume) and chemical factors (composition and content in lignin, hemicelluloses, acetyl groups). These problems amplify each other, making lignocellulose degradation a major biotechnological challenge.

The discovery of lytic polysaccharide monoxygenases (LPMOs) has revolutionized our view on how cellulose is degraded [1]. In contrast to typical cellulases, which are hydrolytic enzymes, LPMOs cleave the β -1,4-glycosidic bonds via the oxidation of the C1- or C4 atom making the substrate tractable to hydrolases, apparently without the need for de-crystallization. In doing so, LPMOs boost the activity of canonical glycoside hydrolases by up to two orders of magnitude, thereby greatly reducing the financial and environmental penalties associated with the use of recalcitrant polysaccharides as a feedstock. This placed LPMOs at the centre of biochemical/bioinorganic research. Therefore, studies on LPMOs have progressed rapidly, however, our knowledge on the functioning of these enzymes is rather limited, the identity of the reactive species, the key steps in the oxidative mechanism and even the identity of the biologically relevant oxidizing co-substrate (O₂ or H₂O₂), are still unknown. Beside biochemistry, synthetic bioinorganic chemistry may also play pivotal role in elucidating the catalytic mechanism, which is the prerequisite of their efficient use in industrial biotechnology.

These proteins are copper-dependent enzymes, having a relatively flat surface containing the catalytic site with a mononuclear copper centre. The copper atom of LPMOs is coordinated by two strictly conserved histidine residues, with one binding bidentate through the N-terminal amine, referred to as the His-brace motif (Figure 1). The strictly conserved His-brace is a rather unusual copper binding motif but can also be found in pMMO proteins. In five of the six families of LPMOs a weakly

bound (if at all) protonated tyrosine OH occupy an axial position of copper(II) with Cu–O(Tyr) distances varying between 2.5 and 3.0 Å.

To our knowledge, only three papers report study on explicit functional models of LPMOs [2-4]. In presence of H₂O₂ and Et₃N these copper(II) complexes were able to catalyse the oxidative cleavage of the model substrate p-nitrophenyl-β-D-glucopyranoside [2,4] or cellobiose [3]. As possible active intermediate mononuclear hydroperoxo (CuOOH) [2,4] and peroxo-bridged dicopper(II) [3] species were suggested. Interestingly, the spectroscopically identified mononuclear hydroperoxo (CuOOH) complexes were relatively stable in aqueous solutions at 298 K. However, the imidazole donors in these complexes were mostly modelled by amino and/or pyridine nitrogens. Histidine containing peptidic ligands, which more closely mimic the biological metal-binding sites, are rarely studied. Our hypothesis is that ‘His-brace’ plays a decisive role in the efficacy of LPMOs, therefore only the use His-peptides as the closest mimics of the active centres of LPMOs may uncover some fundamental aspects of LPMOs catalytic mechanism, unexplored to date by synthetic models. To this end, here we present our results concerning the Cu(II) complexes of two His-containing peptides, HPH-NH₂ (**L1**) and HPHPY-NH₂ (**L2**).

In excess of ligands, *bis*-complexes with *bis*-histamine-like coordination are formed in the pH range 5-9 with both ligands, differing in their protonation states. In equimolar solution between pH 5-6 mono-complexes are formed having {NH₂, 2×N_{im}} coordination mode, similar to the active centres of LPMOs. However, between pH 6-9 unusual dimer species (with a composition Cu₂H₋₁L₁₂ and Cu₂HL₂₂) are dominant the solution, in which the ‘extra’ deprotonation is related to a bridge formation between the two metal ions. At higher pH further deprotonations of these dimer complexes take place. Our kinetic results indicate, that the dimer complexes formed in the equimolar systems, in the presence of hydrogen peroxide as oxidising co-substrate, possess significant LPMO-like activity both at pH 7.4 and 10.5. Their enzyme-like behaviour was confirmed, as the kinetic data could be described by the Michaelis-Menten kinetics. In our communication, the results of our solution equilibrium, solution structural (UV-Vis, CD, EPR) and kinetic data will be detailed.

Acknowledgements

This research was supported by National Research, Development and Innovation Office (NKFIH) through the project GINOP-2.3.2-15-2016-00038. A. A. H. thanks Stipendium Hungaricum for her PhD fellowship, which is also supported by the Cultural Affairs & Mission Sector in Egypt.

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Figure 1. Schematic structure of LPMO's active centre (X = H or OH)

Influence of preceding serine residue(s) on the complex formation processes of histidine/cysteine peptides

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Interaction of metal ions and proteins, peptides, amino acids are essential in the human body; these processes can be based on either coordination or hydrolytic and oxidative reactions.

Investigations of amino acids and peptides and their complex formation processes with transition metal ions, like Cu(II), Ni(II), Zn(II), Co(II), Cd(II), Pd(II), Pt(II), Hg(II), etc. were thoroughly described. In case of peptides, anchor groups are responsible for the capture of the metal ion and further amide nitrogens are also bond as pH increases. During solution equilibrium and spectroscopic measurements, reversible complex formation processes are assumed in the presence of nickel(II) ions. However, a defined motif enables other reactions between the metal ions and the peptide and a non-coordinating side chain of serine or threonine residue is responsible for the exceptional behaviour.

Structure altering effect of these sequences were observed in the case of –S/TXH– motifs through the circular dichroism spectra of their 4N nickel complexes [1,2] and in the presence of the metal ion, selective hydrolysis of the peptide also occurs. [3] Replacement of the anchor to cysteine, cleavage of the peptide was also observed. [4] These reactions, however, were detected at higher temperature and mostly after several hours.

In our work, we studied the structural change of the formed complexes and the possibility of hydrolysis using solution equilibrium and spectroscopic methods. Two types of ligands are involved; short peptides including the –SXH/C– nickel(II) binding area and ligands with –SSH/C-NH₂ C-terminal region where the effect of an additional metal binding site at the N-terminus can be also investigated. Surprisingly, hydrolysis of the molecules is quite diverse comparing different anchors and size of ligands, however, distortion of circular dichroism spectra showed the structural change in the formed complexes compared to those without serine residue(s). Role of serine can be the facilitation of hydrolytic processes by the formation of a defined geometry, however, this preliminary step is not enough in each case for the final cleavage of the peptide.

Acknowledgements: The research was supported by the Hungarian National Research, Development and Innovation Office (NKFIH K115480).

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New artificial copper protein based on the SpyCatcher/SpyTag construct

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Metalloproteins promote several of the most complex biomolecular processes in nature. The design of new metalloproteins is therefore of interest in the field of the development of new efficient biocatalysts which can carry out reactions that are not relevant for biological systems but are important for applications in bio- and nanotechnology.[1] In this context, the “Trojan-horse” strategy is an efficient method to introduce an artificial metal site into a protein that is lacking it in the wild type form. This strategy consists into adding a protein with a substrate, the latter bearing a metal site: the interaction between the protein and its substrate allows the metal site to be grafted on the protein in a specific position.

We present here a new copper protein designed using the SpyCatcher/SpyTag construct.[2] This construct has been redesigned from a domain of a fibronectin binding protein from *Streptococcus pyogenes*, which consists of a 10.5 kDa β -barrel protein (SpyCatcher, Figure 1, green) which binds covalently an oligopeptide (SpyTag, Figure 1, blue) through the formation of an isopeptide bond between an Asp and a Lys residues. The SpyTag peptide that we have designed bears: i) a GSH peptide sequence at the N-terminus for copper(II) binding; ii) a IVMVD^{a)} fragment for the binding to SpyCatcher; iii) a thioredoxin (Trx) domain from *E.coli* at the C-terminus. Both SpyCatcher and SpyTag were also been mutated to exclude any His residue other than that at the ATCUN site of Tag (GSH), expressed in *E. coli* and purified through chromatography.

Figure 1: Left: representation of the SpyCatcher/SpyTagTrx construct. A representation of the ATCUN binding site of Cu(II) is shown; Right: CD spectra for additions of Cu(II) to SpyCatcher/SpyTagTrx. Black: 0 eq. Cu(II); red: 0.5 eq.; blue: 1 eq.; magenta: 1.5 eq.; green: 2 eq. ($C_{\text{Catcher}} = C_{\text{Tag}} = 500 \mu\text{M}$, 20 mM HEPES + 0.1 M NaCl).

Absorption and CD spectrophotometric data show that the protein binds two Cu(II) sequentially at the ATCUN site of SptTag and at the N-terminus of SpyCatcher. Below 1 eq. of Cu(II) the binding is almost selective at the ATCUN site. Beyond 2 eq. of Cu(II), fluorescence spectra evidenced some form of unspecific binding of Cu(II) to the protein.

We have evaluated the catalytic behaviour of the Cu(II)/SpyCatcher/SpyTag adduct toward hydrolysis of *p*-nitrophenylphosphate (pNPP) and toward cleavage of plasmid DNA strands in the presence of ascorbate. As it concerns the cleavage of DNA strands, contrarily to what reported in the literature for other ATCUN peptide the presence of Cu(II) coordinated to the SpyTag ATCUN site seems to protect against the appearance of nicked DNA plasmids. Even more complex observations relate with the phosphoesterase activity against pNPP: although fastest rates of hydrolysis were observed for the protein species in the presence of Cu(II), the apo-proteins also exhibit a non-innocent behaviour with respect of this reactivity.

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Exploring the aqueous solution behavior of copper(II) 8-hydroxyquinoline Schiff base complexes

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Cancer is one of the most challenging diseases and cancer-related deaths are estimated to rise as life expectancy increases. Although relevant progress has been obtained in the treatment of several cancer diseases over the past few decades, the incidence and mortality associated with cancer continues to increase. Current strategies, alternative to the use of Pt-based drugs, such as cisplatin, involve the use of endogenous metals ions, which will certainly offer different mechanisms of action. Copper, in particular, gives also the possibility to explore its redox chemistry and thus, copper complexes are the focus of this presentation.

The interest in quinolones and specifically in 8-hydroxyquinoline (8HQ) derivatives, has grown exponentially in the last decades. The literature thrives with examples of the anticancer, antifungal and bactericidal activity of this type of compounds.[1-3] A. Barilli *et al.* reported on a series of 2-substituted-8HQ ligands, with good results on HeLa cervical cancer cells in the presence of Fe(III) and Cu(II). [4] The intracellular accumulation of these endogenous metal ions led to severe oxidative stress, triggering a caspase-independent process of cell death. Chen *et al.* developed Cu(II) and Ni(II) complexes of 2-((2-(pyridin-2-yl)hydrazono)methyl)quinolin-8-ol, which presented good cytotoxic results in different cancer cell lines.[5]

Within this work we aim to synthesize and characterize new 8-hydroxyquinoline Schiff base metal complexes to determine their structure in solution; evaluate their speciation in aqueous biological media; and screen their ability to reduce the viability of tumor cells. Two families of compounds were developed, and results on their copper complexes will be presented. One Schiff base (SB) derived from 8-hydroxyquinoline and 2-hydrazinobenzothiazole, as well as eight SB ligands derived from the condensation of 8HQ with several hydrazides (Fig 1). They were reacted with Cu(II) and the compounds characterized in solid state and solution, which helped elucidate the coordination to the copper center.

Figure 1: Structure of the 8-hydroxyquinoline ligands reported in this work. $R_1 = \text{N}$ or C , $R_2 = \text{H}$, CH_3 , NH_2 , OCH_3 , OH , Cl and F .

The lack of information on the speciation of metal-based therapeutics has been a drawback. Knowledge of biospeciation, both in cell culture media and inside cells, can help to explain cytotoxicity results as well as other biological effects. Therefore, the compounds' stability in aqueous solution at physiological pH, and their reactivity in the presence of albumin and reduced glutathione are evaluated, showing differences between the compounds which will be exposed. The DNA binding ability of a few compounds was also assessed and will be shown. Their cytotoxicity and mechanisms of cell death are currently under study and preliminary data will be presented.

Acknowledgments: This work was supported by Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia (FCT) (projects UIDB/00100/2020, UIDP/00100/2020, PTDC/QUI-QIN/0586/2020 and grant SFRH/BD/135797/2018).

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Transition metal complexes of Schiff base ligands as selective G-quadruplex DNA binders

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Cationic transition metal compounds of N₂O₂ and N₄ tetradentate Schiff base ligands, have been recently designed and synthesized as selective G-quadruplex DNA binders. The DNA binding with both duplex (B) and G-quadruplex (G4) DNA has been investigated by the combination of experimental and computational approaches [1,2]. The effect of the solution saline concentration has also been monitored, highlighting that the DNA-binding of the positively charged metal complexes is hampered by an increase of the solution ionic strength.

In the effort to synthesize stable Pt(II) and Pd(II) Schiff base complexes, neutral or dicationic, new ligands have been recently designed (Figure 1). The ability of each metal complex to catalyze the oxidation of guanine bases has been monitored, with the aim to promote a selective oxidation of G4 structures with key roles in carcinogenic events (i.e. G4s of oncogene promoters), affecting in such way the machinery of cancer cells [3,4].

Figure 1: Structure of transition metal complexes of N₄ tetradentate Schiff base ligands.

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Sometimes less is more – the impact of the number of His residues on the stability of Zn(II) – SmtB and BigR4 α -5 domain complexes

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The increasing number of antibiotic-resistant pathogens has become one of the major health problems of modern times, not excluding *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* infections [1,2]. One of the possible response of the mammalian immune system to mycobacterial infection is the increase of zinc(II) concentration in phagosomes to a toxic level [3]. The mycobacterial SmtB protein belongs to the family of ArsR/SmtB transcription regulators which in the presence of high concentrations of metals, dissociate from DNA and activate the expression of metal efflux proteins.

In this work, we focus on α 5 zinc(II) binding domains of SmtB/BigR4 proteins (the latter being the SmtB homolog from non-pathogenic *M. smegmatis*) and two mutants of BigR4, taking a closer look at the coordination modes and thermodynamic properties of their zinc(II) complexes. Ligand sequences studied in this project are given below:

- L1 – Ac₋₁₀₁DHHLAHIVVDAIAHASEDRR₁₂₀ (BigR4)
- L2 – Ac₋₁₀₁DHALAHIVVDAIAHASEDRR₁₂₀ (mutant 1)
- L3 – Ac₋₁₀₁DHHLAHIVVDAIAAASEDRR₁₂₀ (mutant 2)
- L4 – Ac₋₁₁₆DHHLAHIVLDAVAHAGEDAI₁₃₅ (SmtB)

Like in other metal-sensitive proteins, domains are composed *i.e.* of carbocyclic acid and imidazole containing side chains [4,5]. The study points out the specificity of metal-ligand interaction and describes the effect of mutations on the coordination properties of studied systems. Stabilities of zinc(II) complexes were determined by potentiometry and coordination sites were determined by NMR experiments and DFT calculations. The comparison of complex stabilities reveals that the Zn(II)-BigR4 species are more stable than the Zn(II)-SmtB complexes, and His mutations strongly affect the stability of complexes and coordination modes of the metal ion [5]. Exchanging one of the histidines into alanine causes, surprisingly, an increase in the stability of zinc(II) complexes with the studied domain (L2), which was confirmed by potentiometric and DFT methods (Figure 1). This work can be considered as a bioinorganic introduction to the search for new strategies in *M. tuberculosis* treatment based on zinc(II)-sensitive mechanisms in bacterial cell survival.

Figure 1. Postulated coordination of zinc(II) in L1 - Ac-₁₀₁DHHLAHIVVDAIAHASEDRR₁₂₀ (A) and L2 - Ac-₁₀₁DHAHLAHIVVDAIAHASEDRR₁₂₀ (B) complexes at physiological pH (7.20). In both cases, three imidazole groups are involved; in L1 to complete tetrahedral coordination water molecule is bound; in the case of L2, involvement of Glu and Asp residues has been observed.

Acknowledgement: Financial support by the National Science Centre (UMO-2017/26/D/ST5/00372) is gratefully acknowledged.

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Copper removal from A β peptide: when less ligand is better and Zn helps

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Alzheimer disease (AD) is the most common neurodegenerative disease in the elderly [1] and it is characterized by β -amyloid peptide (A β) deposits in the brain constituting the senile plaques [2]. The causes of AD are still not clearly identified but several evidences highlight the involvement of metal ions in its pathogenesis and indeed it has been shown that A β peptide possesses the ability to bind Cu, Zn and Fe [3, 4]. When bound to A β peptide, Cu do keep the propensity to produce reactive oxygen species (ROS) and these ROS contribute to the overall increase of the oxidative stress linked to the development of the disease [3].

Many therapeutic approaches are currently developed to aid fighting against AD, one of them targeting the redox active Cu ions. A large range of chemical families has been investigated to remove Cu (mainly Cu(II)) from A β including multi-targeting drugs [5-7]. Along this research line, we report in the present communication the use of a phenanthroline-based peptide like ligand [8] which is able to withdraw Cu from A β and redox silence it in a very stable 4N Cu(II) binding site (Figure 1) even in the presence of Zn [9].

Figure 1. Upper: Chemical structure of the Cu(II)L and Cu(I)L₂ complexes. Lower: Schematic of the proposed mechanism showing the ability of L to remove Cu from Cu(A β) and redox silence it, thus preventing Cu(A β)-induced ROS production, and the effect of excess ligand lessening such effect that it is overcome by the presence of Zn.

In addition and in contrast to what is usually observed, the presence of excess of L do lessen the searched effect of ROS production prevention but it is counterbalanced by the co-presence of Zn [Figure 1, 9]. To explain such unprecedented trends we proposed a mechanism that involves the redox reaction between Cu(II)L and Cu(I)L₂. Our data highlight how speciation and redox chemistry can weaken the effect of a ligand that would have appeared perfectly suitable if only tested in 1:1 ratio and on CuAβ and how working in biological relevant conditions (presence of Zn) is important for the understanding of all the reactions at play.

Acknowledgements

CH and CE thank the ERC aLzINK - Contract n° 638712 for financial support. RBMS thanks CONACYT for the PhD grant 439618.

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Anticancer potency of novel organometallic Ir(III) complexes with phosphines derived from fluoroquinolones encapsulated in polymeric micelles

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Cancers are now considered to be one of the most threatening diseases for humanity in recent decades [1]. Lots of anticancer drugs are currently used in clinical treatment, but over 50% of them are platinum-based anticancer medicines. However, they still cause many side effects (*e.g.*, hair loss, kidney/liver damage *etc.*), and many types of cancer show resistance to classic drugs [2,3]. These disadvantages encourage developing new alternative transition metal-based antitumor agents. The iridium(III) organometallic complexes have been rising stars and possess some unique properties such as potential redox features, universal structure, and wide range of ligand substitution rates, higher cellular uptake efficiency, large Stokes shifts and lower toxicity [4,5,6,7].

Scheme 1. Scheme of cytotoxic action mechanism of Ir(III) complexes.

Novel half-sandwich iridium(III) complexes with aminomethyl(diphenyl)phosphine derived from fluoroquinolones (**IrPCp**, **IrPSf**, **IrPLm**, **IrPNr**) were being studied as possible anticancer chemotherapeutics with potency higher than that of the other well-known metal-based agents *i.e.*, Pt(II) drugs. All compounds were characterized by elemental analysis, selected spectroscopic methods (*i.e.*, absorption and fluorescence spectroscopies, NMR), ESI-MS spectrometry, X-ray diffractometry, and electrochemical techniques. Furthermore, Pluronic P-123 micelles loaded with selected Ir(III) complexes were prepared to overcome low solubility and by providing the complex in a controlled manner to minimize serious systemic side effects. The resulting nanoformulations (**IrPCp_M**, **IrPNr_M**) facilitated efficient drug accumulation inside human lung adenocarcinoma and human prostate carcinoma (A549 and DU-145 cell lines), demonstrated by confocal microscopy and ICP-MS analysis. Studied complexes exhibited promising cytotoxicity *in vitro* with IC₅₀ values significantly lower than the reference drug – cisplatin. To get the insight over the mechanism of action, the role of ROS generation, responsible for the cytotoxicity of the complexes, has been tested. While, the fluorescence spectroscopic data (CT-DNA titration, *in vitro* cell staining) together with analysis of DNA fragmentation (pBR322 plasmid) provided clear evidence for the interactions with DNA. Precise cytometric analysis proved predominance of apoptosis in induced cell death. *In vitro* cytotoxicity assay was also carried out within multicellular tumour spheroids and efficient anticancer action on these 3D assemblies was demonstrated.

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Acknowledgements:

The authors gratefully acknowledge financial support from the Polish National Science Centre (Grant 2020/37/N/ST4/02698). The UV-Vis measurements were carried out with the equipment purchased thanks to the financial support of the Polish National Science Centre (Grant 2016/23/D/ST5/00269).

Study of the structure-activity relationships (SAR) of a family of half-sandwich Ir(III) complexes

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Iridium half-sandwich complexes with anticancer activity have aroused considerable interest among the scientific community [1-3]. They have been extensively studied not only as DNA binders but also as mitochondrial targeting anticancer drugs. DNA-binding cytotoxic drugs are the first choice in the treatment of many cancers, although mechanism of drug resistance such as reduction of drugs accumulation inside cancer cells, increase in the intracellular thiol levels, enhanced DNA repair mechanism are difficult to circumvent [4-5]. In this context, mitochondria seems to be promising targets in the design of new anticancer drugs since its polarized membrane can retain lipophilic cations and its functionality is altered in cancer cells [6]. Targeting tumour mitochondria may promote an oxidative stress response that induce tumour cell demise. However, the challenge is to be able to proceed selectively. It should be notice that cancers cannot evade a treatment that disturbs mitochondria, which are essential for tumour progression.

Herein, we present a structure-activity relationships (SAR) study of eight half-sandwich Ir(III)-Cp* complexes bearing different arylbenzazole ligands. Their behaviour in solution (solubility, replacement of the chloride leaving group by water or DMSO, global charge, acid dissociation constants...) as well as their antiproliferative potential against a battery of human cell lines were studied. Then, their potential biological targets were explored in order to shed some light on the underlying mechanism of action. Finally, the *in vivo* behaviour in mice of the most cytotoxic complex was also investigated.

Hence, this study highlights that small differences in the structure can cause critical changes in both their physicochemical properties and biological mechanism of action. Since we have shown that differences in one or two atoms affect their biological properties, DNA binding or mitochondria dysfunction of this family of complexes.

Acknowledgements: We acknowledge “la Caixa” Foundation (LCF/PR/PR12/11070003), Ministerio de Ciencia Innovación y Universidades-FEDER (RTI2018-102040-B-100) and Junta de Castilla y León-FEDER (BU305P18) for financial support. We are indebted to the group of Dr. G. Espino and especially to Dr. Marta Martínez-Alonso (Universidad de Burgos, Spain) for providing the Ir (III) complexes for this study.

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A comprehensive study on the human serum albumin binding of half-sandwich organoruthenium and organorhodium complexes

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In the research field of anticancer metal complexes ruthenium compounds NAMI-A, KP1019, NKP1339 (BOLD-100) and recently the Ru(II)-containing TLD-1433 have entered into clinical trials [1-3]. Half-sandwich Ru(II)- η^6 -arene complexes are extensively investigated, since the reduced forms of clinically relevant Ru(III) drug candidates were proposed to exert the anticancer effect [4].

Complexes of Ru(II)(η^6 -*p*-cymene) and Rh(III)(η^5 -C₅Me₅) bearing a bidentate ligand (see figure) are widely studied, and recently numerous organometallic compounds were synthesized and tested against human cancer cells. Initially, DNA was suggested as primary target of half-sandwich complexes as well, however, attention directed soon to intra- and extracellular protein targets [5,6]. Proteins have a crucial role in the transport and mode of action of metal-based drugs pointing out the importance of studying metal complex – protein interactions in order to understand their pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic behavior.

Binding to transport proteins e.g. to human serum albumin (HSA) may have an important effect on the distribution, metabolism and excretion of a metal complex. HSA binding of anticancer agents

can be advantageous due to the enhanced permeability and retention effect in solid tumor tissues resulting in the accumulation of protein bound drugs close to the cancer cells. On the other hand, an irreversible protein binding may be responsible for adverse effects and can decrease effective drug concentration as well.

Our recent studies focused on the HSA binding of a set of half-sandwich Ru(II)- and Rh(III)-complexes [8-10], namely Ru(II)(η^6 -*p*-cymene) and Rh(III)(η^5 -C₅Me₅) complexes formed with bidentate (O,O), (O,N) and (N,N) donor ligands. These complexes have different thermodynamic stability, lipophilicity and kinetic lability (see figure). Among them, Ru(II)(η^6 -*p*-cymene) and Rh(III)(η^5 -C₅Me₅) complexes of 8-hydroxyquinoline derivatives and Rh(III)(η^5 -C₅Me₅)(1,10-phenantroline) showed remarkable *in vitro* cytotoxic effect in various cancer cell lines (*e.g.* in MES-SA, MES-SA/Dx5, MCF-7 and multidrug resistant Colo320 cells) [7,8]. Studies were implemented by various spectroscopic and separation techniques (see figure).

Herein we provide a comprehensive picture on the kinetic aspects, binding strength, binding mode and location of HSA binding of these complexes [8-10]. Our studies have shown that lower stability, labile complexes bind in dissociative manner to HSA (via the liberation of the bidentate ligand), while highly stable and/or kinetically inert complexes display preferably associative binding in the protein. High variability applies in the kinetics of protein binding which depends both on the nature of the ligand and the organometallic moiety. In general, Ru(II)(η^6 -*p*-cymene) complexes bind in lower extent to HSA compared to their Rh(III)(η^5 -C₅Me₅) congeners. Moreover, binding affinity towards hydrophobic binding pockets shows correlation with the lipophilicity along with the actual charge of the respective complexes. Studies with amino acid side chain models revealed that His imidazoles are likely coordinating sites in proteins for these complexes, ligand exchange and ternary complex formation occur depending on the stability of the metal complexes. Besides, low molecular mass constituents of blood (*e.g.* histidine, cysteine, methionine, citric acid) seem to interfere with HSA binding of these complexes.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the ÚNKP-20-5 – New National Excellence Program of the Ministry for Innovation and Technology from the source of the National Research, Development and Innovation Fund and through projects GINOP-2.3.215-2016-00038, FK 124240 and Ministry of Human Capacities, Hungary grant, TKP-2020.

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Interaction of model antibiotics with calixarene-based micellar aggregates: an ITC study

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The employment of drug delivery systems (DDSs) for the entrapment of target molecules is an emerging strategy used to improve the therapeutic efficacy of a drug. For example, old generation antibiotics may benefit from the interaction with suitable nanocarriers for overcoming problems associated with antibiotic resistance [1].

Polycationic calixarene derivatives able to self-assemble in nanoaggregates are promising novel nanocontainers for the delivery of antibiotics to bacteria due to their ability to establish electrostatic interactions with the negatively charged bacterial membranes [2]. In particular, a polycationic calix[4]arene amphiphile, CholineC4dod, bearing choline groups and dodecyl aliphatic chains at the cavity upper and lower rim respectively, proved to be a promising nanocarrier for drug delivery [3].

Despite the general interest in the study of drug-micelle interactions, a quantitative analysis of the species, binding affinity as well as thermodynamic parameters for the recognition/inclusion of a drug with(in) micellar assemblies has rarely been addressed. However, the determination of the strength and nature of these interactions is crucial for the design of novel medicines as well as for the modification or selection of suitable shuttles for target-oriented drug delivery.

The present work deals with the study of the binding features of polycationic calix[4]arene derivatives (CholineC4dod, MedeaC4dod and MedeaC4prop) with ofloxacin, chloramphenicol or tetracycline (**Figure 1**) in neutral aqueous solution for investigating the capability of micellar aggregates to recognize and host three old generation antibiotics. These molecules were selected as models of antibiotics affected by the onset of resistance phenomena with the aim of offering a contribution to the design and development of effective DDSs for the repurposing of old-fashioned drugs.

The examination of solution equilibria and the determination of the binding parameters in neutral aqueous solution were carried out using nano-isothermal titration calorimetry, an invaluable technique for determining both stability constant and enthalpy change values for host-guest complex formation [4] and/or self-organization of surfactants into micelles by a single experiment [5,6]. ITC experiments provided key information on the forces driving the molecular recognition processes: the formation of the chloramphenicol-micelle adduct was found to be enthalpically driven, whereas entropy drives the formation of the adducts with both ofloxacin and tetracycline. The picture obtained by ITC results about the positioning of the antibiotics within the micellar backbone was also supported by NMR experiments [7].

Figure 1. (A) From left to right: MedeaC4prop, MedeaC4dod, CholineC4dod; **(B)** from left to right: ofloxacin, tetracycline hydrochloride, chloramphenicol.

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Microspeciation analysis of azacyclophanes by means of NMR data fitting with GEMS

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The determination of protonation constants is a task of major importance in Chemistry.[1] For polyprotic species, with more than one protonation centre, there are several protonation constants which contain information about the degree of protonation but not on where the protons are located within the structure of the molecule. The resolution of the microspeciation can sometimes be useful, but it is not an easy task because not all analytical techniques convey information about the individual protonation sites. Usually, NMR titration data is the preferred tool for the job because a correspondence can be assigned between the nucleus that is shifting and the centre that is being protonated in each step.[2] We have carried out NMR titration of a set of three azamacrocycles and analysed the data with GEMS, a piece of software which implements Cluster Expansion Techniques[3] and Symmetry Simplification[4] and allows the fitting of the protonation microconstants and the resolution of the microspeciation. We present the protonation scheme of these azamacrocycles and validate the results obtained with additional techniques.

Figure 1: Microspeciation of the 3, 6, 9-triaza-1-(1, 3)-benzena-cyclodecaphane. (Top) Species distribution (solid line) and protonation centres population (marks). (Bottom) protonation microconstants and microspecies population.

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Properties of Cu²⁺ and Ga³⁺ NOTA-monoamide complexes

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Some metal radioisotopes, e.g. ⁶⁴Cu²⁺ and ⁶⁸Ga³⁺, are key components of promising probes for cancer diagnosis or treatment. The metal ions cannot be used as their aqua complexes because of their non-specific distribution in tissues. Therefore, the metal ions have to be bound in a thermodynamically stable and a kinetic inert complex. The most suitable ligands for these purposes are derivatives of polyazamacrocycles. Their complexes are commonly used as experimental contrast agents but chemical properties some of them have been poorly investigated.

Currently, NOTA-monoamides are the most commonly used NOTA-based ligands in molecular imaging. However, their complexes have not been investigated. Two NOTA-monoamides (**1** and **2**) were prepared (**Figure**). Acid-base and coordination properties were investigated by potentiometry. Replacement of a carboxylic pendant arm by amide group caused a decrease of overall ligand basicity and, consequently, values of stability constants were decreased by several orders of magnitude if compared to those of NOTA [1]. Formation and dissociation kinetics of Cu²⁺ complexes were investigated by stopped-flow UV-VIS spectroscopy. Acid-assisted decomplexation (3 M HClO₄) of Cu²⁺ complexes was slower comparing to the Cu²⁺-NOTA complex. The Ga³⁺ complexes were investigated by NMR. Amide bond in the [Ga(**2**)]⁺ complex was hydrolysed to [Ga(**3**)] even in slightly basic solution due to coordination of the carbonyl group. At pH 4–7, [Ga(**1**)]⁺ complex is coordinated in N₃O₃ mode. At pH>7, amide nitrogen atom [Ga(**1**)]⁺ deprotonates and binds to Ga³⁺ ion. It significantly increases thermodynamic stability of the complex. Complex structures were confirmed by X-ray diffraction.

Results show that NOTA primary monoamide are suitable ligands for *in vivo* utilization unlike the secondary amide derivatives.

This work was carried out in frame of CA18202-NECTAR COST Action and was supported by the Ministry of Education (INTER-COST LTC20044).

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Luminescent Eu(III) complexes as probes for citrate sensing in complex matrix

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Rationally designed Eu(III) complexes can be exploited as probes in the detection of important analytes in biological fluids, by means of luminescence.[1] These complexes must be stable in aqueous solution, absorb and efficiently transfer the UV excitation to the metal ion (*antenna effect*). We succeeded to obtain this goal by including isoquinoline *antenna* into the ligand backbone. In fact, the luminescence of [Eu(bisoQcd)]⁺ and Eu(isoQC3A) (Figure 1) complexes significantly increases in the presence of the main analytes which constitute the interstitial extracellular fluid (*i.e.* hydrogen carbonate, serum albumin (SA) and citrate at their typical concentration).[2,3]

Figure 1. Molecular structure of the Eu(III) complexes

The optical response of our Eu(III)-based probes is selective towards citrate molecule, when a complex matrix is considered. Citrate molecule is a very important bio-analyte and since it is involved in many metabolic pathway, the monitoring of its concentration is crucial in order to identify the presence of metabolic disease.[4] When a simulated interstitial extracellular fluid is employed, the change of the citrate concentration gives rise to an increase of the Eu(III) luminescence emission intensity of [Eu(bisoQcd)]⁺ (Figure 2). On the other hand, negligible or no change of the luminescence intensity was detected when the concentration of both hydrogen carbonate and SA is changed. Such a finding opens up the possibility to determine quantitatively the citrate anion in complex matrices up to concentrations of 500 μ M.

Figure 2. Eu(III) complex suitable for citrate sensing

Actually, all the main analytes present in this biological fluid show a similar affinity for the Eu(III) complexes and directly interact with the metal ion displacing a variable number of water molecules from the inner coordination sphere. As well known, this phenomenon produces a peculiar increase of the luminescence intensity stemming from Eu(III). Differently than hydrogen carbonate and SA, we demonstrate that citrate is capable to displace a higher number of water molecules giving a distinctive increase of the luminescence intensity. Moreover, the Eu(III) intrinsic quantum yield of the adduct is higher.

The obtained results candidate our europium complexes as viable probes for luminescence analysis of biofluids with complex matrix.

Acknowledgments: The authors thank the Italian Ministry of education, university and research for the received funds (PRIN (Progetti di Ricerca di Rilevante Interesse Nazionale) project "CHIRALAB", grant n. 20172M3K5N).

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Tuning the physicochemical properties of fluorescent sensors

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The design of fluorescent sensors with fine-tuned physicochemical properties that respond to different analytes with high selectivity and fast response are paramount in several fields namely in biotechnology, medicinal chemistry and environmental sciences.[1]

Among the many optical sensors, fluorescent sensors are particularly important due to the highly sensitive, rapid, simple and real-time monitoring. Moreover, fluorescence-based sensors can be used to readily detect low metal ion levels without the need for sophisticated instrumentation or time-consuming sample preparation. The fluorescence quantum yield (before and after the addition of the analyte), the ligand chelating ability and sensitivity are determinant parameters to be considered when evaluating the efficiency of a new sensor.

Aiming to design fine-tuned fluorescent sensors that interact mainly with metal ions, herein we describe several fluorescent-chelator conjugates by combining different classes of fluorescent molecules with diverse structural features (like size, solubility, lipophilicity and fluorescence quantum yield) with selected chelating units (including pyridyl, catechol and 3-hydroxy-4-pyridinone) that present high affinity for M(II) and M(III) but distinct pK_a values. [2-7] The immobilization of fluorescent sensors in a polymeric support or matrix is also an important goal aiming to create hybrid materials with suitable mechanical properties and as a strategy to reduce the tendency of most fluorescent molecules to aggregate, providing an ideal environment for the analyte detection.[8]

Figure 1: Fluorescent hybrid material: PET membrane with a fluorescent ‘turn-on’ sensor for iron (III) sensing.

Acknowledgements: This work received financial support from PT national funds (FCT/MCTES, Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia and Ministério da Ciência, Tecnologia e Ensino Superior) through the project UIDB/50006/2020, PTDC/QUI-QIN/28142/2017, PTDC/QUI-QOR/29426/2017. A. M. G. Silva and A. Leite thank FCT for funding through program DL 57/2016 – Norma transitória.

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HNBO-based ligands as selective sensors for Mg(II)

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Magnesium is the most abundant divalent cation within cells and one of the main ions in the body, playing crucial roles in many physiological processes. Both too high or too low Mg(II) concentrations may be deleterious to plants and animals, food and water Mg(II) contamination being for instance associated with the occurrence of serious diseases [1,2]. The development of simple and fast systems for the detection of magnesium in different matrices is a highly desirable task. In this view, fluorescent chemosensors represent a suitable approach to the selective determination of Mg(II), being especially attractive when showing selectivity towards Ca(II) ions. A new series of chemosensors containing the 2-(2'-hydroxy-3'-naphthyl)-4-methylbenzoxazole (HNBO) fluorogenic unit [3] featuring selectivity for magnesium was synthesized and characterized (Figure 1). Molecules **L1-L3** bear either distinct amine guest-binding sites or a different number of HNBO fragments, representing similar systems with growing structural complexity. Notably, all compounds showed a selective fluorescent response for Mg(II) over alkaline and alkaline-earth ions in DMSO solution. Moreover, **L3** is able to sense Mg(II) also in ACN solution, with a more efficient response compared to alkaline, alkaline-earth and some first row transition metal ions. Interestingly, the three compounds show a trend in their fluorescent response in ACN: while **L3** is able to sense Mg(II) over all other metal ions tested, **L2** shows only a moderate specificity for Mg(II) over alkaline and alkaline-earth ions but a higher response to Zn(II) and Cd(II), and **L1** mostly senses Zn(II) and Cd(II).

Figure 1: The ligands presented in this contribution.

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Multi-sensing-spot device for smart colorimetric measurements of pH from 1 to 13

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pH is a key target parameter in a broad range of applications from environmental to industrial and biomedical [1] since chemical and biological properties of many substances are dependent on the pH of their mediums, like solubility of metals, the toxicity of some species and chemical reactions rate. [2]. Therefore, measuring pH in various environments represents a crucial analytical task.

Glass pH electrode is universally known as the principal pH measurement tool, and it is currently employed in laboratories, factories, hospitals, and so on. [3] However, glass pH electrode has few disadvantages, like the size, rigid design, fragility, unsuitability for long-term monitoring or small sample volumes. [1]

pH measures based on colorimetric methods have been proposed to overcome these limitations. More recently, optical pH sensors, based on pH indicators as receptors, have recently emerged as a new trend, inspired by traditional pH paper. While the traditional pH paper provides a basic estimation of pH states via a simple and convenient operation, it is not reversible. In addition, it does not show an accurate pH value for a target analyte. [3] Optical pH sensors are more advanced than pH papers since they can be operated reversibly and can be calibrated to output an accurate pH value.

In the last years, countless optical pH sensors have been proposed, divided into generalized or specific for a pH range or an application. Although one advantage of using pH sensors over the pH electrodes is to operate also at the extremes of the pH scale, only few optical pH sensors have been reported for use in these regions. [4]. Furthermore, detection is usually performed by UV-Vis spectroscopy or fluorescence, while extensive data treatment, complex algorithms or smartphone applications are always required for colorimetric detection.

In this scenario, we developed a 3x4 multi-sensing-spots device exploiting a panel of pH indicators, covering a wide pH range, ideally 0-14, covalently bound to ethylene-vinyl alcohol (EVOH) copolymer. Some of these receptors have already been employed to develop smart labels for high-protein foods, both embedded in cellulose-based tissue [5-7] and bound to EVOH [8,9]. After that, we expanded the selection of the dyes to cover a wide pH range, considering that a shift to higher $\log K_a$ values of around one unit is observed after functionalization.

Functionalisation was performed according to the patented synthetic pathway [10-11], then raw material was pressed, and miniaturized sensors were cut from the films. One sensing spot per each pH indicator was poked with a needle, and a thread was put through the hole to anchor the sensor on a netted plastic support in a fixed position. The final device is shown in Figure 1a.

When dipped in solutions at various pH, the sensing spots assumed a coloration related to the pH of the medium: combining a large number of pH indicators, with different $\log K_a$ values, a broad pH range, from 1 to 13, could be measured.

Once dipped in test solutions, our multi-sensing-spots device allowed multiple levels of interpretation. Firstly, by naked-eye comparison between the device and the reference colors, the pH range is easily evaluated. Secondly, a multi-techniques chemometric model was developed to calculate the exact pH value, starting from the RGB triplet of each sensing spot. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is performed to estimate sample pH range and thus informative receptors, as shown in Figure 1b. For improving sensitivity and sensing performances, three Partial Least Square regression (PLS) models are developed (acidic pH in red, neutral pH in green and alkaline pH in violet) aiming to calculate the exact pH of the samples, basing only on the informative receptors in pH range of interest.

In conclusion, the proposed device allows colorimetric detection of pH, both by naked-eye and multivariate approach, in a wide pH range from 1 to 13. Moreover, it is here presented as a generalized device, but it can be tailored for specific pH ranges and application a priori, selecting only the receptors that turn their color in the pH range of interest.

Figure 1: Picture of the final multi-sensing-spot device (a). Score plot on the first two components of the PCA model: red, green, and violet areas identify three pH ranges, in which the same receptors are informative, and thus a common reduced PLS model is used to calculate pH.

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Interaction between platinum group metal ions and novel ambidentate (N,N) and (O,O) chelating ligands in aqueous solution

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Cisplatin and other square planar Pt(II) complexes have been using successfully in the chemotherapy of cancer for decades but in addition to them only a few promising metal-containing agents have been developed (KP1019, NAMI A etc.). However, the number of selective drug candidates might increase significantly by using hypoxia-activated cobalt(III) complexes.

Hypoxia present in cancer tissues is a remarkable difference from normoxic conditions in healthy, untransformed cells enabling the development of metal complexes that are selectively activated under hypoxic conditions. The inert Co(III) form can act namely as a chaperon carrying a biologically active ligand and in the more reductive environment of the cancer tissue via selective reduction and subsequent dissociation of the Co(II) species formed, targeted release of the active biomolecule can be achieved. With the use of ambidentate chelating ligands, beside Co(III), a second metal ion with proven anticancer potential (e.g. platinum group metal (PGM) ions) can also be incorporated into the molecule resulting in heterobimetallic complexes [1,2]. To achieve metal ion selectivity ambidentate ligands having chelating donor atom sets with different hard-soft character are desired.

Therefore during our research we have synthesized various hydroxypyridinone derivatives of maltol utilizing well-known literature methods [3]. Then from these amines we have developed and synthesized new Schiff-base compounds and their reduced derivatives with the help of 2-pyridinecarboxaldehyde (H(L3), Fig. 1) and pyrrole-2-carboxaldehyde (H(L5), Fig. 1). Using these new ligands equilibrium studies have been carried out in the presence of Pd(II), $[(\eta^6\text{-}p\text{-cym})\text{Ru}]^{2+}$ and $[(\eta^5\text{-Cp}^*)\text{Rh}]^{2+}$ ($p\text{-cym}$ = 1-methyl-4-isopropylbenzene, Cp^* = pentamethyl-cyclopentadienyl anion) to explore the ligands acid-base and metal ion binding characteristics.

Pd(II) was found to form precipitate with these ligands hindering subsequent solution studies. Our results suggest that L3 is a less efficient (N,N) chelator for $[(\eta^6\text{-}p\text{-cym})\text{Ru}]^{2+}$ and $[(\eta^5\text{-Cp}^*)\text{Rh}]^{2+}$ than L5 (Fig. 1). Similarly, the relative effectivity of the (O,O) and (N,N) chelates (relative order of their conditional stability constants) determines that L5 coordinates in a (N,N) manner to $[(\eta^6\text{-}p\text{-cym})\text{Ru}]^{2+}$ and $[(\eta^5\text{-Cp}^*)\text{Rh}]^{2+}$ in the whole pH range studied at 1:1 ratio while for L3 the complexation starts with (O,O) coordination. At 2:1 metal ion to ligand ratio L3 cannot hinder the intensive hydrolysis of the second metal ion although a small amount of 2:1 complex with rhodium can be detected.

Based on the results of this solution study, out of L5 and L3, the former one seems to be a better ligand to develop Co(III)/PGM heterodinuclear complexes involving (N,N)-chelated PGM and (O,O)-chelated Co(III) metal cores.

Figure 1.: The suggested coordination modes in the $[(\eta^6\text{-}p\text{-cym})\text{Ru}]^{2+}\text{-L3}$ and -L5 systems ($Z = \text{H}_2\text{O}$ or Cl^-).

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Dinuclear Cu₂(μ-EDTA)(2- or 4-apmd)₂ compounds with amino-pyrimidines related to 2-aminopurine or adenine

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Structural knowledge on mixed-ligand copper(II) complexes having 2-aminopurine (H2ap) or adenine (Hade) revealed that the preferred donor of H2ap is N7 [1], in contrast to the fascinating diversity of binding modes for Hade [2,3]. This fact seems to be related to the strategic site of the exocyclic amino group in these aminopurines (see Scheme). Deeping into that, we have synthesized and structurally characterized the compounds [Cu₂(μ-EDTA)(2apmd)₂]_n (**1**), and {[Cu₂(μ-EDTA)(4apmd)₂·4H₂O]_n (**2**) on the basis of a recent molecular recognition study [4].

Scheme 1. Correlation between purine and pyrimidine N-heterocycles.

The two N-heterocyclic donors of 2apmd are equivalent and correspond to the N1 and N3 atoms in purines. The crystal structure of the polymer **1** (293^o C, monoclinic, P2₁/c) consists of fused layers of centro-symmetric dinuclear units. We could anticipate [4] that the asymmetric unit of the crystal (Figure 1) features each half of the binary chelate Cu₂(μ-EDTA) recognizing the 2apmd ligand by means of the cooperation of the Cu1-N1(2apmd) coordination bond (2.021(1) Å) and the intra-molecular interligand N2-H2B...O1(coordinated EDTA) H-bonding interaction (2.755(2) Å, 155.9^o). Note that, in this compound, the bond distances of Cu1-N1(2apmd) and Cu1-N5(EDTA) (2.027(1) Å) are very similar! The N-heterocyclic donors of 4apmd are non-equivalent. In addition, note that the N1 and N3 atoms of 4apmd correspond to the N3 and N1 donors of purines, and the exocyclic amino group in 4apmd

corresponds to the –N(6)H₂ group of adenine. The asymmetric unit of **2** (Figure 2) also shows fused centrosymmetric dinuclear units in layers, which reveal that, in this occasion, the molecular recognition pattern between each half Cu₂(μ-EDTA) and the 4apmd ligand only represents the Cu1-N1(4apmd) bond (1.975(2) Å). Note that this bond is slightly shorter than the Cu1-N7(EDTA) (2.023(2) Å)!

Figure 1. Dinuclear unit in the crystal of [Cu₂(μ-EDTA)(2apmd)₂]_n (**1**).

Figure 2. Dinuclear unit in the crystal of {[Cu₂(μ-EDTA)(4apmd)₂]_n·4H₂O} (**2**) (water molecules have been omitted for clarity).

That last compound exhibits two interesting features. First, the formation of a bond corresponding to the Cu-N3(Hade), with N3 being the N-heterocyclic donor with the lowest basicity of Hade (in terms of proton affinity: N₉>N₁>N₇>N₃>N₆). Second, it seems clear that the formation of a single Cu-N1(4apmd) bond is preferred to the cooperation between Cu-N4(4apmd) bond with an (4apmd)N-H...O(coordinated, EDTA) interligand interaction (as featured in **1**). This can be attributed to the steric hindrance imposed by the exocyclic amino group on the N3(4apmd) atom.

Acknowledgements: Financial support from Projects No. PGC2018-102047-B-I00 (MCIU/AEI/FEDER, UE) and Junta de Andalucía (FQM-283 and FQM-247) is gratefully acknowledged. M.B.-O. also acknowledges support from Cost Action CA18202 (Network for Equilibria and Chemical Thermodynamics Advanced Research). C.R.-M. is grateful by a Collaboration Grant from Ministry of Education and Professional Training (Spain).

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Mechanistic studies on the binding of platinum, palladium and gold complexes with tetradentate aromatic ligands to biosubstrates: different features for different metal centres

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Platinum complexes are studied since the discovery of cisplatin, which is known to produce DNA damages and cell apoptosis [1]. Due to the many similarities between Pt(II) and Pd(II), there is interest in studying Pd(II) complexes as potential anticancer drugs. Given the much faster hydrolysis of Pd(II) complexes with respect to the Pt(II) analogues, there is the need for a very strong nitrogen ligand, able to ensure the reaching of its biological target. Compounds with tetradentate ligands obviate this rapid hydrolysis reaction [2,3]. Another series of metal complexes that have a similar coordination structure to Pt(II) complexes are the Au(III) ones. They generally suffer from stabilization issues, due to their tendency to be easily reduced to Au(I) or Au(0) particles, making the choice of the ligands particularly relevant. Differently from DNA-focused Pt(II) species, Au(III) complexes often preferentially bind proteins [4].

Figure 1. Chemical structure of the studied metal complexes

Here, we present a series of stable four-coordinated complexes of Pt(II), Pd(II) and Au(III), comparing their interaction with poly and oligonucleotides. Natural double-stranded DNA, poly(rA)poly(rU) and poly(rA)2poly(rU) RNAs, DNA G-quadruplexes and a RNA four-way junction are all considered in our

studies. These systems are analysed using different techniques and approaches (spectrophotometric and fluorometric titrations, melting assays, viscosity tests and mass spectrometry). In this contribution, we will present our results, which enlighten the different mode of interaction of the complexes bearing different metal centres.

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A new approach in the critical evaluation of the hydrolysis constant of the Zn²⁺ cation

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In the evaluation of solution equilibria involving a metal cation, the knowledge of the hydrolysis constants is mandatory to assess the correct speciation model and a reliable value for the stability constants to be refined. This means that hydrolysis constants should be known in the same medium and at the same temperature and ionic strength of the system to be investigated. In the literature, great attention has always been paid to this process and many papers and compilation were published in the past. Among them, the book of Baes and Mesmer [1] is the historical reference for any researcher in the field solution equilibria. After Baes and Mesmer, the work of Eckberg and Brown [2] requires great consideration. In that book, the hydrolysis constants are critically analysed determining the temperature dependence at first and, once the value at T = 298.15 K is obtained, its dependence on ionic strength is evaluated according to the SIT model.

In the present contribution, the original data reported in the literature for the zinc hydrolysis constants have been re-analysed taking into account the evaluation criteria reported by Eckberg and Brown and other compilation such as JESS (Joint Expert Speciation System) [3]. The whole process has been based on two approaches: 1) analysing conditional values taking into account different ionic media; 2) using the so called "Pure water model" [4], *i.e.*, transforming the data into a general non-interacting ionic medium to be used in combination with all the weak species (accounted as formation constants) that can be formed in a given solution.

The first approach is used as reference method, the second is based on the assumption that equilibrium constants in any ionic medium are influenced by the formation of weak species occurring between the reactants and the ions of the supporting electrolyte. The correcting equation, based on the solution of the mass balance equation, is:

$$\text{Log } K' = \text{log } K - \text{log } (1 + K^{\text{ZnX}} \cdot [\text{X}]) \quad (1)$$

Where K' is the apparent formation constant in the presence of the competitive ion "X", which forms the weak complex "ZnX" with the metal cation "Zn²⁺" of K^{ZnX} stability, $\text{log } K$ is the corrected (to pure water) stability constant. To make this correction, a set of weak complexes for each molecule is necessary.

The output of this work consists of several sets of parameters for the ionic strength and temperature dependence, related to eq. (2), for zinc hydrolysis constants valid in various ionic media

(*i.e.*, conditional hydrolysis constants) and one set of parameters for the “pure water model” to be used in any ionic medium in combination with all the weak species formed in the solution.

$$\log K_{i,T} = \log K_{i,T}^{0,\theta} - z^* \cdot 0.51 \cdot \text{D.H.} + C \cdot I + F_1(T) \cdot (\Delta H_{i,T}^0 - 1.5 \cdot \text{D.H.} + C' \cdot I + \Delta c_p \cdot \Delta T) \quad (2)$$

$$\text{D.H.} = z^* \cdot I^{0.5} / (1 + 1.5 \cdot I^{0.5}) \quad (2a)$$

$$F_1(T) = 52.23 \cdot (1/\theta - 1/T) \quad (2b)$$

$$z^* = \sum (\text{charges})_{\text{reactants}}^2 - \sum (\text{charges})_{\text{products}}^2 \quad (2c)$$

$$p^* = \sum (\text{Stoic. Coeff.})_{\text{products}} - \sum (\text{Stoic. Coeff.})_{\text{reactants}} \quad (2d)$$

where $\log K_{i,T}$ is the value of the equilibrium constants at any value of ionic strength (I) and temperature (T) in a given range of experimental, $\log K_{i,T}^{0,\theta}$ is the value of the equilibrium constants at infinite dilution ($I = 0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) and at the reference temperature ($T = \theta = 298.15 \text{ K}$); C is an adjustable parameters for the ionic strength dependence of equilibrium constants; $\Delta H_{i,T}^0$ is the enthalpy change of the given species at infinite dilution ($I = 0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) and at the reference temperature ($T = \theta = 298.15 \text{ K}$), C' and Δc_p are adjustable parameters for the ionic strength and temperature dependence of enthalpy changes.

The two approaches are alternatives, but the chemical information carried is the same.

However, while the “conditional dataset” can only be used in the specific ionic medium considered, the “pure water dataset” allows the modelling of Zn^{2+} in any ionic medium containing the ions taken into account by the weak interactions, in every possible combination (*i.e.*, even in mixed media like many real aqueous systems).

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POSTER COMMUNICATIONS

Ternary dinuclear Cu(II) complexes of 1,3-PDTA with imidazole or N-(2-hydroxyethyl)imidazole coligands

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A search in the structural Cambridge Structural Database reveals that the chelating agent 1,3-PDTA act as hexadentate for most first-row transition metal ions (V-Zn), both as M²⁺ (Mn, Co, Ni, Cu or Zn) or M³⁺ (V, Cr, Fe, Co) cations. The bridging μ_2 -mode is also reported for a few Cu(II) complexes for its 1,3-H₂PDTA²⁻, 1,3-HPDTA³⁻ or 1,3-PDTA⁴⁻ anions [1]. We have proved that in the crystal of {[Cu₂(μ_4 -EDTA) (Him)₂·2H₂O]_n (Him = imidazole) intermolecular H-bonds, π -stacking and (water)O-H/ π interactions contribute to the crystal packing [2]. Now we have synthesized and structurally characterized related compounds with Cu(II), 1,3-PDTA and Him or N-(2-hydroxyethyl)imidazole (heim). These N-hetero-cycles are the five-membered moieties of adenine (Hade) or its synthetic nucleoside N9-(2-hydroxyethyl)adenine (heade) [3] respectively (see Scheme below).

Scheme. Formulas of N-heterocyclic ligands Hade and 9heade, and Him and heim.

The 3D-polymer {[Cu₂(1,3-PDTA)(Him)₂·2H₂O]_n (compound **1**, 100 K, tetragonal, P4₃2₁2, R₁ 0.034, Figure 1) consists of a centrosymmetric dinuclear complex unit and non-coordinated water molecules. We can consider that the Cu(II) centre exhibits a rather asymmetrical elongated octahedral coordination, type 4+1+1* [3] (Cu1-N11 1.969(3), Cu1-O12#1 2.273(3), Cu1-O12 2.928(3) Å, #1 = $y-1/2, -x+1/2, z+1/4$). Nonetheless, the distance Cu1...O12 is just the sum of Van der Waals radii (2.92 Å), i.e., just a contact. Therefore, the Cu(II) coordination in **1** could be best referred as a distorted square-base pyramid, type 4+1, with O12#1 as distal donor.

Figure 1. Dinuclear complex unit in the polymeric compound **1**. Non-coordinated water molecules omitted for clarity.

A crystal of $[\text{Cu}_2(\mu\text{-}1,3\text{-PDTA})(\text{heim})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ (compound **2**, Figure 2) has been measured at R.T. and its structure solved (orthorhombic, $\text{Pca}2_1$, final R_1 0.047). The dinuclear molecule shows disorder in the 2-hydroxyethyl arm of one heim ligand. Hence, both Cu(II) centres are non-equivalent even if both exhibit very similar elongated square-base pyramidal coordination, type 4+1, with the distal O-aqua donors at 2.34 Å.

Figure 2. Structure of the dinuclear complex molecule in **2** (disorder of heim on Cu1 omitted).

We conclude that the N-(2-hydroxyethyl) pendant arm of heim favours the molecular structure of **2** and also agrees with the preferred N7-binding mode for this synthetic purine nucleoside, as have been recently reported for $[\text{Cu}_2(\mu\text{-}1,3\text{-EDTA})(\text{heide})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]\cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ [3].

Acknowledgements: Financial support from Project No. PGC2018-102047-B-I00 (MCIU/AEI/FEDER, UE) and Junta de Andalucía (Research groups FQM-283 and FQM-247) is gratefully acknowledged.

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Evaluation by Electrochemical Methods of Iron Chelators for Dopaminergic Neurotoxicity Inhibition in the Parkinson Disease

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Parkinson's disease (PD) is the second most common neurodegenerative disorder after Alzheimer's disease (AD), affecting about 2% of the population aged of more than 65 years worldwide. The evolution of this disease is frequently associated with excessively high levels of localized iron concentrations within the brain and a severe depletion of dopamine (DA) due to the loss of dopaminergic neurones in *substantia nigra pars compacta* (SNpc). Even though DA is an essential neurotransmitter, it leads to the formation of toxic quinones and reactive oxygen species (ROS) which are in close relation with the occurrence and the progress of the PD [1]. The presence of iron may induce the iron catalysed oxidation of DA, which may aggravate the progression of PD by enhancing the accumulation of DA-derived quinones or even the production of strongly oxidizing hydroxyl radicals ($\bullet\text{OH}$). As such, given the increasing iron content of cells on aging, the redox state of iron present and the transformation of iron between the +II and +III oxidation states are considered to be of particular significance in the progression of PD.

Treatments resulting in reduction of the iron content in the diseased brain are generally considered to be a promising approach to disease mitigation considering the possible effect of such treatment in reducing the iron aggravated generation of DA-derived toxic metabolites and ROS. Of all the investigated chelators [2], the small compound, deferiprone (DFP), which is already used as an active ingredient to treat iron overloads actually completed phase 2 clinical trials for PD treatment [3].

Electrochemistry is a versatile analytical tool to probe reactions involving electron transfers. Electrochemistry relates the flow of electrons to chemical changes. Polarography and voltammetry can be considered convenient alternatives to routinely employed analytical methods, in that they present the great advantage of permitting a direct, simple and rapid determination requiring a minimum volume of sample. Electrochemical techniques have also been used for the determination of a wide range of drug compounds. They have the advantage of being non-destructive, not requiring any pre-treatment and they are less sensitive to matrix effects than other analytical techniques [4]. Additionally, electrochemical techniques allow the study of the redox mechanism of the drugs therefore providing insight into their metabolic fate, *in vivo* redox processes and pharmacological activity.

Figure 1. Molecular structures of the 1,2-HOPO iron chelating agents and DFP tested within this study.

A range of novel chelators based on 1-hydroxy-2(1H)-pyridinone (1,2-HOPO) has been prepared (Figure 1) and their iron chelation activity was assessed [5]. Further work has been done to measure the pKa and Fe(III) stability constants of these bidentate chelators by potentiometric and spectrophotometric titrations in order to rationalise their biological function. Herein we are presenting a complementary method which consists in the characterization of the redox behaviour of these promising ligands, as well as of the electronic transfer mechanism of their complexes with iron. Several electrochemical methods have been used (cyclic voltammetry, differential pulse voltammetry and polarography) using a glassy carbon electrode or a dropping mercury electrode and the specific electrode processes were established. The calculated values of the metallic complexes' formation constants and of the corresponding stoichiometries were compared with those obtained by spectropotentiometric techniques.

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Metal binding of the unionized alcoholic group in copper(II) chelates of 1,3-diamine-2-propanol-N,N,N',N'-tetraacetate(4-)

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The chelating behavior of the 1,3-diamino-2-propanol-N,N,N',N'-tetraacetic acid (H₅dapolta) is structurally documented for a large variety of high-valence metal ions, Mⁿ⁺ (n ≥ 3) where its alcoholate group acts as a bridging donor atom within the full-anion dapolta⁵⁻. The same applies to two heterometallic compounds with Ge(IV) and Cu(II) [1] or Zn(II) [2]. In addition, there are a few mononuclear compounds where Co(III) is hexadentately chelated by Hdapolta⁴⁻ with non-dissociated alcoholic group (unbound to the metal) [3]. It seems clear that the formation of the pentavalent anion dapolta⁵⁻ is favored by the coordination of –OH group to Mⁿ⁺ (n ≥ 3) ions. The aim of this work is the preparation and structural characterization of dinuclear chelates 'M₂(Hdapolta⁴⁻)' where the non-dissociated –OH group of the chelator acts as bridging group. To this purpose we have chosen Cu(II) as metal center and we have used the N-heterocyclic coligands imidazole (Him) and N-(2-hydroxyethyl)imidazole.

Herein, the crystal and/or molecular structures of {[Cu₂(μ-Hdapolta)(Him)₂(H₂O)]·5.5H₂O}_n (**1**, Triclinic, P-1, Figure 1), {[Cu₂(μ-Hdapolta)(Him)₂]·4H₂O}_n (**2**, Monoclinic, C2/c, Figure 2) and [Cu₂(μ-Hdapolta)(heim)₂(H₂O)]₂·7H₂O (**3**, Triclinic, P-1, Figure 3) are reported. Compounds **1** and **2** represent two different hydrated forms of the same complex, crystallized at different temperatures in our laboratories (depending on the date of their synthesis).

Figure 1. Fragment of {[Cu₂(μ-Hdapolta)(Him)₂(H₂O)]·5.5H₂O}_n (**1**).

Figure 2. Fragment of the polymer $\{[\text{Cu}_2(\mu\text{-Hdapolta})(\text{Him})_2]\cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}\}_n$ (**2**).

Figure 3. Dinuclear complex molecule of $[\text{Cu}_2(\mu\text{-Hdapolta})(\text{heim})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})]_2\cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (**3**). Non-coordinated water omitted for clarity.

In conclusion, Hdapolta⁴⁻ anion is able to build polymeric or molecular dinuclear complex units, 'Cu₂(Hdapolta)', involving its non-dissociated –OH moiety as a bridging group between two Cu(II) centers. That is attributed to the divalent charge of both metallic centers. Indeed, if one or both metallic centers have trivalent or highest oxidation states, they efficiently increase the acidity of the alcoholic group acting as μ-dapolta⁵⁻ full anion.

Acknowledgements. Financial support from the Research groups FQM283 and FQM247 (Junta de Andalucía) and Research Projects No. PGC2018-102047-B-I00 and CTQ2017-85821-R are gratefully acknowledged. M.B.-O. acknowledges support from Cost Action CA18202—Network for Equilibria and Chemical Thermodynamics Advanced Research.

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Caffeic acid coordination properties towards Eu(III) and Dy(III): a chemical speciation study in aqueous solution

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Representing the 15 elements of the first period of the f-block, the lanthanides are distinguished by high chemical activity. Lanthanide ions associated with organic ligands form interesting complexes in terms of biological and physicochemical properties, being widely used in several applications such as catalysis, fluorescence imaging, molecular biology research and microscopy, and on medical applications as well, as diagnostics tools.[1] Furthermore, many studies revealed that lanthanide complexes present good antibacterial and antiviral activity.[2]

Phenolic acids, which are naturally present in our daily lives, are aromatic acids composed of at least one carboxylic and one phenolic hydroxylic functional group. They can be classified into two categories according to the number of carbon atoms: i) benzoic acids, containing seven carbon atoms (C₆+C₁), and cinnamic acids, comprising nine carbon atoms (C₆+C₃).[3]

Interestingly, several hydroxycinnamic acids have shown high antibacterial and anti-inflammatory properties, leading to their use in many pharmacological applications. One of the most common hydroxycinnamic acids is caffeic acid ((E)-3-(3,4-dihydroxyphenyl)-2-propenoic acid, *Caf*), being found in the extracts of many plant products such as coffee, apples, potatoes, spinach, as well as in olive oil and wine [4]. Caffeic acid has been widely studied due to its strong antioxidant and antibacterial properties.[2] Furthermore, its coordination properties have been studied towards several metal ions, as Al³⁺, Fe³⁺, Zn²⁺, Cu²⁺, Cd²⁺ and (CH₃)₂Sn²⁺ [5-9], evidencing a synergic effect of the metal coordination on the antimicrobial and anti-oxidant activity when comparing free ligand with metal complexes.

With all this in mind, we started an investigation on the chemical speciation of caffeic acid in the presence of lanthanides in aqueous solution, targeting a later stage study of caffeic acid – lanthanides complexes as anti-microbial or anti-proliferative agents as well as anti-oxidants with potential

application on food industry. Following this line, the aim of the work here presented is the study of the chelating properties of caffeic acid towards Eu^{3+} and Dy^{3+} cations, in aqueous solution. Chemical speciation studies have been performed in KCl aqueous solutions at $I = 0.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $T = 298.15 \text{ K}$ by ISE- H^+ (glass electrode) potentiometric and UV/Vis spectrophotometric titrations. The coordination behavior and the sequestering ability and selectivity of caffeic acid towards dysprosium and europium are compared and discussed. [10]

Acknowledgement: This contribution was financed by the National Science Centre, Poland under the research project number 2018/29/B/NZ9/01997, the program ERASMUS+ “Aide à la Mobilité Internationale”, and is based upon work from COST Action CA18202, NECTAR – Network for Equilibria and Chemical Thermodynamics Advanced Research, supported by COST (European Cooperation in Science and Technology).

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On the adsorption ability of bovine serum albumin-based aggregates towards Pb²⁺ ions

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In this study, protein aggregates of the bovine serum albumin (BSA) have been tested as adsorbent material for the removal of lead(II) ions from aqueous solutions. Kinetic adsorption experiments were carried out in two different ionic media (NaCl and NaCl/NaNO₃) at fixed ionic strength (0.1 mol L⁻¹), pH ~ 5 and at T = 298.15 K. The dependence of the adsorption ability on ionic medium, pH and temperature have been evaluated carrying out batch isotherm experiments at different experimental conditions. Both kinetic and equilibrium experiments were carried out by using the differential pulse anodic stripping voltammetry (DP-ASV) technique to measure the metal ion concentration of the solutions. Different kinetic (pseudo-first order, pseudo-second order, pseudo generic order and double-exponential) and isotherm (Langmuir and Freundlich) models were used to fit experimental data.

Figure 1. Adsorption of Pb²⁺ ions onto BSA aggregates.

The thermodynamic parameters (ΔG , ΔH and ΔS) of Pb²⁺ adsorption process were calculated by using Gibbs and van't Hoff equations. In order to test the reusability of the adsorbent material, four Pb²⁺

adsorption-desorption cycles were done in column by using a metal ion ($C_{Pb^{2+}} \approx 30 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$) solution at $I = 0.1 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ (NaNO_3), $\text{pH} \sim 5$ and at $T = 298.15 \text{ K}$ and, as extracting solution, EDTA 0.1 mol L^{-1} .

The results showed that the ionic medium, the pH and the temperature of the metal ion solution affect the adsorption capacity and the kinetic of adsorption of BSA aggregates towards Pb^{2+} ions. The higher adsorption value was obtained at $\text{pH} = 5.0$ and without ionic medium and at $T = 283.15 \text{ K}$ ($q_m = 211.3 \text{ mg g}^{-1}$). An adsorption mechanism mainly based on ionic exchange was hypothesized.

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Comparison of transition metal complexes of Tau (326-333) mutants

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Neurodegenerative tauopathies are associated with the accumulation of amyloid- β aggregates in senile plaques and hyperphosphorylated tau protein in neurofibrillary tangles [1-2]. Great number of publications supports that metal ions play an important role in the development of neurodegeneration [3-6]. It is generally accepted that the aggregation process of Tau as well as the formation of toxic deposits are promoted by the hyperphosphorylation of the protein and metal ions have a significant impact on this process.

The histidine imidazole nitrogens are frequent binding sites in proteins. Tau protein is relatively rich in this residue. The histidyl sites are well-separated, thus any of them can act as an anchoring site. One field of our present research work is the systematic investigation of Tau protein. The 12 histidyl residues of the protein are in different chemical environment, so it is safe to assume that their metal binding properties – at least slightly – differ.

The (326-333) octapeptide fragment of Tau protein, Ac-GNIHHKPG-NH₂ contains two histidyl residues in adjacent positions. Previously the characterization of the copper(I) and copper(II) complexes of the R3 fragments has also been published [7], where the Tau (323-335) peptide was the model for the R3 domain. In this case only mononuclear complexes with 1:1 stoichiometry have been suggested to form. The involvement of both histidine residues has been supposed: His329 and His330 coordinating in the equatorial and axial positions, respectively. The question is, whether the presence and coordination of two histidine in R3 fragment results in higher metal binding ability than that of 1-histidine containing N-terminal fragments (Tau (9-16), Tau (26-33)) [8]. Another interesting question is whether the presence of proline residue (well-known as a breakpoint for amide coordination) prevents the coordination of two metal ions. In order to answer these questions the interaction of copper(II), nickel(II) and zinc(II) ions with the native sequence as well as its 1- and 2-histidine mutants (Ac-GNGHAKPG-NH₂, Ac-GNGAHKPG-NH₂, Ac-GNGHHKPG-NH₂ and Ac-GNIHHKAG-NH₂) was studied by means of pH potentiometric titration, UV-Vis spectrophotometry and CD spectroscopy.

The comparison of the copper(II) complexes of the 2-histidine mutants revealed that the replacement of isoleucine to glycine has no significant impact on the stability of the mononuclear complexes. The replacement of proline to alanine did not result in drastic change in the stability of the copper complexes, either. Studies of the 1-histidine mutants proved that coordination isomers are present in almost comparable concentration in equimolar solution. In the presence of excess of ligand, bis(ligand) complex can be formed. The presence of metal excess results in the formation of dinuclear complexes, i.e. the proline in the peptide chain does not prevent the amide coordination toward the C-termini.

In the presence of nickel(II) ions only the formation of mononuclear complexes of the 1- and 2-histidine mutants was observed at all investigated metal to ligand ratios. CD spectroscopic studies revealed that

the main anchoring site for nickel is unambiguously the second imidazolyl residue (His330) although not exclusively: approximately 5-15% of coordination isomers with His329 being the main binding site is also formed.

The 1-histidine mutants cannot prevent the hydrolysis of zinc(II) ions and the titration results in precipitation in the slightly alkaline media. However, on the other hand, all mutants containing two histidyl residues are able to bind one zinc(II) ion with the involvement of imidazolyl and amide nitrogen donor atoms.

The comparison of the copper(II) and nickel(II) binding affinity of Tau (326–333) to the N-terminal peptide fragments of Tau protein (Tau (9-16), Tau (26-33)) shows that the fragment Tau (26–33) is a more effective ligand than Tau (326–333), although the previous one contains only one histidyl residue. The presence of more polar side chains or even more likely, the presence of an adjacent methionine in the (26–33) fragment can be responsible for the enhanced stability but its complete explanation may require further studies on the complexes of other metal ions, because of the possible biological consequences of this observation.

The research was supported by the Hungarian Scientific Research Fund (K115480).

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Crystallizing the linear trinuclear copper(II) anion $\{\text{Cu}(\text{Him})_4[\text{Cu}(\mu\text{-EDTA})\text{Him}]\}_2^{2-}$ with diamagnetic imidazolium(1+) counter cations.

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A search for 'linear trinuclear copper(II) complexes' affords only 9 specific references within the past two decades, revealing its remarkable magnetic interest. Sergienko et al. [1] reported the structure of the salt $[\text{Cu}(\text{Him})_6]\{\text{Cu}(\text{Him})_4[\text{Cu}(\text{EDTA})(\text{Him})]_2\}\cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Him = imidazole), reference GEMPOE in the Cambridge Structural Database (CSD). This compound was obtained from an large excess of Him [1], compared to that used in the synthesis of $\{[\text{Cu}_2(\mu_4\text{-EDTA})(\text{Him})_2]\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}\}_n$ [2] and the corresponding stoichiometry Cu:EDTA:Him = 2:1:6. In an attempt to prepare GEMPOE, we got some single crystal of $(\text{H}_2\text{im})_2\{\text{Cu}(\text{Him})_4[\text{Cu}(\text{EDTA})(\text{Him})]_2\}\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (hereafter **1**, triclinic, $P\bar{1}$, 298 K, final R_1 0.043) with certain serendipity (Figure 1). On this basis, we rethought the stoichiometric synthesis in water for both GEMPOE and **1** using green malachite $\text{Cu}_2\text{CO}_3(\text{OH})_2$, H_4EDTA and Him, in agreement of their respective formulas. These procedures have the advantage to only yield CO_2 as by-product. Both saline compounds are very soluble in water, and their crystallizations need to be favored by diffusion of diethyl ether and isopropanol as anti-solvents (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Crystals of $(\text{H}_2\text{im})_2\{\text{Cu}(\text{Him})_4[\text{Cu}(\text{EDTA})(\text{Him})]_2\}\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (**1**).

In the symmetric trinuclear anion $\{\text{Cu}(\text{Him})_4[\text{Cu}(\mu\text{-EDTA})(\text{Him})]_2\}^{2-}$ of **1** (Figure 2) the terminal Cu(1) centers exhibits an slightly asymmetric elongated octahedral coordination, type 4+1+1, fulfilled by the proximal N20(Him) donor and a pentadentate EDTA chelator. The trans-distal sites are occupied by the O8 and N12 atoms of EDTA (angle O8-Cu1-N12 150.93(7)°). Just this N12 atom supports the non-chelating acetate arm, which supplies the O19 donor to the central Cu2 center. Thus all carboxylate of $\mu\text{-EDTA}$ groups play a monodentate role. For symmetry reasons, the Cu2 center has a symmetrically elongated octahedral coordination, type 4+2. Its distal donors are O19 atoms from of the non-chelating acetate arms $[\text{Cu}2\text{-O}19^a$ 2.720(3) Å] from the $\mu\text{-EDTA}$ chelating ligands of both Cu1

centers. Pairs of symmetry related [$a = -x, -y+2, -z$] *trans*-Cu₂-N(Him) bonds (Cu₂-N₂₅ or Cu₂-N₃₀) occupy the four proximal coordination sites [Cu₂-N₂₅ 2.033(2) Å, Cu₂-N₃₀ 1.996(2) Å] in the plane defined by such N(Him) donors.

Figure 2. Structure of the trinuclear anion $\{(\text{Him})_4[\text{Cu}(\text{EDTA})(\text{Him})_2]\}^{2-}$ of **1** ($a: -x, 2-y, -z$).

Non-coordinated water molecules of **1** are disordered in two positions, those of O1A and O1B in a crystal network (Figure 3) where all N-H bonds from Him ligands or H₂im⁺ counter-ions and O-H of water acts as donors for H-bonds with O-EDTA acceptors. In the 3D H-bonded crystal, the H₂im⁺ ions and water molecules generate H-bonded chains aligned to the trinuclear anions. These chains are further connected by (Him)N-H...O(EDTA) interactions. These anions are H-bonded to H₂im⁺ ions and disordered water molecules. In the crystal, pairs of H₂im⁺ ions display a π, π -stacking interactions (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Fragment of the crystal of **1** showing H-bonded H₂im⁺ ions and water molecules, as well as π, π -stacking between a pair of imidazolium ions (symmetry codes: $a: -x, 2-y, -z$ and $i: -x, -y, 1-z$).

From a magnetic point of view, both GEMPOE and **1** have remarkable interest, but the last one stands out because the diamagnetism of its counter imidazolium(1+) ions. The ESR spectra and magnetism of both compounds are currently under study.

Acknowledgements: Financial support from Projects No. PGC2018-102047-B-I00 (MCIU/AEI/FEDER, UE) and Junta de Andalucía (Research groups FQM-283 and FQM-247) is gratefully acknowledged.

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A study on Fe(III) - tannic acid interaction

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Tannic acid (TA) belongs to the class of hydrolysable tannins [1,2] that are natural polymers derived from the vegetable kingdom. TA is able to interact with macromolecules through hydrogen and ionic bonding or hydrophobic interactions [3-5]. It also can coordinate metal ions through the oxygenated functions. The chemical formula for commercial TA is often given as $C_{76}H_{52}O_{46}$, but in fact it is a mixture of polygalloyl glucoses or polygalloyl quinic acid esters with the number of galloyl moieties per molecule ranging from 2 up to 12. Therefore, the modelling of the interaction of metal cations with TA is a challenge, as can be the modelling of the metal complexation upon natural macromolecules without a well-defined molecular structure and the data treatment can not be based on just the stoichiometric approach. In this work [6], the redox behaviour and the fluorescence spectroscopy. Multivariate Curve Resolution-Alternating Least Squares (MCR-ALS) [7] and Parallel Factor Analysis (PARAFAC) [8] were used for the data treatment, respectively. The pH range in which there is the redox stability of the system Fe(III)-TA was evaluated. The binding capacity of TA was defined by Job's plot method and the results suggested that TA can coordinate at most four Fe(III) cations. Fluorescence excitation–emission matrices (EEM) highlighted that Fe(III) has a quenching effect on the emission peak of TA, located at excitation/emission wavelengths of 210/360 nm, in accordance with previous findings on fluorescence signals of soluble organic matter [9,10]. The UV-vis spectra obtained on solutions with metal/ligand molar ratio 1:1, and concentrations in the order of magnitude 10^{-5} mol L⁻¹, were analysed by MCR-ALS technique obtaining pure spectra and pure concentrations of the components in solution.

Figure 1. (a) Absorption spectra recorded on a solution of Fe(III)/TA with concentration 2.00×10^{-5} and 2.01×10^{-5} mol L⁻¹, respectively, at different pH values; (b) component 1 (blue line) and component 2 (orange line) concentrations profiles and (c) pure spectra for the developed MCR-ALS model.

The molar extinction coefficients of the two species (MTA1, MTA2) were estimated: $\epsilon_{\max}^{\text{MTA1}} = 3487 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ Lcm}^{-1}$ ($\lambda_{\max} = 580 \text{ nm}$); $\epsilon_{\max}^{\text{MTA2}} = 7576 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ Lcm}^{-1}$ ($\lambda_{\max} = 513 \text{ nm}$) and the molar extinction coefficients of the species MTA1 is in good agreement with the values usually proposed for the bis-catecholate complexes [11].

The stability of the interaction between TA and Fe(III) was then interpreted through the chemical models usually employed to depict the interaction of metal cations with humic substances [12] and quantified using the concentration profiles estimated by MCR-ALS. The concentration of the species in solution estimated by MCR-ALS, for each pH value, was hence used to calculate conditional formation constants cK applying the equation (1):

$${}^cK = \frac{[\text{MTA}]}{[\text{M}] (\text{TA})_{\text{total}}} \quad (1)$$

where [MTA] is the molar concentration of the metal bound to tannic acid, [M] is the molar concentration of the free metal cation and $(\text{TA})_{\text{total}}$ is the concentration of total tannic acid in solution expressed as mass per unit of volume (g L^{-1}).

The $\log {}^cK$ linearly increases with pH until pH ~ 5 . This behaviour is expected because in the pH range 3.5 – 5.0 the coordination of the binding sites involves the proton exchange reaction and at least a fraction of binding sites dissociates for competition of metal cation towards the proton. On the other hand, the pH 5 corresponds to the maximum formation of the first species and to the start point of formation of the second one, behaviour confirmed by the position of the inflection point obtained during alkalimetric titrations.

Acknowledgments

This contribution is based upon work from COST Action CA18202, NECTAR—Network for Equilibria and Chemical Thermodynamics Advanced Research, supported by COST (European Cooperation in Science and Technology).

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Investigation of Vanadium(III) and Vanadium(IV) Compounds Supported by the Linear Diaminebis(phenolate) Ligands. Correlation Between Structures and Magnetic Properties.

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The chemistry of vanadium compounds with tetradentate ONNO ligands like Schiff bases (salens) and diaminebis(phenolate) (salans) is of persistent interest to chemists in context of their relevance to bioinorganic chemistry,[1] molecular magnetism,[2] catalysis,[3] and prospective therapeutic applications. [4] Among them, those containing salan ligands have mostly been studied due their potential in the creation of compounds mimicking the active centers of vanadium nitrogenase. Also observation of salan-based vanadium(V) compounds oxidizing NH_2NMePh to 2-tetrazene ($\text{N}_4\text{Me}_2\text{Ph}_2$) has been crucial for better understanding of the biological formation of hydrazine. Therefore, our work undertaken to find other selective and efficient synthetic methods of salan – based oxidovanadium(IV) complexes to prepare their crystals in dimeric or monomeric form separately by using various solvents and H_2salans differently substituted in aromatic rings. Along this line a family of oxidovanadium(IV) compounds carrying the linear diaminebis(phenolate) (salans) L^{1-5} ligands $\{\text{L}^1 = [\text{MeNCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NMe}(\text{CH}_2-4-\text{CMe}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CMe}_3-\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{O})_2]^{2-}; \text{L}^2 = [\text{MeNCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NMe}(\text{CH}_2-4-\text{CH}_3-\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{O})_2]^{2-}; \text{L}^3 = [\text{MeNCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NMe}(\text{CH}_2-4-\text{Cl}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{O})_2]^{2-}; \text{L}^4 = \{\text{MeNCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NMe}[\text{CH}_2-4,6-(\text{CH}_3)_2-\text{C}_6\text{H}_2\text{O}]_2\}^{2-}; \text{L}^5 = \{\text{MeNCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NMe}[\text{CH}_2-4,6-(\text{Br})_2-\text{C}_6\text{H}_2\text{O}]_2\}^{2-}$ and non-oxidovanadium(III) with $\text{L}^{2,4}$ and acac ligands has been prepared and characterized by chemical and physical techniques. Reactions of $[\text{VO}(\text{acac})_2]$ with ligand precursors H_2L_2 , **4** in toluene or hexane afforded vanadium(III) compounds $[\text{V}(\text{L}-\kappa^4\text{ONNO})(\text{acac})]$ (**1**, L^2 ; **2**, L^4), while the use of acetonitrile or ethanol led to the formation of dimeric oxidovanadium(IV) $[(\text{VO})_2(\mu-\text{L}-\kappa^4\text{ONNO})_2]$ (**3**, L^1 ; **4**, L^2 ; **5**, L^3) and monomeric $[\text{VO}(\text{L}-\kappa^4\text{ONNO})]$ (**6**, L^4 , **7**, L^5) compounds. As shown by X-ray crystallography, compounds **1** and **2** are monomeric, in which the chelating ligands afford octahedral cis- α geometry at the vanadium center. In the dimeric structures of **3-5**, the six-coordinate vanadium centers are bridged via two oxygen atoms of the L^{1-3} ligands while the $\text{L}^{4,5}$ ligands generate square pyramidal structure of the monomeric **6** and **7** compounds. HFEP studies allowed to determine the spin Hamiltonian parameters of the $S=1$ spin state of the monomeric V(III) and dimeric V(IV), and $S=1/2$ in monomeric V(IV) compounds. Magnetic measurements of **3-5** indicated weak ferromagnetic metal-metal exchange interactions. A reaction course for the deoxygenation and reduction of vanadyl-salan compounds is proposed.

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Interaction of an ambidentate pyridinone derivative with organometallic $[(\eta^6\text{-}p\text{-cym})\text{Ru}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]^{2+}$ and $[(\eta^5\text{-Cp}^*)\text{Rh}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]^{2+}$ cations

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Half-sandwich type Ru(II) and Rh(III) complexes are promising candidates with anticancer potential with the hope of overcoming the serious side-effects of Pt(II) drugs currently used in the chemotherapy.

Although N-donor preference of these metal ions is well-known, formation of stable complexes with (O,O)-donor pyrone and pyridinone derivatives, especially with deferiprone (1,2-dimethyl-3-hydroxy-pyridine-4(1H)-one) is reported in the literature. This ligand is able to hinder the formation of $\{[(\eta^6\text{-}p\text{-cym})\text{Ru}]_2(\text{OH})_3\}^+$ and $\{[(\eta^5\text{-Cp}^*)\text{Rh}]_2(\text{OH})_3\}^+$ hydroxido complexes up to pH 9-10. [1-3] Study of interaction of these cations with aminohydroxamic acids being able to form (N,N)-chelates with different stability beside the hydroxamate (O,O)-chelate revealed an important role of N-donors in metal ion binding. [4-5]

Based on the above, our aim was to study the role of the presence of an coordinating, monodentate N-donor beside the (O,O)-donors in complexation.

In this work, an ambidentate pyridinone derivative, 1-(3-aminopropyl)-3-hydroxy-2-methylpyridine-4(1H)-one (Figure 1) synthesized in our research group was studied as a model ligand. pH-potentiometric, ¹H NMR and ESI-MS methods were used to determine the composition and stability constants of the complexes formed and to assess their most plausible structure in solution.

Figure 1: Resonance structures of the fully protonated form of the ligand studied.

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On the different features of the interaction with biosubstrates of Ag(I) and Au(I) bis-carbene complexes: a thermodynamic study

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After the introduction of Auranofin (AF) in 1985 for the clinical treatment of rheumatoid arthritis, a series of following studies highlighted for AF a cytotoxic potential similar to that of cisplatin against some selected cancer cell lines [1]. Recently, extensive studies have been performed in order to explore the possible therapeutic applications of gold complexes as anticancer agents [2,3]. N-heterocyclic carbenes (NHCs) ligands turned out of particular interest in medicinally relevant gold complexes [4]. Also, silver(I)-NHC complexes have been tested, and in recent scientific papers was reported an antitumor activity comparable and, in some cases, greater than that of gold carbenes [5].

Here, we describe some of our recent results on the biological activity of the Au(I)/Ag(I) – NHC - anthracenyl fluorescent complexes shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Molecular structure of the Ag(I)/Au(I)-NHC-anthracenyl complexes studied.

We analysed the solution behaviour of these complexes and some mechanistic details on their interaction with biosubstrates such as DNA, RNA, DNA G-quadruplexes and the serum albumin protein (BSA). To this aim, we carried out ESI-MS experiments, spectrophotometric and spectrofluorometric titrations, melting assays and viscometric tests. The obtained results showed some substantial differences in the reactivity features that are strictly dependent to the type of the complex's metal centre.

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Aroylhydrazones as potential protecting agents against metal-catalyzed oxidation of prion protein

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Metal-catalyzed oxidation (MCO) of proteins can lead to damage of bio-molecules and this is implicated in oxidative stress, biological aging and neurodegenerative diseases. Misfolded prion protein is known for its role in fatal neurodegenerative diseases, such as Creutzfeldt-Jakob disease. Metal-catalyzed oxidation of prion protein have been implicated as trigger for the conformational changes in protein structure, which, in turn, leads to misfolding. MCO of proteins is mainly a site-specific process in which only one or a few amino acids at the metal-binding sites of the protein are preferentially oxidized. [1]

Metal-protein attenuating compounds (MPACs), such as aroylhydrazones constitute a promising class of agents with potential application on the treatment of neurodegenerative diseases. Aroylhydrazones can act as moderate tridentate ligands towards divalent metal ions such as copper(II) and zinc(II) through the (N,N,O) donor atoms, thus has a potential to protect the protein from misfolding. The metal binding ability of two aroylhydrazone derivatives alone, and in the presence of a human prion fragment (Ac-SKPKTNMKHM-NH₂) were studied. The protecting role of these compounds during the oxidation of the prion protein fragment was also investigated. The stability constants of the copper(II) and zinc(II) parent and mixed ligand complexes were determined by pH-potentiometry. Spectroscopic techniques (UV-Vis, CD) were used to study the speciation, and bonding details of copper(II) complexes. The oxidation of the prion protein fragment in Cu(II):peptide system was studied in the presence of aroylhydrazones in the physiological pH range by the addition of H₂O₂ by HPLC-ESI-MS and MS/MS methods.

The main result of our experiments is that the relevance of aroylhydrazone compounds as metal-protein attenuating compounds is proved. These ligands provide preferred binding sites in the physiological pH range in the case of both copper(II) and zinc(II) ions. They also play a protecting role against the metal-catalyzed oxidation of peptides. [2]

Acknowledgement: The authors thank the Hungarian Scientific Research Fund (NKFI-115480 and NKFI-128783) for the financial support. The authors also thank the UNKP-20-5 New National Excellence Program of the Ministry of Human Capacities. This research was also financed by the János Bolyai Research Scholarship of the Hungarian Academy of Sciences.

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1H-Pyrazole azamacrocyclic ligands with antioxidant activity

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Reactive oxygen species (ROS) are related to neuronal death processes in neurodegenerative disorders. The first biological line of defence against ROS is the family of enzymes called superoxide dismutase (SOD). The enzymes contain different electroactive metal ions in their active centres depending on the type of organism and on their location at the cellular level. Herein we propose the design, synthesis [1] and characterization of complexes based on azamacrocyclic ligands constituted by the polyamine tris-2-(aminomethyl)amine linked to an 1H-pyrazole aromatic spacer and functionalized with either pyridine or quinoline substituents attached to the polyamine [2]. We study their coordination to Cu²⁺ and Mn²⁺ and their applications as SOD mimics by using the McCord and Fridovich method [3].

Figure 1: Azamacrocyclic ligand constituted by polyamine tris 2-(aminomethyl)amine linked to an 1H-pyrazole spacer; R= pyridine, quinolone.

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Influence of sialylation on the binding of ferric ion to human serum transferrin

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Human transferrin is a plasma glycoprotein that transports ferric ions in the blood. It is comprised of two globular lobes, C-lobe and N-lobe, each with one metal-binding site for the ferric ion. Transferrin structure consists of 679 amino acids with two *N*-glycan structures covalently linked to asparagine residues 413 and 611 on the *C*-lobe. The *N*-glycan structures can be bi- or tri-antennary and each of them terminates with sialic acid. Physiological and pathophysiological changes in transferrin sialylation may alter the thermodynamic and kinetic properties of iron binding. In this study, the equilibrium constants for the two binding sites of human transferrin were determined at pH 5.6 and 7.4, in the presence of different synergistic anions and different sialylation patterns: for the native transferrin (Tf+s) and desialylated transferrin (Tf-s) [1]. Titrations of apotransferrin (transferrin containing no iron bound) with ferric ion presented in a nitrilotriacetate complex were performed and the extent of transferrin iron saturation was monitored spectrofluorometrically. Binding constants were calculated from the observed fluorescence intensities using HypSpec2014 software [2-5]. At pH 7.4 in the presence of carbonate as a synergistic anion, the calculated equilibrium constant for the binding of the second ferric ion to Tf+s is greater than the constant for the first ferric ion ($K_2 > K_1$), and in the presence of oxalate as a synergistic anion it is reverse ($K_2 < K_1$). A similar effect is observed for the binding of the ferric ion to Tf-s: in the presence of carbonate the first ferric ion binds to transferrin stronger than the second ferric ion ($K_2 < K_1$), and in the presence of oxalate it is reverse ($K_2 > K_1$). Such inverse affinities for the binding sites might be attributed to steric effects due to the difference in size between carbonate and oxalate. At pH 5.6 only one ferric ion binds to apotransferrin with a lower affinity than at pH 7.4 [6]. The difference in binding constants for Tf-s in the presence of oxalate and carbonate indicates the increased influence of sialylation on the preferred carbonate binding site. The results strongly suggest that the degree of sialylation significantly affects one of the transferrin iron binding sites, presumably on the *C*-lobe which also contains the *N*-glycan binding sites.

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Acid-base properties and binding ability of creatinine towards biologically relevant metal cations in aqueous solution

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Creatinine is an important physiological component of blood, brain and muscles and it is also the last product of the nitrogen metabolism in the vertebrates. Despite its importance in the medical field and the recognized possibility of interaction with metals, not so many thermodynamic data are available in the literature [1-3]. Only few authors studied the acid-base properties of creatinine in aqueous solution ((particularly, protonation and stability constants)) but often the data for the calculation of the stability constants are not reported or imprecise and unspecified, especially there is little information regarding the ligand concentrations, the ionic strength and the equilibria considered. For this reason we focused our attention on the study of its acid-base properties, in particular to the determination of the protonation constants ($\log K_i$) of L at $T = 298.15$ K at various ionic strengths (from $I = 0.1$ to 1 mol dm^{-3}) in $(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{NCl}_{(\text{aq})}$, $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_4\text{NI}_{(\text{aq})}$ and $\text{NaCl}_{(\text{aq})}$, by means of ISE- H^+ potentiometric titrations. For the last medium, we have also explored other temperatures (288.15, 310.15 and 318.15K). The dependence of protonation constants on ionic strength was performed by a Debye–Hückel type equation and the Specific ion Interaction Theory (SIT). The protonation constant at infinite dilution and $T = 298.15$ K resulted to be $\log K = 4.845 \pm 0.004$ (\pm standard deviation). The dependence of $\log K_i$ on ionic medium was also interpreted in terms of formation of weak complexes between L and the cations of the supporting electrolytes. The binding ability of creatinine towards other biologically and environmentally relevant cations, such as Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Cu^{2+} and Zn^{2+} was also investigated in $\text{NaCl}_{(\text{aq})}$ at different ionic strengths (from 0.1 to 1 mol dm^{-3}), and the corresponding stability constants are reported.

Figure 1. Creatinine tautomeric forms

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Curcumin-based β -diketo ligands for Ga³⁺: on the way to develop new antineoplastic agents

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Curcumin is by far known for its therapeutic properties, among these, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory and anti-cancer ones stand out. Moreover, curcumin metal complexes showed widespread applications in medicine [1] and can be exploited as lead structures for developing metal-based drugs. Unfortunately, curcumin is poorly bioavailable mainly due to its instability in physiological conditions; this weakness is tightly connected to the presence of the β -diketo moiety undergoing tautomeric equilibrium. Stability and metal-chelating ability can be tuned by modulating the electronic effects and steric hindrance close to β -diketo moiety, in addition the formation of the metal-complex shifts the tautomeric equilibrium towards the β -keto-enol form and increases stability in biological media.

Among metals used in clinical therapy, gallium nitrate showed to have significant antitumor

activity against non-Hodgkin's lymphoma and bladder cancer, thus indicating that gallium-based drugs have potential for further development as antineoplastic agents with improved therapeutic activity [2]. Curcuminoids demonstrated high affinity for gallium (III), allowing the formation of stable positively charged M:L 1:2 β -diketonate complexes that benefit of the therapeutic activities of both the metal and ligand [3,4].

In this landscape, seven new curcumin derivatives were synthesized (**Scheme 1**) and completely characterized. The new derivatives retain the solvent-dependent keto-enol tautomerism, with the prevalence of the diketo form in aqueous solution. Generally, they showed enhanced

stability in simulated physiological conditions in comparison to the lead compound curcumin. The presence of Ga^{3+} anticipates the dissociation of the enolic proton, allowing the chelate complex formation, and contemporarily it shifts the tautomeric equilibrium towards the keto-enol form. Complete $^1\text{H}/^{13}\text{C}$ NMR and UV-vis studies were performed in order to define the Metal-to-Ligand stoichiometry ratio and the overall stability constants for all the compounds. An example of UV-vis spectrophotometric titration for B21 is reported in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1. pH-metric spectrophotometric titration of Ga^{3+} :B21 1:1 system in aqueous solution ($[\text{NaNO}_3] = 0.1 \text{ M}$, 298 K).

In conclusion, the synthesized curcumin-based molecules may act as Gallium(III)-chelators with improved stability with respect to curcumin and could open interesting perspectives for the development of novel therapeutic agents for cancer.

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New ferulic acid derivatives as metal modulating agents with potential anti-Alzheimer's disease roles

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Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a multifactorial neurodegenerative disorder characterized by progressive loss of neurons in the brain. Early symptoms comprise memory decline and language problems, followed by other cognitive serious dysfunctions related to brain atrophy [1]. AD is the most common cause of dementia: the number of patients in 2019 was estimated to be 50 million and projected to reach 152 million individuals by 2050 [2].

Despite enormous research efforts, the pathogenesis and the mechanism of AD progression are not yet completely understood. However, several hallmarks have been identified such as extracellular amyloid- β (A β) plaques, intracellular neurofibrillary tangles (NFT), dyshomeostasis of physiological metal ions (Cu, Zn, Fe) and oxidative stress. According with the multifactorial nature of this disease, the most recent studies aim to develop multitarget-directed ligands (MTDL), able to act simultaneously against different pathological features. Under the context of MTDL approach, several compounds isolated from plants and microorganisms have shown benefices in the treatment of AD [3], thus confirming that the use of natural compounds can be an interesting area of research when developing AD therapies.

Following previous studies of anti-AD compounds enclosing moieties based on cinnamic acid and, especially, ferulic acid (FA) derivatives [4], we are proposing now a new set of hybrids containing FA analogues. FA is a phenolic compound largely present in human diet, and well-known for its antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties, with a potential role in the treatment of AD by inhibiting A β aggregation *in vitro* and *in vivo* AD mouse model [5].

Herein we present the results of physico-chemical (antioxidant activity, metal chelation) and biological (inhibition of A β aggregation) characterization of a set of new hybrid FA analogues (see **Scheme**), where the FA moiety is coupled with benzyloxyamines substituted with methoxy, trifluoromethyl or chlorine. The compounds showed good radical scavenging activity and metal chelation ability towards Fe³⁺ and Cu²⁺, as well as good inhibition capacity for self- (28.3-52.8 %) and copper-induced (68.8-79.6) A β aggregation. Importantly, this set of FA hybrids present also good pharmacokinetic descriptors. Discussion of the results is made based on structural-activity relationships, namely associated to the effect of different substituent groups. Overall, the studied FA derivatives seem to be good proposals for further pursuing research envisaging their potential as anti-AD drugs.

R = (a) 2-OCH₃; (b) 3-OCH₃; (c) 2-CF₃; (d) 3-Cl; (e) 2,4-Cl.

Scheme. Structural formula of ferulic acid (FA) and its benzyloxyamidic derivatives

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A morphology study on several PEG 400 based nanocolloids

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Phase change materials (PCM) are materials with a large area of tuneable properties, while the solid–liquid type of PCM is the most widely applied on various processes. The solid–liquid type of PCM can be classified into two groups—organic and inorganic PCMs. Organic solid–liquid PCMs have a stable phase transition temperature, no phase separation, no sub-cooling, thermal stability, low phase change enthalpy and low thermal conductivity. In comparison, inorganic PCMs have high thermal storage capacity, low thermal conductivity and small changes in phase transition volume [1, 2]. Also, liquid PCMs are lately considered as heat transfer fluids due to their excellent heat transfer properties. Adding nanoparticles to liquid PCMs can counter on nanofluids class of materials. Considering this option, aggregation and sedimentation of nanoparticles play an important role in the stability of nanofluids and their behaviour as heat transfer agents. A number of studies have indicated that the pH of the dispersion influences the overall stability of nanofluids [3-8]. In this idea, new fluids were prepared for this study and to fully understand their properties and behaviour several tests were accomplished.

This paper presents an experimental study of a new phase change material involving three types of nanoparticles Al₂O₃, ZnO, MWCNT (0.5 % mass fraction) suspended in polyethylene glycol PEG 400. Before proceeding to the preparation of the new fluids, the morphology of the nanoparticles used in this study was analysed, as well as the structure and purity of polyethylene glycol PEG 400. The characterization of the nanoparticles was performed by means of TEM analysis. All prepared fluids were also analysed from a structural and stability point of view, performing Thermogravimetric analysis and pH measurements. The pH was checked at ambient temperature using the Edge[®] HI 2030 (Hanna Instruments), with integrated temperature sensor and large measuring areas, up to 500 mS/cm and resolution 0.01 μ S/cm. Thermogravimetric (TG) measurements were performed using a STA 449F1 JUPITER (Netzsch, Germany) device. About 40-70 mg of each probe was used for TG measurements at a heating rate of 10 C°/min. The tests were carried out using a nitrogen atmosphere at heating up to 700 °C. Concluding, these fluids stability was found to be very good after was checked through visual observation as well as by pH and no surfactant was added. All fluids characteristics are influenced by the type of nanoparticles and is essential to extend the research on their properties and behaviour.

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Cd(II) sorption on a novel L-glutamic N,N-diacetic acid based polymer inclusion membrane in aqueous solution

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Despite the availability of many chelating agents able to efficiently bind metal cations in solution, only few are actually viable as a large-scale countermeasure to the persistent problem of metal-polluted wastes. For instance, among them, the non-biodegradable ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) ended up being overused, thus becoming a polluting agent itself, pointing out the necessity to search for new strategies for efficient cations removal and environmental remediation [1]. In this scenario, this contribution reports some preliminary results on a research focused on the development of novel ecofriendly efficient and “practically usable” materials. Although this goal is still far from being achieved, the fundamental idea of the material biocompatibility led to the synthesis of a series of novel and ecofriendly polymer inclusion membranes (PIMs), whose formulation is based on a biopolymer matrix, namely polylactic acid (PLA) including Aliquat336 (Ali, an ionic liquid) and L-glutamic N,N-diacetic acid (GLDA), the latter being a readily biodegradable chelating agent [2]. Such material has already shown a remarkable chelating capability toward Cd²⁺ along with high tolerance to extreme conditions such as low pH and high electrolyte concentration. In this regard the chemometrics approach during the experimental design was of pivotal importance. This versatile method greatly simplified the assessment of the chemical behavior of these materials in heterogeneous solutions. In particular, the acid-base equilibria of L-glutamic N,N-diacetic acid entrapped inside the polymeric membrane were investigated by potentiometric titrations in a pH range comprised between 3 and 11 and ionic strength between 0.1 and 1 mol dm⁻³. Moreover, kinetics experiments for the sorption of the Cd²⁺ cation were performed by means of differential pulse anodic stripping voltammetry (DP-ASV) to assess the time required to reach equilibrium between the PIMs and a solution containing Cd(II), at different chloride concentration values. This information was then taken into account while performing isotherm experiments by DP-ASV. Last, the surface structural characterization was performed by means of attenuated total reflectance (ATR). The preliminary data obtained are encouraging and may suggest the use of these polymer inclusion membranes for remediation purposes.

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Link between fibril formation and antimicrobial properties of zinc(II)-pramlintide complex

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The problem of antimicrobial resistance (resistance of a microorganism to an antimicrobial drug that was originally effective), which has been growing for years, necessitates the development of new therapeutic agents. Antimicrobial peptides (AMPs), which are small, polycationic peptides that take part in the innate immune response, are being believed to become a novel class of therapeutics, mainly because of the general lack of resistance towards them.

Presented work concerns non-aggregating analogues of amylin - a 37-amino acid peptide hormone (KCNTATCATQRLANFLVHSSNFGAILSSTNVGSNTY-NH₂), which in addition to the function of regulating blood sugar levels, has also been classified as antimicrobial peptide. [1] Due to the fact that amylin has tendency to fibrillization, it cannot be used as a medicine for type 2 diabetes. Therefore, based on the amino acid sequence of non-fibrillating rat amylin, its synthetic analog, pramlintide (KCNTATCATQRLANFLVHSSNFGPIPTNVGSNTY-NH₂), was developed. [2]

For some AMPs, the presence of divalent metal ions, such as Zn²⁺ and Cu²⁺ has an effect on their activity or mode of action. This is attained either by (i) binding metal ions, so that microbes cannot get enough nutrients essential for their life and virulence (a process named 'nutritional immunity') or (ii) using metal ions as a booster of antimicrobial activity of AMPs, effecting the charge and/or structure of the peptide. [3] The presence of copper(II) and zinc(II) ions has also potential effect on amylin fibrillation. [4]

The main aim of this work is to understand the bioinorganic chemistry of Zn(II) and Cu(II) complexes with amylin analogues – rat amylin, amylin₁₋₁₉, pramlintide (Figure 1) and Ac-pramlintide in SDS micelles, as model membrane environment. We discuss the details of the coordination mode, structure and stability of the studied complexes, in order to understand the potential effect of metal ions on the antimicrobial activity of the peptides. The most surprising result of our work is the fact that among the studied ligands and their complexes, only the Zn(II)-pramlintide complex has antifungal properties and only the Zn(II)-pramlintide complex is able to form amyloid structures (Figure 2). We show a correlation between Zn(II)-pramlintide morphology and its antimicrobial properties, hypothesizing that the amyloid, needle-like structures are able to disrupt the fungal surface.

Figure 1. Proposed coordination modes for the Cu(II)-pramlinitide complex at pH 7.4 (A) {NH₂, 3N⁻}, (B) {Nim, 3N⁻} and (C) Zn(II)-pramlinitide complex at pH 7.4 {NH₂, Nim}

Figure 2. AFM images of pramlinitide after 24h incubation a) without metal ions b) with Zn²⁺ ions

Acknowledgements

Support of the National Science Centre (UMO2017/26/A/ST5/00364) is gratefully acknowledged.

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Coordination properties of ligands constituting fragments of membrane proteins of commensal bacteria

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Metals are essential for all living organisms. They play a key role in the functioning of enzymes and the proper structure of proteins. The survival of bacteria in the human body depends on the proper acquisition of essential nutrients, especially metal ions. Transition metal ions such as Cu^{+2+} , Zn^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , $\text{Fe}^{2+/3+}$ are involved in many biological processes. Therefore, it is crucial to understand the role and homeostasis of metal ions at the molecular level [1].

Staphylococcus aureus is a gram-positive commensal bacteria. Under certain conditions, this microorganism has the capacity to infect nearly every tissue in the human body upon breaching its initial site of colonization. Bacterial Feo (ferrous iron transport) system is widely distributed among archaea and bacteria. It plays an important role in bacterial virulence connected with colonization and intramacrophage survival. Although ferrous iron transport system is very widespread among microorganisms, it is still poorly described in Gram-positive pathogens [2].

Herein, combined potentiometric and spectroscopic studies were performed to determine the first selected metal ion, namely Cu(II), binding by ligands constituting fragments of FeoB protein from *S. aureus*. The studied fragments are Ac-IDYHKLMK-NH₂, Ac-ETSHDKY-NH₂ and Ac-SFLHMGVS-NH₂. The

calculated overall stability constants of the complex species allowed to compare the binding strength of Cu(II) among ligands. For this purpose, previously calculated stability constants were applied to a situation, in which equimolar amounts of Cu(II) and each ligand are present in solution. As can be seen in the Figure 1, cupric ions are most effectively chelated by the Ac-ETSHDKY-NH₂ fragment.

Figure 1. Competition diagram for Ac-IDYHKLMK-NH₂, Ac-ETSHDKY-NH₂ and Ac-SFLHMGVS-NH₂ complexes with Cu(II). The concentration of all reagents equal 1 mM.

Moreover, gel electrophoresis and UV-Vis spectroscopy were used to test whether the formed complexes are able to generate reactive oxygen species (ROS) in the presence of hydrogen peroxide. It was found that all tested complexes generate free radicals and cleave plasmid DNA.

Acknowledgements

The authors thanks the Polish National Science Centre (Grant NCN 2017/26/A/ST5/00363)

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Multi-technique approach applied on the study of the coordination properties of 8-hydroxyquinoline-2-carboxylic acid towards divalent metal cations

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Tryptophan (Trp) is an essential amino acid with a large variety of physiological functions, with a fundamental role on the regulation of immune, central nervous and gastrointestinal nervous systems and with a significant influence on the intestinal microbiota. Due to its physiological relevance, it is not surprising that imbalances in the level of Trp and its metabolites (TrpM – e.g., kynurenic acid (KynA), xanthurenic acid (XA), quinaldic acid (QA), 8-hydroxyquinoline-2-carboxylic acid (8-HQA), etc.) are associated with a wide range of human pathologies, including depression, schizophrenia, autoimmunity, neuro-degeneration and cancer, in particular colorectal cancer (CRC), one of the most malignant cancers. Most of these disease result from the fact that Trp metabolic disorder can affect the balance of intestinal microbiota leading to inflammation that contributes to the progression of, for example, CRC, and vice-versa, i.e., CRC development results in inflammation that changes the homeostasis of intestinal microbiota affecting Trp metabolism.[1,2] Furthermore, it is well reported the metal homeostasis relevance on the balance and quality of intestine microbial community, being known that dietary metal ions have the potential to change the distribution and function of the microbiota.[3] In this way, can

TrpM metal complexes tune Trp metabolism? And can they be used as anti-tumoral drugs on CRC or other microbiota related disorders?

Aiming the finding of some answers to these questions, we present here in a detailed study on the coordination properties of one TrpM (8-HQA) towards several biologically relevant metal cations as Zn^{2+} , Mn^{2+} and Co^{2+} . For that purpose, a multi-technique approach has been adopted, in order to derive a comprehensive set of information necessary to assess the chemical speciation of the 8-HQA/ M^{2+} systems. 8-HQA binding ability towards M^{2+} has been investigated in $KCl_{(aq)}$ at $I = 0.2 \text{ mol}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$ and $T = 298.15 \text{ K}$ by ISE- H^+ (glass electrode) potentiometric and UV/Vis spectrophotometric titrations. CV (Cyclic Voltammetry), ESR (electron spin resonance) and quantum mechanical calculations have been also performed to complement the information about the coordination modes, structure and nature of formed species. The sequestering ability and selectivity of 8-HQA towards the different studied metals will be discussed, along with a comparison with previous results obtained for the systems 8-HQA/ Fe^{3+} and 8-HQA/ Fe^{2+} . [4]

Acknowledgments:

This contribution is based upon work from COST Action CA18202, NECTAR – Network for Equilibria and Chemical Thermodynamics Advanced Research, supported by COST (European Cooperation in Science and Technology).

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Zinc binding sites in Aspf2, a zincophore from *Aspergillus fumigatus*

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The frequency of drug resistant invasive mycoses due to opportunistic fungal pathogens has increased significantly over the past three decades. This phenomenon forces to focus on searching innovative methods of treatment. One of the biggest difficulty in finding new specific anti-fungal therapeutics comes from the fact that fungi share many essential metabolic pathways with a human organisms [1]. Consequently, in order to design a highly specific antifungal drug, it is necessary to understand and to use the difference in human and fungal metabolic pathways [2]. One of the significant differences between mammalian and fungal cells is the mechanism of metal uptake and transport [3], which is one of the critical aspects of fungal infection and survival. *Aspergillus fumigatus* secretes an extracellular zincophore Aspf2, a 310 amino acid protein that is able to sequester zinc from host. The secreted Aspf2 zincophore is released into surrounding host cells, where it binds the host's zinc and then returns to the fungal cell and delivers it to the fungal pathogen through physical interaction with the ZrfC transporter [4] (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Schematic model of *Aspergillus fumigatus* scavenging from host cells. After invasion of the host cell, Aspf2 is expressed and secreted. It binds zinc, either in the form of free Zn(II) or from zinc-binding proteins of the host reassociation with the *A. fumigatus* cells and Zn(II) transportation into the cell occurs *via* a Aspf2-ZrfC interaction.

The results of mass spectrometry, potentiometry, UV-Vis and CD spectroscopy allowed us to determine the stoichiometry, the exact zinc(II) and nickel(II) binding site and the geometry of their complexes. Among the precisely chosen, most probable Zn(II) binding sites in Aspf2, the unstructured

C-terminal region of Aspf2, Ac-PNCHTHEGGLHCT, binds Zn(II) with the highest affinity *via* a set of three histidine imidazoles and one cysteine thiol.

The C-terminal region of the Aspf2 zincophore has also a high affinity towards another biologically relevant metal ion – Ni(II). At pH 7.4 Ni(II) is coordinated by a sulfur atom of a cysteine residue, two nitrogen atoms of histidine residues and an amide nitrogen, with a {S⁻, 2N_{im}, N} binding mode. At higher pH values is present the deprotonation and subsequent binding of two other amide nitrogens, with a {3N⁻, S} binding mode. Microbiological experiments that aim to check if the short zincophore fragment can be recognized by *Aspergillus* and used as a targeting molecule are currently ongoing.

Acknowledgements:

Support of the National Science Centre (UMO2017/26/A/ST5/00363) is gratefully acknowledged.

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Peptides derived from R3 repeat of Tau protein: copper complexation and redox catalysis

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Tau is a 441-mer peptide present in significant amounts in neurons, where it contributes to the stabilization of microtubules. Insoluble amyloid aggregates of tau are associated with over 20 neurological disorders known as tauopathies, among which is Parkinson.[1] In neurons, tau binds tubulin through its microtubule binding domain which comprises four repeats (R1-R4) characterized by the presence of histidine residues. These regions are potential binding sites for metal ions.[2] The elucidation of the binding capacities toward metal ions, especially those redox active such as copper(II), may shed light on the biomolecular processes that underlie the progression of tauopathies.[3] Recently, our research group examined the stability of Cu(II) and Cu(I) adducts with two peptide fragments which are encompassed in the R1 and R3 repeats of tau (Fig. 1).[4]

R3:

R3Long:

R3LongC322A:

Figure 1. Left. Sequences of the R3 peptides. **Right.** Distribution diagram of the Cu(II)/R3LongC322A system (R3L = R3LongC322A, $C_{\text{Cu}} = 0.252 \text{ mM}$, R3L:Cu = 2.1:1).

The presence of a tandem His-His site in the R3 peptide sequence promotes the reduction of Cu(II) to Cu(I), mainly through the formation of stable Cu(I)/R3 adducts. By accommodating copper in both oxidation states, the His-His site provides an active catalyst for reactions that activate oxygen, such as catechol oxidation.

Several neuropeptides, actually, contain other His residues beyond those of the His-His dyad (e.g. β -amyloid). Although much is known about copper/peptides that promote oxidative reactions, the relationship between the catalytic properties and the position of the His residues within the peptide sequence is still far from being fully elucidated [5,6]. With the aim to shed light on this relationship I

have synthesized four peptides, derived from the tau R3 fragment, that bear a His-His dyad and a third additional His residue located at different positions along the amino acid sequence.

In this communication I will discuss the study of the complex formation equilibria of Cu(II) and Cu(I) with the elongated analogues of the R3 peptide, (Figure 1, [4]) as well as the complex formation equilibria of Cu(II) with the four new peptides containing the extra His residue.

Acknowledgements: The authors acknowledge MIUR for financial support through the project "Metal ions, dopamine, and oxidative stress in Parkinson's disease" (PRIN 2015T778JW). This work was supported by a STSM Grant from COST Action CA18202.

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Study of the formation of complexes between dopamine and different cations of biological and environmental interest in NaCl aqueous solution at different ionic strengths and temperatures

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Our group has been involved during the last years in studies aimed to the determination of the thermodynamic aqueous parameters of different classes of organic ligands of biological and pharmaceutical interest. The knowledge of these parameters is very important for pharmaceutical product design, influencing the pharmacokinetics, such as the release, transport and the degree of absorption of the drug in the organism [1-3].

Data regarding the thermodynamic aqueous properties of Dopamine appear till now few and quite confusing, and no systematic modeling study such as their dependence on the experimental conditions (ionic medium, ionic strength and temperature) is reported.

The main aim of our investigation is to give an important contribution on the knowledge of the thermodynamic aqueous properties and sequestering ability of Dopamine towards some metal (CH_3Hg^+ , Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Sn^{2+}) ions of biological and environmental interest in NaCl aqueous solutions at different ionic strengths and temperatures.

The speciation schemes were compared to each other and the effect of the ionic media, ionic strength and temperature was discussed.

The sequestering ability of the ligand towards the metal ions was estimated by means of the $pL_{0.5}$ parameter and some empirical equations were proposed for the modelling of the variation of the $pL_{0.5}$ with the experimental condition changes.

The dependence of such thermodynamic parameters on the ionic strength was modeled by means of an extended Debye-Huckel equation and of the SIT (Specific ion Interaction Theory) approach.

The sparingly soluble species obtained during the potentiometric titrations were studied and characterized by means of the TGA analysis.

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Clathrochelate complexes and globular proteins as supramolecular couples

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The specific recognition of protein surface elements seem to be undoubtedly important for the development of various biochemical and biomedical tools, such as sensors, affinity tags, protein-based materials or novel immobilization techniques [1]. Upon interaction, the host protein molecules exhibiting inherent chirality are able to induce asymmetry of achiral organic and coordination compounds, and therefore may cause an appearance of a signal in their CD spectra. These induced CD (ICD) bands are very sensitive to the arrangement of the binding sites of hosting proteins and may reflect both the structural alterations and the conformation transitions of proteins. Various organic compounds and metal complexes have been reported to be ICD probes due to their binding to proteins and sensitivity to their structural alterations. Among them, cage metal complexes = clathrochelates [2], have been recently recognized as prospective biological effectors using their three-dimensional structure as rigid scaffold for macromolecular binding.

Here we will present our recent results on iron(II) clathrochelates as macrobicyclic cage metal complexes able to form multicentered supramolecular interactions in the vacant cavities or at the surface of protein macromolecules and/or their macromolecular complexes [3-5].

Acknowledgements

The project leading to these results has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement no. 778245.

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Spectroscopic and redox properties of SOD biomimetics: a practical and theoretical approach

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Naturally, Reactive Oxygen Species (ROS) as superoxide radical anion (O_2^-) are formed during human metabolism, and its formation can be altered by external sources such as pollutants or radiation. The study of ROS production and consumption is of great interest because ROS are very reactive species that can interact and alter the structure and biological functions of many essential molecules in the body. Consequently, changes in ROS levels have been linked with diseases such as cancer, inflammatory and neurodegenerative diseases, diabetes, among others [1]. One of the body's defense mechanisms to mitigate the excessive increase in ROS levels and to avoid oxidative stress is superoxide dismutase (SOD). SOD makes possible the dismutation of the superoxide anion to hydrogen peroxide and oxygen. These redox processes are catalyzed by metal cofactors such as copper that continuously cycles between Cu^{2+}/Cu^{1+} donating and receiving electrons to transform superoxide anion [2].

However, despite the proven biological potential of SOD against ROS, the direct use of native SOD in therapy has been limited due to many factors such as its low permeability through the membrane, immunological responses, short lifespan in the body, prices of production, and others. Therefore, a significant scientific effort has been devoted to develop low molecular weight biomimetics [3]. An essential part of the research regarding SOD mimetics has been focused on metal complexes because metals are suitable for redox cycling due to their diversity of redox states [4]. For these reasons, this work focuses on the synthesis and characterization of new copper and manganese complexes to understand their reactivity as a first step to obtain new biomimetic complexes of SOD. As part of the experimental work, the synthesis and purification of the ligands and the corresponding complexes will be discussed. In total, five ligands were synthesized and used to obtain five copper complexes and four manganese complexes. An important goal during this study was to understand better the effect of minor structural differences in the physicochemical properties of the ligand and their corresponding complexes. In this sense, four of the ligands share the same general structure, except for the substituents at the para position (-H, -OH, -Cl, -CH₃), as shown in the figure below.

Figure 2 a) General structure for ligands with para substitutions b) Optimized structure for ligand with Cl substitution

Moreover, their corresponding complexes of copper and manganese can be observed in Figure 2. As can be seen, depending upon the metal used, the coordination mode changes, showing the ligands' versatility. Characterization was carried out both experimentally and computationally. Experimentally, the physicochemical characterization of the compounds obtained was made using infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), UV-Vis spectroscopy (solid and liquid), and magnetic susceptibility. The next stage of the project was focused on the computational analysis using DFT and TDDFT. In this sense, the experimental results obtained were used to propose initial geometries that were optimized and used to calculate FTIR and UV-Vis simulation, which agreed with experimental results.

**Figure 3 Optimized structure of complexes with ligands described in Figure 1 a) Complex with copper
b) Complex with manganese**

Then, a computational prediction of the biological activity of the complexes was made. First, a geometry optimization of each coordination complex in two oxidation states was completed. The oxidation states are the same as those for the corresponding metal in the native isoforms of SOD metalloprotein. These results were used to determine the geometry changes upon reduction/oxidation allowing to determine whether break of bonds or changes in geometry are expected during the redox cycle and to have an insight regarding the plausible catalysis mechanism. The energy obtained for the optimized structures was used to determine the electron affinity which has been previously reported to relate to SOD mimetic activity [5]. Finally, the frontier molecular orbitals were studied to understand the electron transfer process further and extract reactivity parameter such as electrophilicity from HOMO and LUMO values. All of these results allow us to determine the better SOD mimetic: in this study the copper and manganese complexes with chloro substitution in para position. Other ligands and complexes with different substituents at para position that were not available in the laboratory are being calculated, using this process to predict how to improve the proposed complexes for future studies and synthesis.

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Acknowledgments:

- To the School of Chemical Science and Engineering at Yachay Tech University for the access to laboratory.
- To PhD. Duncan Mowbray for the access to Imbabura cluster for computational calculations.

Speciation studies of bifunctional alkyl-(amino-carboxylic)-3-hydroxy-4-pyridinones in the presence of Fe³⁺

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The 3-hydroxy-4-pyridinones are a class of compounds suitable for specific chelation of *hard* metal cations (e.g. Al³⁺, Fe³⁺), as the chelating drug deferiprone [1]. Due to their efficacy in all biological conditions, and without relevant drawbacks [3,4], 3-hydroxy-4-pyridinones are considered a good alternative to the use of deferoxamine (Desferal) as iron-decorporating drug [2]. These ligands consist of an aromatic *N*-heterocyclic ring with a hydroxyl and a ketone group in *ortho* positioned and can be easily further *N*-extrafunctionalized to introduce differentiation in terms of pharmacokinetic parameters and potential interaction with proteins. As a continuation of our previous studies on the synthesis, and study of the binding ability of a set of bifunctional alkyl-(amino-carboxylic)-3-hydroxy-4-pyridinones (L1-L5) towards Al³⁺ [4] and biologically relevant metal cations such as Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺ [5], Zn²⁺ [6] and Cu²⁺ [7], the investigation of their interaction with Fe³⁺, as possible iron(III) chelating agents, appeared as a quite relevant issue. Thus, this contribution is focused on the results of an investigation on the complexing ability of these ligands towards Fe³⁺ in aqueous systems, namely at *I* = 0.15 mol L⁻¹ in NaCl_(aq), *T* = 298.15 K and, for Fe³⁺/L2 and Fe³⁺/L5 systems, also at *T* = 300.15 K. The analytical techniques used were potentiometry (ISE-H⁺) and UV-Vis spectrophotometry. The elaboration of the experimental data allowed the determination of speciation models consisting of Fe_pL_qH_r species with different stoichiometry and protonation degree. The stability constants (logβ) obtained for the corresponding complex species by different analytical techniques were in good agreement. Furthermore, the sequestering ability and the affinity of the set of 3-hydroxy-4-pyridinones towards Fe³⁺ were investigated by the determination of the empirical parameter pL_{0.5} [8] at different pHs and of the pM [9] values at physiological pH (pH ~ 7.4).

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Metal ion binding and Ca²⁺-promoted fluorescence of bis(diethylamino)xanthene-labelled BAPTA analogues

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Ca²⁺-responsive, fluorophore-labelled molecular probes are fundamental bioanalytical tools in monitoring the Ca²⁺ concentration at the cellular level and they assist the understanding of biochemical processes with the participation of this essential metal ion. The innovative Ca²⁺-chelating skeleton of the unique aminocarboxylic acid type compound, 1,2 bis(2-aminophenoxy)ethane N,N,N',N' tetraacetic acid (BAPTA) (Scheme below), designed by Tsien et al. over 40 years ago [1], provides a platform for the construction of fluorophore-labelled structures that turn on their fluorescence when chelating Ca²⁺ ions. The major advantage of the BAPTA chelator lies in the acid dissociation constants (pK_a) of the Ca²⁺-binding donor groups of the ligand, which all release their protons well below pH 7, in contrast to several other metal ion chelators, such as EDTA or EGTA. This endows BAPTA with the ability to bind Ca²⁺ ions in a pH-independent fashion in the neutral pH-range and above. BAPTA was also shown to be rather selective for the binding of Ca²⁺ ion over the potentially competing, abundant and essential metal ion, Mg²⁺ [1].

In the past decades, a variety of BAPTA-based fluorescent Ca²⁺-indicators have been developed for monitoring Ca²⁺ levels under various cellular conditions and for the purpose of cellular imaging [2-4]. Already the prototype of these BAPTA-related constructs was rather successful, however, via different modifications in the signaling element (the fluorophore unit) different wavelength regimes may be covered and fine-tuning of the chelator moiety may shift the free Ca²⁺-sensitive range to lower and higher concentrations (corresponding to a high and low affinity, respectively). This is rather important since the level of Ca²⁺ varies in biological systems over a broad range from the cytosol to the internal space of different organelles.

Along this train-of-thought, we have constructed several BAPTA-analogue chelator scaffolds and coupled these to the easily attachable bis(diethylamino)xanthene fluorophore unit (Scheme below). Our strategy was to systematically modify the length of the linker between the two, originally identical "sides" of the BAPTA skeleton and thus to tune the size of the metal ion chelating cavity formed by the four acetate arms, the two amino functions and the linker etheric oxygen(s) (when present). Besides, in one structure we completely removed one of the aminophenyl-based moieties (see the fragment of the molecule in red in the Scheme) and replaced it by an ethylene-linked imino-diacetate unit.

By studying these ligands, we intended to investigate the effect of the length of the linker/the size of the metal ion binding cavity on the Ca²⁺ ion binding affinity, as well as on the fluorescence "turn

on” effect induced by Ca²⁺-binding. It turned out, that either the increase or the decrease of the length of the original linker notably reduces the Ca²⁺-binding affinity of the indicators. Nevertheless, the “shortest” analogue, bearing only a single oxygen atom between the two aromatic rings, as well as the compound with the aliphatic imino-diacetate unit, displays a notable, only ca. one log unit weaker Ca²⁺-binding affinity relative to the original BAPTA-based construct, and at the same time, a rather significant Ca²⁺-promoted fluorescence “turn on” effect, too.

We also synthesized some of these ligands as pure chelators, without the attached fluorophore. This allowed us to investigate in details the pH- and metal ion - ligand ratio dependent speciation of the complexes formed between the ligands and the metal ions and to accurately determine the Ca²⁺-binding affinity of the chelators. Besides, we could also gain information on the Mg²⁺-binding affinities and thus the metal binding selectivity of the ligands, which is an essential information at the designing stage of new Ca²⁺-indicators targeting different cellular compartments. Our data reflect a remarkably increased Mg²⁺-binding affinity of the compound with only a single oxygen linker between the two aromatic rings, as compared to that of BAPTA. These results suggest that while the Ca²⁺-binding affinity may be efficiently fine-tuned by modifying the length of the linker, the Ca²⁺ vs. Mg²⁺ selectivity might be unfavourably affected and one must pay attention to the potential coordination of a second metal ion to the ligands in the presence of metal ion excess.

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A theoretical study of Iron complexing with N-ligand: understand and design a catalyst

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Iron is a ubiquitous element, present both in nature and inside our bodies, for example, in hemoglobin and siderophores. From an inorganic chemistry standpoint, iron is a fascinating element found in variable oxidation and spin states depending on the binding ligands' nature showing exciting properties. (1) N-containing ligands are particularly interesting as they can stabilize iron (IV) or iron (V) through different geometries. The affinity of nonheme ligands with iron already showed a specific affinity for N atoms, which, through different nitrogen content, can result in various bindings. The binding nature, ionic or covalent, is one critical aspect influencing iron properties and reactivity. In this quest of understanding, theoretical and computational chemistry have been particularly efficient.

(2)

The present research develops a theoretical study of a particular iron compound coordinated with a nitrogenated ligand (N-ligand) to understand its catalytic effect on oxidative dehydrogenation reaction. This reaction is interesting because of its exothermic characteristics and its presence in fundamental reactions like alkene production from alkanes or amino acid synthesis. (3) In this work, the complex yields to oxidation that contributes to forming an imine from an amine through the transition metal intervention.

The metallic Fe³⁺ center coordinated with 1,9-bis(2'-pyridyl)-2,5,8-triazanonane or 1,9bis(3'pyridyl)-2,5,8-triazanonane ligands show a highly different behavior, not only in conformation but also in catalytic response. Moreover, the experimental results illustrated in the literature are supported by the theoretical results obtained. (4) Through DFT studies, the reaction mechanism was studied to explain the observed differences between both complexes. Furthermore, the mechanisms were probed under different solvents' actions to estimate which condition would favor oxidative dehydrogenation. And finally, theoretical chemistry can allow not only to explain but also to design additional modifications of this ligand, which will be tested to predict their catalytic activity.

An old-new ligand family for complexation of Cu(II) in radiotheragnostics

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1.2 million, this was the number of the assumed new cases of prostate cancer worldwide in 2018 causing major public health problem in Europe with increasing incidence and mortality. [1] According to CSO and WHO data, it is the second most frequent cancer diagnosis made in men and the fifth leading cause of death worldwide. Another, but at least as dangerous cancer type is the malignant melanoma (originates from melanin producing cutaneous melanocytes) have also high rate in the Caucasian population [2] by reason of its high metastatic potential. Less than the 20% of the affected patients have chance for a 5-year survival after the diagnoses, especially when widespread metastatic lesions are present in organs. [3] Therefore, the early diagnoses of both cancer types by use of sensitive imaging techniques such as PET (Positron emission tomography) or MRI (Magnetic resonance imaging) is a key for the effective therapy contributing to the long-term survival. [4] Of course, to achieve this goal it is necessary to find the best tools for indicating the small changes in tissues at the cellular level. Based on the results published in the last years, the radiolabelled prostate-specific membrane antigen (PSMA) has been deemed suitable for the detection of prostate cancer, while the NAPamide molecule (NAPamide is an alpha-MSH analog can specifically bind to MC1-R receptor located on the membrane of melanoma cells) can be used in the non-invasive detection of melanin producing melanoma tumors. [5]

In the last decade, there was a growing interest in the combined application of the targeted diagnosis and therapy (theragnostic) for the personalized and precise medicine. One of the most promising candidates for this purpose is the ⁶⁴Cu isotope thanks to its excellent decay properties ($t_{1/2}=12.7$ hours, β^+ 18%, β^- 39%). [6] The positrons arising from the decay of ⁶⁴Cu can be utilized for PET imaging, while the combination of the β^- and Auger electrons delivers the therapeutic effect. For these reasons, the application of ⁶⁴Cu isotope in radiopharmaceuticals could be a huge improvement in radiotherapy. Of course, for the successful applications, the *in vivo* degradation of the ⁶⁴Cu agents must be avoided by means of highly inert complexes (usually conjugated with biomolecules), [7] however the formation of the complexes with frequently used chelates is very slow. [8] The complexation of the Cu(II) ion for radiodiagnosis and radiotherapy should be fast even in acidic

condition considering the life time of the isotopes, furthermore the inertness of those has to be high enough to inhibit the *in vivo* dechelation, which may lead to the loss of the diagnostic and/or therapeutic effect. In practice, to accelerate the complexation of Cu(II) ion usually harsh circumstances are applied e.g. reflux in organic solvents or a long preparation time in aqueous solution. Therefore, it is easy to see that developments of ligands show fast complexation with Cu(II) is highly desired. For this reason, we have synthesized and studied the Cu(II) complexes of the simplest member of an old-new ligand family (Scheme 1.) and its nitrobenzyl derivative, to gain information on their thermodynamic stability, inertness and radiolabeling features. The synthesis of the pentaaza bicyclic 1,4,7,10,13-pentaazabicyclo[8.5.2]heptadecane (CB-15aneN5) (Scheme 1.), has been described almost two decades ago, however only one publication provides information on the physico-chemical parameters of its Cu(II) complex to date limited to its inertness.[9]

The results of our investigation show that the thermodynamic stability ($\log K = 28.3(1)$) of the [Cu(CB-15aneN5)] is high enough to keep the Cu(II) ion in complexed form above pH = 2. The dissociation half-lives of the [Cu(CB-15aneN5)] and [Cu(*p*NO₂Bn-CB-15aneN5)] chelates were found to be 8 and 140 minutes in the presence of 5.0 M HCl at 50 °C, respectively, providing very high inertness at physiological pH. Furthermore, the radiolabeling experiments of the *p*NO₂Bn-CB-15aneN5 with ⁶¹Cu(II) isotope indicated that the labeling is complete in μM range at pH = 6.0 and room temperature in less than 30 minutes. Based on these findings it can be concluded that this ligand family can provide promising platforms for Cu(II) complexation in radiodiagnostics and radiotherapy.

Scheme 1. The structure of the CB-15aneN5 and *p*NO₂Bn-CB-15aneN5 ligands.

Acknowledgement: The research was funded by the Hungarian National Research, Development and Innovation Office (NKFIH K-134694, PD-128326 and FK-134551 projects.)

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Copper(II) complexes of Tau protein fragments

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Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a progressive neurodegenerative disorder, its main symptom is dementia, and leads to decline of motor and cognitive function. Pathophysiological changes involving abnormal protein aggregation in the central nervous system characterise AD. These changes begin several years earlier before the first clinical symptoms appear. While aggregation of amyloid- β ($A\beta$) leads to the formation of extracellular amyloid plaques, aggregation of hyperphosphorylated Tau protein forms neurofibrillary tangles [1-4]. Previous studies also justified that metal ions such as Cu(II), Zn(II), Fe(II), that are essential for normal brain function, are accumulated in the brain of AD patients and contribute to hyperphosphorylation of Tau protein, leading to cell impairment. [5]. Tau protein contains 12 histidine amino acids in the sequence, which provide high metal binding affinity to Tau and its various peptide fragments. These residues with metal binding ability are well-separated and several other coordinating side chains are also available close to histidyl sites [6]. However the characterisation of the metal binding sites of Tau protein have not adequately been clarified yet.

The systematic investigation of Tau fragments containing the possible metal binding sites began a few years ago in our research group. As a first step we investigated the copper(II) complexes of fragments that contain seryl or threonyl residue close to histidyl sites: Ac-AQPHTEI (Tau 91-97), Ac-KTDHGA (Tau-385-390), Ac-SPRHLS (Tau-404-409). Beside serine and threonine, proline amino acid could also play crucial role in the stability and structure of copper complexes of these fragments, because the peptide binding formed from the secondary amine group does not allow its coordination. Therefore the coordination of Cu(II) ions to the proline containing peptides is modified relative to those of fragments without proline. Generally the imidazolyl group of histidine is the anchoring site of Tau protein, followed by deprotonation and coordination of peptide nitrogens preceding histidine at higher pH. However the presence of proline in two Tau fragments, Tau 91-97 and Tau 404-409, results in the deprotonation and coordination of the peptide nitrogen towards the C-termini and imidazole nitrogen is also replaced by amide nitrogen resulting in formation of $[CuLH_4]$ complexes.

The different complex formation processes are well reflected by distribution curves of three peptide-Cu(II) systems (Fig. 1.)

Biological properties of ruthenium cyclopentadienyl complexes bearing different imidato ligands

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The biological activity of Ru complexes has been widely investigated. Ru(III), and Ru(II) complexes have shown remarkable antitumor activity with various advantages than traditional platinum drugs [1]. Compared to platinum compounds, ruthenium complexes exhibit certain different physical, chemical and biological properties.

Cyclic imides and their *N*-derivatives possess structural features which confer biological activity. The imide ring contains -CO-N(R)-CO- functional group and thus is hydrophobic and neutral and can cross biological membranes *in vivo*. According to the literature, this group of compounds displays antibacterial, antifungal, antiviral [2], and antitumor activities [3].

In presented studies, we investigated a cyto- and genotoxic potential of four ruthenium cyclopentadienyl complexes bearing different imidato ligands: maleimide, phthalimide, succinimide. We used two types of cells – normal peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs) and leukemic HL-60 cells. We found that different properties of studied ruthenium complexes depend significantly on the type of imide ligand bind to the ruthenium atom.

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Can the Cu(II) ion-Prs1 protein fragment system be involved in the initiation of radical-forming processes leading to the onset of Alzheimer's disease?

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Alzheimer's disease (AD) is the most common neurodegenerative disease whose etiology is not yet fully understood.[1] A drug that would reverse the changes in the brain caused by this disease or completely inhibit the development of AD has still not been invented.[2,3] Therefore, it is extremely important to understand the new molecular mechanisms of this disease.

The Presenilin 1 (Prs1) human protein located in the brain may play a key role in the development of Alzheimer's disease. This protein has the ability to coordinate transition metal ions (TMI) such as Cu(II) ions, which are one of the most widespread TMI in the brain.[4] Moreover, Prs1 is responsible for the transport of Cu(II) ions, as well as their homeostasis.[5-7] It is therefore highly probable that Prs1 binds Cu(II) ions in the brain and in the presence of endogenous oxidants and reducing agents (*e.g.* hydrogen peroxide or ascorbic acid) [8,9], participates in the formation of the hydroxyl radical ($\cdot\text{OH}$) (in the Fenton reaction) contributing to the initiation of AD.

A coordination process of Cu(II) ion to the Ac-HWKGPLR-NH₂ (**L1**) and Ac-RDShLGPHRST-NH₂ (**L2**) peptide ligands (from Prs1 protein) containing one or two histidyl residues in their sequences, respectively, was studied by potentiometry, spectroscopic methods (UV-Vis, CD, EPR) and MS technique. Both ligands are capable of forming mononuclear complexes with a metal ion in the 1:1 M:L molar ratio. Moreover, the **L2** ligand after binding of Cu(II) ions (in the 2:1 M:L molar ratio) forms dinuclear complexes in the aqueous solution. The CuH₂L species with the 3N {N_{im}, 2N⁻} coordination mode and the CuH₂L complex with the 4N {N_{im}, 3N⁻} binding sites are present at pH 7.2 (intracellular brain pH) for the Cu(II)-Ac-HWKGPLR-NH₂ (**CuL1**) system. In the case of the Cu(II)-Ac-RDShLGPHRST-NH₂ (**CuL2**) complex, the CuH₂L species with 4N {2N_{im}, 2N⁻} donor atoms dominates at pH 7.2. In addition, CD spectroscopy confirmed that the **L2** ligand changes its secondary structure only after metal ion coordination, which may affect the toxicity of the resulting system.

The ability of uncomplexed Cu(II) ions, ligands and their complexes in the presence of hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) or ascorbic acid (Asc) to produce reactive oxygen species (ROS) at pH 7.2 was also studied. The following methods were used for ROS detection: *i)* UV-Vis spectroscopy (with NDMA- *N,N*-dimethyl-*p*-nitrosoaniline and NBT- nitroblue tetrazolium as respectively $\cdot\text{OH}$ and O₂⁻ detectors); *ii)* fluorescence spectroscopy (with TA- terephthalic acid as $\cdot\text{OH}$ detector); and *iii)* gel electrophoresis with/without SOD- superoxide dismutase, DMSO- dimethyl sulfoxide and NaN₃- sodium azide as O₂⁻, $\cdot\text{OH}$ and ¹O₂ scavengers, respectively. The complexes have been shown to produce the highest level of ROS, which are also involved in the radical mechanism of plasmid degradation.

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Acknowledgements:

The author gratefully acknowledge financial support from the Ministry of Science and Higher Education (4478/E-344/M/2018). The UV-Vis measurements were carried out with the equipment purchased thanks to the financial support of the Polish National Science Centre (Grant 2016/23/D/ST5/00269). The author would like to thank Prof. dr hab. Teresa Kowalik-Jankowska for her support and assistance in research.

Coordination and catalytic features of NiSOD related metallopeptides

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Superoxide dismutases are a dedicate class of enzyme family capable of catalyzing the decomposition of superoxide anion radical in the extracellular matrix. [1,2] The dismutation reaction yields molecular dioxygen and hydrogen peroxide that degrades through various pathways in further reactions catalyzed by catalase or glutathione peroxidase to yield harmful products. [3,4] The absence of these enzymes results in an elevated level of superoxide anion concentration which can cause oxidative stress, formation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and extensive cellular damaging. [5,6] Several studies also reported that the intensive ROS generation can act as a mediator of a number of inflammatory diseases. [7] Copper/zinc, manganese and iron containing SOD enzymes are characterized by several methods such as structural, equilibrium and computational analysis. However, for the relatively novel class of Ni-containing SOD enzymes, the controlled design of the active site has not been reported so far. Consequently, the models of the NiSOD enzymes are the subject of great interest.

In our work, systematic studies have been performed to explore the thermodynamic, structural and catalytic features of several peptides mimicking the N-terminal binding site of NiSOD enzyme. [8-10] Moreover, the active center of the metallopeptides has also been fine tuned to control the metal assisted dismutation of the superoxide anion radical. The model complexes bearing the NiSOD binding motif exhibit superior SOD activity and high thermodynamic stability. Nickel(III) species were generated by oxidizing the Ni(II) complexes with KO₂ and the coordination modes were identified by EPR spectroscopy. Moreover, the structure of the Ni(III) species was further corroborated by computational investigations.

A detailed kinetic model of the dismutation is also postulated which incorporates spontaneous decomposition of the superoxide ion, the dismutation cycle and the intramolecular redox degradation of the complexes. A unique feature of these systems is that the Ni(III) form of the catalyst rapidly accumulates in the dismutation cycle and simultaneously the Ni(II) form becomes a minor species. On the basis of these results, the complexes are excellent models of the native SOD enzyme.

Figure 1. Representative structures for the most populated cluster obtained along the 200 ns MD for the nickel(II) complex of NiSOD fragment containing penicillamine moiety (a). DFT optimized conformations (B97D) accounting for the experimental EPR parameters of Ni(III)–wtSOD (b) and Ni(III)–wtPen (c).

Acknowledgements: N.L. and I.F. are grateful for the financial support of the Hungarian National Research, Development and Innovation Office (NKFIH PD-128326 and K-124983). The research was also financed by the EU and co-financed by the European Regional Development Fund (under the projects GINOP-2.3.2-15-2016-00008). E.G. and G.S. thank Regione Autonoma della Sardegna (grant RASSR79857) for financial support. This work is also supported by the ÚNKP-20-4-II New National Excellence Program of the Ministry for Innovation and Technology from the source of the National, Research, Development and Innovation Fund and prepared with the professional support of the Doctoral Student Scholarship Program of the Co-operative Doctoral Program of the Ministry of Innovation and Technology financed from the National Research, Development and Innovation Office.

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Access to free Zn concentrations in systems of biological interest with AGNES

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Free Zn²⁺ concentrations have been reported as playing a key role in many biological systems, ranging from signaling to regulation of energy metabolism in mammalian blood [1]. Given the large number of possible Zn complexes, with ligands whose exact concentration is often unknown, and the uncertainties in many of their stability constants, computational methods can only provide rough estimations. The typical experimental approach has relied on the use of fluorescent dyes, but they encounter various interferences, such as the uncontrolled formation of ternary complexes (i.e. dye+Zn+ligand), and correcting for these effects is still difficult [2].

AGNES (Absence of Gradients and Nernstian Equilibrium Stripping) is an electroanalytical technique specifically designed to measure free metal ion concentrations of amalgamating metals such as Zn, In, Cd, Pb, Sn, etc. [3]. In several instances [4], AGNES has been able to discriminate amongst competing complexation models (i.e. indicate which sets of the proposed stability constants are not compatible with the direct [Zn²⁺] provided by AGNES).

In this contribution, the implementation of AGNES to measure [Zn²⁺] in systems of biological interest will be reported. This implementation combines: i) the use of a thin film mercury electrode that reduces the required deposition time, due to the small mercury volume and the high mass transfer rate and ii) the covering of the mercury surface with Nafion[®] to avoid electrodic adsorption and undesired redox reactions of large molecules. Two systems have been used for this proof of concept study: a) A mixture of Bovine Serum Albumin (BSA) with Zn²⁺ and b) Fetal Bovine Serum (FBS). Retrieved concentrations are consistent with expectations and lend support to this new (complementary) approach to better understand the role of Zn in biological systems.

Acknowledgements:

Support from the Spanish Minister of Science and Innovation is gratefully acknowledged (Project PID2019-107033GB). This project has received funding from the European Union's H2020 research and innovation programme under Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 801586. CAB thanks the Leverhulme Trust (RPG-2017-214) for support.

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Molecular and supramolecular aspects in mono- and dinuclear Cu(II) complexes with a synthetic adenine nucleoside

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As a part of our research program on metal complexes with the synthetic purine nucleoside N9(2-hydroxyethyl)adenine (9heade), we have reacted it with aqueous $\text{Cu}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ solutions, using different 9heade:Cu molar ratios (from ~4:1 to 1:1) [1]. A solution with molar ratio (4.4):1 yielded $[\text{Cu}_2(\mu\text{-OH})_2(9\text{heade})_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4](\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 2(9\text{heade}) \cdot 11\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (**1**, triclinic, $P\bar{1}$, 100 K, R_1 0.098) with two non-equivalent but rather similar dinuclear cations, with $\text{Cu}\cdots\text{Cu}$ distance of 3.00 Å (Fig. 1). Herein, the overall excess of 9heade leads to its reaction with water, generating the bridging hydroxide ligands.

Figure 1. Structure of the complex cation $[\text{Cu}_2(\mu\text{-OH})_2(9\text{heade})_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]^{2+}$ in compound **1** (a: 1-x, -y, 1-z).

A solution with 9heade:Cu molar ratio 2:1 initially produced small long blue crystals. However, the action of sun light on the crystallizer (covered with a tight plastic film) induced its recrystallization, generating parallelepiped shaped crystals of $[\text{Cu}_2(\mu\text{-OH})_2(\mu\text{-ClO}_4)_2(9\text{heade})_4] \cdot 6.75(\text{H}_2\text{O})$ (**2**, Fig. 2). In this crystal [triclinic, $P\bar{1}$, 100 K, R_1 0.045], the acyclic arm of 9heade and water are disordered. After several days, crystalline samples of **2** (contained in Eppendorf vials) underwent an additional recrystallization event, generating some new greenish crystals of compound *cis*- $[\text{Cu}(9\text{heade})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4](\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 2(9\text{heade})$ (**3**, Fig. 3). Note that, in **3**, the real ratio 9heade:Cu is 4:1. Therefore, a new synthesis with such

9heade:Cu 4:1 stoichiometry was designed to reproduce the crystallization of compound **3** [monoclinic, *C2/c*, 298 K, R_1 0.069] (Fig. 3).

Figure 2. a) Recrystallized parallelepiped crystals of **2**; b) Structure of the dinuclear complex molecule of **2** [Cu...Cu 2.877(1) Å] (a: $1-x$, $1-y$, $1-z$).

Compound **3** (Fig. 3) represents a centro-symmetric entity encompassing the *cis*-complex cation, two perchlorate anions and two solvate 9heade molecules. This is contrary to the higher thermodynamic stability expected for its *trans*-isomer.

Figure 3. Molecular structure of **3**, showing intra-complex and supra-cation-anion molecular recognition cooperating in the *cis*-coordination of both 9heade ligands (a: $-x+1$, y , $-z+1/2$).

The *cis*-conformation of the complex cation of **3** features at least two interesting singularities. First, the intra-molecular interligand interaction involves the distal O2-(aqua distal, Cu1-O2 2.550(3) Å) acceptor atom. Indeed the N6-H6...O2(aqua, distal) [2.989(4) Å, 159.1°] cooperates with the Cu-N7(9heade) bond (2.007(3) Å). Secondly, the anion-cation recognition by means of two (aqua)O-H...O(perchlorate) H-bonds, namely (proximal aqua)O1-H1b...O3(ClO₄) [2.748(4) Å, 162.1°] and (distal aqua)O2-H2b...O6^a(ClO₄) [2.986(7) Å, 157.1°, $a = -x+1, y, -z+1/2$].

Acknowledgements: Financial support from Projects No. PGC2018-102047-B-I00 (MCIU/AEI/FEDER, UE) and PPIIA2019-03 (UGR), and Junta de Andalucía (FQM-283) is gratefully acknowledged. A.D.-M. and M.B.-O. acknowledge support from Cost Action CA18202—Network for Equilibria and Chemical Thermodynamics Advanced Research.

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A new bis-squaramide chemosensor for the detection of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs

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Among the many pharmaceutical chemicals found in waters, non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) are the most ubiquitous. These chemicals are not routinely monitored and they have been generally grouped as Emerging Pollutants (EPs). The Directive 2013/39/EU of European Union defines EPs as pollutants not currently included in routine monitoring programs but which could pose a significant risk that require regulation, depending upon their potential eco-toxicological and toxicological effects and on their levels in the aquatic environment. [1]

Given the relatively low levels of detection, their negative effects on humans and the biosphere are related to their constant releases into the environment, leading to long-term high concentrations. The problem with these biological active molecules lies in their high stability, which gives them resistance to biodegradation, ecotoxicity, persistence and consequently make them a threat to the environment and migration in the food chain. [2]

Figure 1. Structure of **L** and UV-titration in DMSO of **L** and Sodium Ibuprofen

Herein we report a hydrogen bond donor squaramide chemosensor (**L**) which can strongly interact with anions of carboxylic acids through the converging hydrogen bonds; donor groups are placed at a suitable distance to be able to coordinate an oxygen atom of the carboxylate group. This receptor is able to strongly interact with selected substrates giving changes in physico-chemical properties of the system that can be measured through spectroscopic methods (**Figure 1**).

Results for binding and recognition processes towards NSAIDs obtained with chemosensor **L** will be presented.

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Curcumin derivatives as Platinum (II) coordination system for colon-rectal cancer therapy

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Curcumin (**Figure 1, A**) is well known for its countless therapeutic properties, including antitumor, anti-inflammatory, antimetastatic activity, as well as inhibitory of angiogenesis [1]. These, together with its high affinity for colon-rectal cancer cells, makes it a feasible tool for selective chemotherapy [2]. Despite its properties, it has a few problematic sides that must be considered: low solubility in water, low rate of intestinal absorption and rapid degradation in physiological media. These features could be attributed to the presence of the β -diketo moiety that make it a challenging compound to deal with. The synthesis of similar derivatives that possess higher water solubility as well as increased stability may bring to new lead compounds for pharmacological purposes.

Platinum complexes, cisplatin above all, are nowadays widespread and well-known therapeutics for the treatment of different cancers, mainly prostate and ovarian. Oxaliplatin was the first platinum-based anticancer drug to be approved in 1999 by EMA and in 2002 by FDA, and successfully applied for the clinical treatment of colorectal cancer, a major cause of cancer deaths worldwide [3, 4].

Developing new curcumin analogues with improved chemical features and able to bind Platinum(II) may lead to more effective platinum-based drugs, that benefit of both Pt(II) interaction with DNA and antiproliferative activity of curcumin, hence allowing lower dosages and possibly side

Figure 1. A – Curcumin chemical structure; **B** – chemical structure of MPYC3NH2 [4-((E)-2-[4-(3-aminopropoxy)-3-methoxyphenyl]ethenyl]-6-methylpyrimidin-2-amine]. effects.

To accomplish the requirements of stability and higher solubility, the new compound MPYC3NH2 (**Figure 1, B**) was synthesized. In this new derivative, the β -diketo moiety was replaced with an amino-

Figure 2. From bottom to top, ^1H NMR spectra of: MPYC3NH₂ (MeOD-*d*₄), K₂PtCl₄:MPYC3NH₂ 1:1 immediately after K₂PtCl₄ addition (MeOD-*d*₄/D₂O 500µL/150µL), K₂PtCl₄:MPYC3NH₂ 1:1 after 24h (MeOD-*d*₄/D₂O 500µL/150µL), K₂PtCl₄:MPYC3NH₂ 1:1 after 1 week (MeOD-*d*₄/D₂O 500µL/150µL). Spectra were acquired at 298 K at 600 MHz.

pyrimidine ring and the phenolic group was functionalized with an alkyl chain with an amine ending group. This amine is meant to be both the coordinating agent for Pt²⁺ and a reactive group for further structural modifications. The molecular weight below the cut-off value of 500 Da in combination with the presence of polar groups may account for sufficient water solubility and cellular uptake. A complete $^1\text{H}/^{13}\text{C}$ NMR characterization with both 1D and 2D techniques was carried out, as well as the acid-base behaviour by spectrophotometric techniques. UV-vis data allowed to evaluate protonation stability constants. Complexation study by UV-vis analysis was instead prevented by the extremely slow kinetics of the complexation

reaction. For this reason, the complexation process with Pt²⁺ (K₂PtCl₄) was investigated by ^1H and ^{195}Pt NMR. As shown in **Figure 2**, proton spectra point out downfield shifts of signals belonging to the alkylic-amine chain. This outcome indicates the effective formation of a metal-complex species with slow kinetics. It should be noted that the most affected signal is the one of the -CH₂- groups directly bound to the amine group, while the shift gets less evident for the -CH₂- protons in β and γ positions.

This preliminary results are encouraging and suggest that these studies may lead to a new class of compounds although further biological studies need to be carried out.

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Small antioxidant amino-nanozymes able to disaggregate Hunting-ton's inclusion bodies

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Huntington disease is known as one of the most devastating neurological pathologies that modern societies faces nowadays. Some of the key issues underlying the generation of such neurological ailment are the formation of Huntingtin aggregates in cerebellum, striatum and/or cortex, dyshomeostasis and chelation of Cu^{2+} by the mutant Huntingtin fibrils, and oxidative stress.[1,2] Up to date, very little success has been achieved in the treatment of Huntington disease. In this work we report the synthesis of a novel amino-nanozyme, with both a striking antioxidant activity and the capacity to disaggregate the Huntington's inclusion bodies. The nanozyme is based on the anchorage of a tetraaza-macrocyclic onto the surface of boehmite nanoparticles. By means of potentiometric methods we determine the capacity of the macrocycle to quantitatively subtract Cu^{2+} from medium, while using McCord-Fridovich assays and in vitro mitochondria oxidative stress evaluations we figure out the notably high antioxidant activity of the resulting complexes, dramatically enhanced by the grafting of the ligand onto the nanoparticles. Furthermore, we also show the capacity of the amino-nanozymes to significantly reduce the mutant Huntingtin deposits in cells. The results here exposed suggest the potential use of the developed amino-nanozymes as antioxidant and disaggregating agents in the treatment of diseases associated with both misfolded proteins that create aggregates in the cells and oxidative stress.

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Impact of Cu(II) and Zn(II) ions on antimicrobial peptides from marine creatures

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In the face of the worldwide increase of antimicrobial resistance, new more potent and more specific therapeutics are intensively sought. [1]

Antimicrobial peptides are a very diverse group of 7 to about 100 amino acid molecules. They are present in all multicellular organisms and take part in the innate immune response. [2, 3] They can be divided according to their charge, secondary structure, presence of specific amino acid residues, or to their functions. So far, more than 3250 peptides have been isolated, presenting antibacterial, antifungal, antiviral, antiparasitic and even anti-cancer properties. [4] Importantly, with few exceptions, pathogens do not show any significant resistance towards them, [5] which makes them promising candidates in the fight with drug resistance.

Additionally, biologically relevant metal ions, such as Cu(II) and Zn(II) can also have an impact on the antimicrobial peptides' activity. For example, peptides can bind them, so that microbes cannot get enough metals essential for their life and virulence, or AMPs can use the given metal ion to boost their antimicrobial activity. [3]

Marine organisms are a very rich source of antimicrobial peptides. In this work, we focus on two peptide families: clavanins and piscidins.

Clavanins are cationic, histidine-rich antimicrobial peptides, isolated from the sea squirt *Styela clava*. [6] They contain 23 amino acid residues and in the membrane-mimicking environment, and form an alpha-helical structure. This peptide family consists of five highly-conserved members: clavanin A, B, C, D and E and one of them (clavanin C) possess a very characteristic N-terminal motif (so-called 'ATCUN-motif'). [7] According to the literature, at pH 5.5, they were effective against bacterial strains such as *Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. [8, 9]

Piscidins were isolated from the mast cells of hybrid striped bass [10]. In this work, piscidin 1, 2 and 3 were analysed. These peptides contain 22 amino acids and, similarly to clavanins, show an alpha-helical structure and positive charge. As clavanin C, they comprise an ATCUN-motif. [11] Literature data confirms their antibacterial and antiviral activity, highlighting the differences in their modes of action: piscidin 1 is more membrane-disrupting, while piscidin 3 is more likely to show a nuclease activity. [12-14]

The aim of this research was to find and understand the relationships between the coordination chemistry, structure, stability, mode of action and biological activity of the Cu(II) and Zn(II) complexes of the chosen peptides.

All studied complexes have a 1:1 stoichiometry. Clavanins bind Zn(II) ions with similar affinity, by three imidazole groups of histidines. Cu(II) ions are bound to imidazoles, and (at higher pH) three amide groups. Clavanin C is an exception, because of the presence of the N-terminal ATCUN motif, which coordinates Cu(II) ions by the N-terminal amine group, two amide nitrogens and imidazole group of the His3 residue. Moreover, because of this motif, clavanin C has a higher affinity towards Cu(II) ions than the rest of clavanins. All clavanins have shown antifungal properties, and the highest antibacterial activity was observed for the Zn(II)-clavanin C complex.

Similar to clavanin C, all piscidins contain an ATCUN motif, which determines their mode of Cu(II) coordination. Among these complexes, at physiological pH, piscidin 2 has a slightly higher affinity towards Cu(II). Zn(II) complexes show similar stability, with a minor advantage of piscidin 3. Zn(II) ions are probably coordinated by three imidazole groups of histidines and one water molecule. What is most important, piscidins occurred to be very effective not only against bacterial strains (more effective than commercially used antibiotics) but also showed anticancer activity.

Acknowledgements: Financial support by the National Science Centre (UMO 2017/26/A/ST5/00364 is gratefully acknowledged.

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Iron(III) and gallium(III) complexes of ferrioxamine e biomimetic analogues – coordination chemistry and biological activity

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Multi-drug-resistant bacterial and fungal infections are emerging problem, [1] that is why development of new diagnostic and treatment strategies is highly demanded.

Novel diagnostics and treatments and ways to specifically deliver them to drug resistant bacteria and invasive mycoses are being actively sought. We aim to find pathogen-specific theranostics that will not cause severe side-effects in patients in accordance to selective toxicity rule.

Those properties are presented by wide group of microbe-produced low molecular weight compounds – siderophores, which are used by bacteria and fungi to acquire ferric ions that are crucial for their viability. Although pathogen-selective targets are scarce, what arises from the fact that bacteria and fungi share essential metabolic pathways with humans there is at least one significant difference between the microbial and mammalian cells: the transport of transition metal ions.

We want to focus on the transport of indispensable metal ion – Fe(III). It's effective acquisition is often considered as a virulence factor. Bacteria and fungi have developed highly efficient transport systems, which rely on siderophores – metal chelating molecules which are excreted outside the pathogen in order to efficiently bind iron ion. Then, the ferric-siderophore complex is uptaken via high specificity receptors into bacterial cell [2].

Figure 1. Structure model of native siderophore Desferrioxamine E (DFO E)

To fully understand mechanisms of those processes and utilize them, we need to examine thermodynamics and coordination chemistry of siderophores towards iron ions. It is also a necessity to comprehend transportation mechanisms of siderophore complexes. To make that possible we are investigating not only natural siderophores but also analogues with structural differences.

DFO E analogues were labelled with radioactive gallium-68 isotope to study in vitro and in vivo properties of these novel compounds for molecular imaging using Positron Emission Tomography (PET). [3,4,5].

Here we will present our current advancements in research concerning Ferrioxamine E alongside with its biomimetic analogues.

Acknowledgements: The financial support from the National Science Centre Poland (UMO-2015/19/B/ST5/00413 and 2017/26/A/ST5/00363) is gratefully acknowledged.

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Interactions of *p*-coumaric acid with physiologically relevant metals in aqueous solution

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p-Coumaric acid (4-hydroxycinnamic acid) (*p*-CA, Scheme 1) belongs to the group of phenolic acids and is one of the three hydroxyl derivatives of cinnamic acid that exists either in free or conjugated forms in plants. It is present in many fruits, vegetables, graminaceous plants and some mushroom species (used in traditional Chinese medicines).[1]

Scheme 1. Structure of *p*-coumaric acid (*p*-CA)

The literature survey shows that *p*-CA acid possess the ability to effectively inhibit the growth of bacterial pathogens.[2] The mechanism of its antibacterial action is based on disrupting bacterial cell membranes and inhibition of cellular functions by binding to bacterial genomic DNA that cause the cell death. It is also reported that metal complexes of phenolic acids may exhibit higher antibacterial properties when compared with those of the free ligands. Therefore, the aim of this study is the evaluation of the interactions of *p*-CA acid with physiologically relevant metals (Mg, Ca, Zn) in aqueous solution. The formation of complexes through the changes in the distribution of the electronic charge in the ligand, may cause a change in the mechanism of their interaction with cellular membranes and consequently increase their biological activity. In the future, this will allow to design new, safe for humans, substances with antimicrobial activity, that potentially could be used as food preservatives.

In this communication we will present the solution thermodynamic study of *p*-CA and its complexes with physiologically important metals. Potentiometric and spectrophotometric titration techniques were used to investigate the acid-base behaviour of *p*-CA as well as its complexation ability towards Mg²⁺, Ca²⁺ and Zn²⁺ in aqueous solution over a wide range of pH values (2 ≤ pH ≤ 8), at *I* = 0.1 mol dm⁻³ KCl_(aq) and *T* = 25°C. Some results on ¹H-NMR experiments will be also reported.

Acknowledgements: This work was financially supported by National Science Centre, Poland, under the research project number 2018/29/B/NZ9/01997.

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Pd-DNA hybrids as adaptable systems for nanoscience applications

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DNA has been employed to develop applications in nanoscience and nanotechnology. [1] For instance, they have been shown to guide the growth of metal-based nanowires that could find applications in a new generation of nanoelectronics devices.[2] However, the atomic-level control over the position and growth of a single continuous metal chain that would be necessary for industrial applications is still lacking. Our group has developed a different approach to tackle this problem. [3] We have used a self-assembly reaction between the DNA and Pd(II) complexes that allow controlling the position and stoichiometry of the Pd(II) ions along with the DNA support, giving rise to the formation of a Pd- (1D) one-dimensional (Figure 1).[3b]

Figure 1. Reaction scheme between single-stranded DNA (ss-DNA) and a Pd(II) complex giving to Pd-DNA hybrid comprising consecutive Pd-mediated base pairs.

Here we present our latest results regarding the preparation and characterization of Pd-DNA and Pd-RNA 1D chains. In these systems the interaction between the Pd(II) complexes and the bases of the ss-DNA or ss-RNA strands lead to the formation of consecutive Pd-mediated base pairs with an organization similar to natural base pairs, but where a coordination bond replaces a hydrogen bond.

We have studied these Pd-DNA systems utilizing circular dichroism (CD), small-angle X-ray scattering (SAXS), isothermal titration calorimetry (ITC), atomic force microscopy (AFM), and ab-initio calculations. AFM experiments were performed with ss-RNA molecules (> 2500 bases). The results show the formation of well-differentiated Pd-RNA chains, with a height slightly higher than those observed for free ss-RNA (Figure 2, left). The ITC experiments suggest the existence of two types of binding modes between the Pd(II) complex and the bases of the DNA that could be cooperative, but the first of them giving rise to the most stable species (Figure 2, right).

Figure 2. Left: AFM images for the Pd-RNA hybrids. Right: ITC for the interaction between ss-DNA and Pd(II) complexes.

Acknowledgements: Fiancial support from Spanish MINECO (CTQ2017-89311-P), Spanish MICIU (Salvador Madariaga Program, Red. PRX19/00290), University of Granada (A-FQM-465-UGR18), and Junta de Andalucía (FQM-293 and FQM-283).

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Estrone-salicylaldehyde *N*-methylated-thiosemicarbazone hybrids and their copper complexes: solution study and anticancer activity in tumor spheroids

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Thiosemicarbazones (TSCs) are considered to be potential therapeutics, since they possess a broad range of biological properties including antitumor, antimalarial and antimicrobial activity. Furthermore, metal complex formation can induce higher activity in comparison to the free ligand, and some side effects may be decreased upon complexation. Salicylaldehyde TSC (STSC) and its derivatives were reported to form high stability complexes with transition metal ions in solution and to exhibit marked cytotoxicity [1]. In our previous work, a tridentate estrone-STSC hybrid molecule (estrone-TSC) and an analogous bicyclic derivative (thn-TSC) were developed [2], which proved to be cytotoxic against the hormone-responsive MCF-7 breast cancer cell line (IC₅₀: thn-TSC: 3.7 μM, estrone-TSC: 6.4 μM). Moreover, their Cu(II) complexes were significantly more cytotoxic than the ligands by 1-2 orders of magnitude. Disubstitution of the terminal-NH₂ groups in case of several α-N-pyridine TSCs could result in highly increased anticancer activity (*e.g.* dimethylated Triapine, DpC, Dp44mT) [3]. According to this finding, in this work the terminal *N*-mono- and -dimethylated derivatives of estrone-TSC and thn-TSC (Chart 1) and their Cu(II) complexes were prepared to obtain more effective compounds. While the same (*O,N,S*) coordination mode is expected in these novel complexes as for the reference compounds estrone-TSC and thn-TSC, the substituents on the TSC backbone can distinctly modify the solution stability, lipophilicity and size of the complexes, thus might influence the biological activity as well.

Chart 1. Chemical structures of the investigated ligands

Deprotonation processes of the novel hybrids and the solution stability of the Cu(II) complexes were characterized. Moreover, the anticancer activity was studied via *in vitro* cytotoxicity and ROS generation assays, and the cell proliferation, apoptosis and its caspase-dependence were also screened in three-dimensional cancer spheroids, which are considered to mimic the main features of human solid tumors better compared to traditional 2D cultures.

Acknowledgements:

National Research, Development and Innovation Office-NKFIA projects GINOP-2.3.2-15-2016-00038, FK 124240 and Ministry of Human Capacities (Hungary) grant TKP-2020. Visegrad Scholarship 52010752 (T. V. P.).

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8-Hydroxyquinoline-amino acid hybrids and their half-sandwich Ru and Rh complexes with anticancer aspects: solution chemistry and interaction with biomolecules

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Development of novel chemotherapeutic agents aims to obtain more effective and selective compounds. Platinum(II)-containing chemotherapeutics are widely used for decades in cancer therapy against solid tumors due to their effectiveness. Although, their use is accompanied by drawbacks such as serious side-effects, due to the lack of selectivity, and resistance [1]. To overcome these problems, efforts have been made to find better alternatives such as the complexes of other platinum metals. Furthermore, 8-hydroxyquinolines and their metal complexes are also widely investigated, due to their prominent anticancer properties [2,3]; however, they often have limited water solubility. In this work, two novel water-soluble 8-hydroxyquinoline-D-amino acid hybrids, [(R)-1-((5-chloro-8-hydroxyquinolin-7-yl)methyl)pyrrolidine-2-carboxylic acid (8HQCl-D-Pro) and its homologue 8HQCl-D-hPro (Scheme 1), and their [Ru(η^6 -*p*-cymene)(H₂O)₃]²⁺ and [Rh(η^5 -C₅Me₅)(H₂O)₃]²⁺ complexes were developed.

Scheme 1. Chemical structure of the ligands and the organometallic triaqua cations and ORTEP view of the complex [Rh(η^5 -C₅Me₅)(8HQCl-D-hPro)Cl]

Previously, an 8-hydroxyquinoline-L-proline hybrid and its half-sandwich complexes have already been investigated in our group [4]. Herein, we aimed to understand (i) the impact of changing the structure (proline vs. homoproline) and chirality (L vs. D) of the ligand on the anticancer activity, (ii) solution chemical properties, (iii) complex formation with $[\text{Ru}(\eta^6\text{-}p\text{-cymene})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]^{2+}$ and $[\text{Rh}(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{Me}_5)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]^{2+}$ (Scheme 1) as well as (iv) their interactions with biomolecules such as human serum albumin (HSA) and calf-thymus DNA (ct-DNA).

The ligands and the metal complexes were synthesized similar to the analogous 8HQCl-L-Pro and its complexes in our previous work [4]. pH-Potentiometry, UV-visible spectrophotometry and ^1H NMR spectroscopy were utilized to characterize the proton dissociation processes of the ligands as well as the complex formation equilibria. pK_a values determined for 8HQCl-D-Pro and 8HQCl-D-hPro have revealed that these ligands are mostly neutral at physiological pH; however, due to their zwitter-ionic structure at the proline moiety, they possess excellent water-solubility. All the metal complexes were characterized by high solution stability in the whole pH range, moreover, X-ray crystallographic analysis of the complex $[\text{Rh}(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{Me}_5)(8\text{HQCl-D-hPro})\text{Cl}]$ has revealed the predicted (N,O) coordination to the metal centers. The proton dissociation of the coordinated water and the non-coordinated proline-NH⁺ of the bound ligand was characterized by such high pK_a values that their deprotonation does not take place at pH 7.4. $\text{Rh}(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{Me}_5)$ -complexes possess stronger chloride ion affinity, based on the $\log K'$ values determined for the $\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{Cl}^-$ exchange process. The homoproline derivative 8HQCl-D-hPro was more lipophilic than 8HQCl-D-Pro, and the same trend was observed for the metal complexes as well. The higher chloride ion concentration of the medium increases the lipophilicity of the complexes due to the higher fraction of the neutral chlorido complex.

All the complexes were able to interact with HSA. The results were compared to those of the analogous 8HQCl-L-Pro half-sandwich complexes. Formation of the complex-HSA adducts was much slower for $\text{Ru}(\eta^6\text{-}p\text{-cymene})$ complexes and no ligand release was found upon the protein binding. Our studies suggest the coordination nature of the binding, most likely a histidine nitrogen donor atom of the protein coordinates to the metal center. The complexes have strong affinity towards HSA according to the fluorometric and CZE measurements. They also interact with ct-DNA, however, significant differences were found between the complexes formed with the D-proline and the L-proline derivatives.

All the ligands and $\text{Rh}(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{Me}_5)$ -complexes showed significant cytotoxicity in Colo 205 and Colo 320 adenocarcinoma cells. The $\text{Rh}(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{Me}_5)$ -complexes were more selective against the cancer cells, while the $\text{Ru}(\eta^6\text{-}p\text{-cymene})$ complexes were ineffective against both cancer cell lines.

Acknowledgements: This work was supported by the ÚNKP-20-5 – New National Excellence Program of the Ministry for Innovation and Technology from the source of the National Research, Development and Innovation Fund and through projects GINOP-2.3.215-2016-00038, FK 124240 and Ministry of Human Capacities, Hungary grant, TKP-2020.

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A comparative solution equilibrium study on the interactions of Cu(II), Fe(II/III) and Zn(II) with COTI-2 and its derivatives

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Thiosemicarbazones (TSCs) and their metal complexes have a wide variety of structures and pharmacological effects. These compounds often act as inhibitors of the ribonucleotide reductase enzyme. Their best-known representative is 3-aminopyridine-2-carbaldehyde thiosemicarbazone (Triapine), currently undergoing phase III clinical testing [1]. Triapine has low activity against solid cancer types, which have prompted the development of additional derivatives, including COTI-2, which shows improved antitumor activity [2]. Development of anticancer compounds requires the in-depth knowledge about the structure-solution behaviour/bioactivity relationships. Additionally, there is an ongoing discussion that the complexation of thiosemicarbazones with metal ions in the human body plays a crucial role in the mechanism of action.

The goal of our work was to study the solution chemical properties of COTI-2 and its various derivatives (HL¹, HL², HL³) and their metal binding abilities towards Cu(II), Fe(II/III) and Zn(II) ions. We investigated how structural changes affect proton dissociation constants, lipophilicity and membrane permeability of these ligands by the means of UV-visible spectrophotometry, parallel artificial membrane permeability assay (PAMPA) and *n*-octanol/water distribution assays. Furthermore, the solution stability, structure and redox properties of their metal complexes were characterized by UV-visible spectrophotometry, EPR spectroscopy, X-ray crystallography and cyclic voltammetry. Interaction of the Cu(II) complexes with glutathione was also studied as this reaction seems to have an important role in the resistance profile of certain TSCs [2].

Acknowledgements:

This work was supported by the ÚNKP-20-3-SZTE-483 New National Excellence Program of the Ministry for Innovation and Technology from the Source of the National Research, Development and Innovation Fund and the Austrian Science Fund (FWF) grant P31923.

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Mycobacterial ArsR-Smtb family of virulence proteins as a ligands for Ni(II) ions.

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The latest report published by WHO shows that in 2019, 1.4 million people died due to tuberculosis (TB) as a result of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* infections. [1] The COVID-19 pandemic strongly impacts the number of global deaths from TB. Considering the fact that even a slight variations of metal ions concentration inside bacteria cell easily disrupt functioning of pathogen [2,3], understanding the process of maintaining metal homeostasis by bacteria may be an important step on a way to overpower multidrug-resistant *M. tuberculosis*.

In this study, the properties of metal-binding domains of BigR4 and SmtB – important mycobacterial regulators of metal ions as a ligands for Ni(II) ions, were investigated. Both BigR4 and SmtB belong to the ArsR-SmtB family of proteins, which role is to regulate the transcription of genes responsible for metal-regulators biosynthesis. [4] The sequences of the studied peptides are as follows: **L1** - ₁₀₁DHHLAHIVVDAIAHASEDRR₁₂₀ (BigR4) and **L4** - ₁₀₁DHHLAHIVLDAVAHAGEDAI₁₂₀ (SmtB). A variety of analytical methods were used to determine the stability, stoichiometry, geometry and metal-binding sites of complexes such as: potentiometric titration, mass spectrometry, NMR, UV-VIS, CD and molecular modelling (DFT). Point mutations studies helped to understand the role of each histidine residue in the studied peptides.

Figure 1. A model of Ni(II)-₁₀₁DHHLAHIVVDAIAHASEDRR₁₂₀ complex. Based on a results of DFT calculations.

Both native peptides and mutants form equimolar complexes with Ni(II) ions. The replacement of His102 and His106 with Ala residue strongly decreased the stability of L1 complex with Ni(II) ions, which confirms that His102 and His106 are engaged in Ni(II) binding. NMR studies showed that additionally, His14 and carboxyl groups of acidic amino acid residues interact with Ni(II) ions in the complex. It was

also confirmed by the DFT calculations. The analogical results were obtained for the L4. The comparison of the experimental data to the literature data about Zn(II)-binding residues of the L4 enabled to establish, that peptide L4 form Ni(II)-complexes with different coordination mode than in Zn(II)-complexes. It means, that some additional amino acids are involved in Ni(II) ions binding comparing to the Zn(II)-complex. It is in agreement with results from the CD and UV-VIS experiment, confirming that Ni(II) ions form octahedral complexes and their coordination number equals 6 (in the range of pH 2-9), meanwhile Zn(II) ions form tetrahedral complexes and their coordination number equals 4. Moreover, the studies on the native proteins were also carried out. The BigR4 and SmtB proteins were expressed in *E. Coli* system and purified with the use of the Strep-Tag[®] method. Then the BigR4 crystals were obtained and measured with the XRD method in order to determine the 3D structure of a protein and its binding residues for metal ions.

The results shows the interesting properties of L1 and L4 as a ligands for Ni(II) ions and strongly encourage further studies of this topic.

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Support of the National Science Centre (NCN 0202/2217/18) is gratefully acknowledged.

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Triamine receptors as fluorescent chemosensors for anti-inflammatory nonsteroidal drugs. The ketoprofene case.

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Emerging pollutants are chemical compounds whose potential environmental impact has been recognized only in the last few years. In most cases, they are industrial chemical compounds whose toxicity has been ignored for years or product used in everyday life whose harmfulness has been clarified only in the last few years. In most cases (and countries) their use is not yet subjected to exact normative. Among them, a number a commonly used drugs, including antibiotics and nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), have been now recognized as harmful for the environment, and, in a long-time perspective, for human health. Their large use is leading to a progressive increase of their presence in the environment, in particular in marine and internal water.

The purpose of the present work is the development of new fluorescent molecular sensors for NSAIDs. Here we use two fluorescent triamine receptors, L1 e L2, as optical probes for one of the most used NSAIDs, ketoprofen. The two receptors are constituted by a polyamine chain, which can protonate in aqueous solution a neutral pH and two anthracene units, which feature a high fluorescence emission and a marked hydrophobic character. From this point of view, the two receptors possess optimal structural

characteristics for NSAIDs recognition. In fact, NSAIDs, and ketoprofen among them, present in their structure a carboxylic group, normally deprotonated at neutral pH, and aromatic units. Therefore, the triamine chain of the receptors, when protonated, can interact *via* charge-charge and hydrogen bonding interactions with the anionic carboxylate group of ketoprofen, while the anthracene units can give hydrophobic and/or π -stacking interactions with the aromatic portions of the NSAID.

Furthermore, polyamine chains can form stable complexes with metal cations, in particular transition metals, which can be used as anchoring points for substrate, including ketoprofen, which can bind to metal cations *via* its carboxylate group.

Therefore, we have explored the binding and sensing properties of L1 and L2 and their Zn(II) complexes for ketoprofen in aqueous media by coupling potentiometric, ¹H NMR, UV-vis spectrophotometric and fluorescent emission measurements. Potentiometric titrations have shown that both receptors can easily form protonated species in aqueous solution, enabling the interaction

with the substrate to form 1:1 adducts, stabilized by charge-charge and hydrogen bonding interactions involving the carboxylate group of ketoprofen. This hypothesis has been also confirmed by an X-ray crystal structure of the adduct between the diprotonated form of L2 and ketoprofen. In contrast, ¹NMR measurements show that the anthracene units seem do not interact with aromatic groups of the substrate.

However, at pH 7 the interaction gives rise to a marked increase of the fluorescence emission of both L1 and L2. At neutral pH, the triamine chain is monoprotated, the acidic proton being localized on its central nitrogen. The two amine groups adjacent to the anthracene units can act as fluorescence quenchers *via* a photoinduced electron transfer (PET) process to the excited anthracene moieties. Binding of ketoprofen induces a translation of the acidic proton from the central nitrogen to a benzylic amine group, inhibiting the PET process and therefore inducing a renewal of the anthracene emission.

Both L1 and L2 can also bind to Zn(II), forming fluorescent mononuclear metal complexes. The metal complexes have been shown to interact with ketoprofen to give ternary adducts, in which the carboxylate group of the NSAID binds to Zn(II). Even in this case, ketoprofen coordination is translated in an optical signal. In fact, a marked enhancement of the emission of the Zn(II) complexes is observed upon ketoprofen binding.

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Dissolution of In₂O₃ nanoparticles followed by AGNES

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AGNES is an electroanalytical technique specifically designed to measure free metal ion concentrations for amalgamating elements such as Zn, Cd, Pb, Sn or In [1]. AGNES has followed the kinetics of the dissolution of ZnO nanoparticles by recording the free Zn concentration at time intervals as short as 5 minutes. The impact of the radius of the nanoparticles on its solubility has also been determined. One advantage of AGNES over competing techniques (e.g. ultrafiltration combined with ICP-MS) to follow the dissolution process is the sparing of any separation process (such as filtration, where very small particles can be erroneously counted as free ions) [2].

Indium is a Technology Critical Element widely used in electronic devices, often under the form of its oxide, In₂O₃. These materials will, sooner or later, reach environmental compartments, but their behaviour and fate there is not sufficiently known [3]. So, the study of the dissolution process of In₂O₃, which implies the release of free indium to the medium, is timely.

AGNES can follow the dissolution of In₂O₃ by measuring the resulting free indium concentration in the medium. Recent work has established the general characteristics to work with indium, such as the need of a calibration to determine the preconcentration factor or gain [4]. Also, the thin mercury film plated on top of a rotating disk electrode is extremely efficient in reducing the required deposition time [5].

In₂O₃ nanoparticles (and bulk In₂O₃) have been dispersed in KNO₃ background solutions of various pH values and in synthetic seawater and kept at constant temperature and stirring for months. Aliquots taken at suitable time intervals are analysed with AGNES to obtain dissolution curves that reveal the dissolution process and the final stabilization. From the final equilibrium concentrations, values for the solubility constants of these materials will be derived and compared.

Acknowledgements:

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Antimicrobial peptide – metal complexes as the basis of the design of specifically targeted antimicrobial peptides (STAMP)

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The aim of our work is to fully **understand the relationship between antimicrobial peptide-metal coordination, structure, stability, and mode of action.**

The inspiration for this project comes from the dramatic increase of **antimicrobial resistance** – the resistance of a microorganism to an antimicrobial drug that was originally effective for treatment. Because of the general lack of resistance towards antimicrobial peptides (AMPs), they are being relied on as **novel class of therapeutics aimed to conquer drug-resistant bacteria and fungi** [1].

Biologically indispensable metal ions, such as Zn(II) and Cu(II), which are the key players of this project, are substantial for the survival of microbes, being crucial for metalloproteins, such as metalloenzymes, storage proteins and transcription factors. Their effective acquisition is often considered as a **virulence factor**. For some AMPs, metals act as **activity boosters**, affecting the AMP charge and/or structure [2]. Taken together, metal ions have a dual effect on the activity of antimicrobial peptides: (i) AMPs bind them, so that microbes cannot get enough metals essential for their life and virulence (**removal of metal ions, nutritional immunity**) or (ii) AMPs need the given metal ion to **boost their antimicrobial activity**.

In the scope of our work, we have focused on a variety of antimicrobial peptides – clavanins, piscidins, histatins, amylin and shepherins. We focus on the **thermodynamics, structure and coordination chemistry** of the studied complexes. The comparison of these data to the outcome of biological growth studies on several bacterial and fungal strains allow us to draw conclusions about the **relationship between the metal-antimicrobial peptide complex structure, stability, mode of action and efficacy**. Several of the most efficient complexes could serve as **templates for a rational design of novel, more potent AMP-based therapeutics** – we plan to attach the metal-AMP complexes to so-called targeting molecules, such as the C-terminal part of the Pra1 zincophore, which will specifically deliver the AMP to *Candida albicans* [3].

Acknowledgements

Support of the National Science Centre (UMO2017/26/A/ST5/00364) is gratefully acknowledged.

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Coordination of heavy metal ions by macrocyclic polyamines.

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The synthesis, acid–base behaviour and heavy metal (Hg(II), Cd(II), Pb(II)) coordination chemistry of the hexaaazacyclophane ligand (1⁴-hydroxy-3,7,11,14,18,22-hexaaza-1(2,6)-pyridinacyclotricosaphane, **L1**) have been studied by potentiometric, NMR and UV-Vis techniques. Protonation studies reveal that deprotonation of the pyridinol moiety gives rise to a keto-enolic equilibrium, which justifies the higher protonation constant values compared with those analogous pyridine receptors, **L2**. Coordination chemistry studies reveal the formation of mono and binuclear species above pH 5, highlighting the formation of mostly mononuclear species in the case of Cd(II).

Figure 1: Structure of ligand **L1**

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Metal-coordinated assemblies as promising drug delivery platforms

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Cancer is a problem of great impact on public health and it is the leading cause of death worldwide [1]. Despite several molecules with promising features have been proposed to treat cancer, low solubility, poor permeability and short biological half-life time significantly reduce their application in cancer therapy. Among these, quercetin is a flavonoid that displays a broad spectrum of physiological activities such as neuro/cardioprotective, anti-inflammatory and anticancer effects but its pharmacological application is severely confined due to its low water solubility and *in vivo* bioavailability [2]. Over the years, several drug delivery systems (DDSs) have been developed to overcome the above drawbacks and to enhance the therapeutic efficacy by releasing chemotherapy agents at the tumor site and retarding the drug leaking into a healthy physiological environment [3]. Although drug and carrier interactions are of paramount significance for the efficiency of the resulting systems, a quantitative characterization of the molecular interactions between drugs and carriers in solution has been rarely addressed.

In this work, the study of multiple equilibria in solution is proposed as the key for the design and development of DDSs obtained by the co-assembly of quercetin (Que), polyacrylic acid (PAA), a biocompatible and pH-responsive polymer, and metal ions of biological interest (Cu^{2+} and Zn^{2+}) with the aim of optimizing the stability and the drug loading capability of the resulting assembly (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the metal-coordinated assembly.

The flavonoid capacity to complex metal ions and polymer as well as the interaction of the quercetin metal complexes with PAA have been investigated by both UV-Vis spectroscopy and

isothermal titration calorimetry (ITC) in neutral aqueous solution at 25 °C. Speciation models showed that Que can form 1:1 species with both metal ions and an additional 2:1 species with Cu²⁺ [4]. ITC measurements allowed for the determination of the thermodynamic parameters (ΔH° and $T\Delta S^\circ$) that guide the formation of the complex species formed by Que with Cu²⁺ and Zn²⁺ in aqueous solution [5,6]. Interestingly, it was observed that although Que and PAA are unable to interact, the presence of the metal ion allowed for their interaction and thus its features resulted to be crucial for the formation of the final assembly. ITC and UV-vis measurements mutually confirmed the species and stability of the Que-M-PAA systems in solution.

This study highlights the crucial role played by metal ions for the improvement of quercetin stability in aqueous solution and their ability to act as a bridge to associate a drug with a stimuli-responsive polymer. Data obtained provide useful insights for the design of DDSs with enhanced stability and drug loading capability and for the development of new metal-coordinated assemblies able to face current challenges in cancer treatment.

Coordination pattern and reactivity of outer-membrane proteins

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Colorectal cancer (CRC) is the third most common cancer [1]. Despite the progress in diagnosis and treatment methods, it remains one of the most leading causes of death among oncological patients (the second place worldwide) [1]. Among the risk factors, unhealthy diet, obesity, lack of physical activity, postmenopausal hormones, tobacco and alcohol are distinguished [2]. Moreover, gut microbiota plays an essential role in carcinogenesis of the large intestine [3]. Correlations between the human microbiota composition and CRC were first announced in the 1970s. It was later reported that the existence of more than a dozen bacterial species is associated with a higher risk of colon cancer [4, 5]. In 2013, it was concluded that *Fusobacterium nucleatum* increases neoplastic changes [6, 7]. This anaerobic Gram-negative bacteria is naturally present in the human dental plaque. However, if it is present in the colon, it becomes a precursor to cancer. Interestingly, this bacterium is actively involved in cancer progression [8].

What is noteworthy, to effectively achieve adherence to host surfaces, bacteria produce adhesins (multiple adherence factors). They are an important type of virulence factor that facilitates bacterial binding to various host mammalian cells. Thus, they are responsible for the repopulation of the physiological microflora of the human body. They also allow the organism colonization by pathogenic bacteria. Therefore, the examination of adhesin properties is essential for understanding bacterial pathogenesis.

Figure. a) Species distribution diagram for the Ac-ANKGHEHQLE-NH₂ complexes with copper(II) ions; Cu(II):L 1:1, [Cu(II)] = 1 mM. b) Structures of complexes. Blue ribbons follow backbone.

It seems to be interesting to investigate the effect of metal ions coordination on the activity of outer-membrane proteins from *F. nucleatum* and to answer the question whether proteins increase

the prooxidative activity of metal ions. Usage of a broad spectrum of experimental methods as well as theoretical calculations allowed to characterize: the protonation of designed peptides (fragments of outer-membrane proteins), the ability of the ligands to coordinate divalent metal ions, the full description of the coordination process, competition in metal binding between different peptides as well as the specificity of different metals coordination by the same ligand. Moreover, it was also found that some forming complexes generate reactive oxygen species (ROS) in the presence of hydrogen peroxide, ascorbic acid, or their mixture. Therefore, complexes are able to cleave plasmid DNA [9]. All these findings suggest that enhanced ROS production in the presence of *F. nucleatum* proteins may be crucial in colon cancer progression.

Acknowledgements

The project leading to these results has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 778245.

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Additional feature of heat shock protein B1 in ferroptosis?

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Regulated cell death is something that accompanies us practically from the first moments of life, allowing, for example, the separation of fingers during the prenatal life. One of the types of such a phenomenon is ferroptosis, which is dependent on iron [1]. Despite ferroptosis was found to be distinct and disparate from other processes of cell death, both morphologically and biochemically, and many pathways leading to this type of programmed cell death were defined, many questions about this phenomenon are still open. One of them is how does iron regulate the downstream or upstream controllers of ferroptosis in the singling path [2]?

As iron is transported into the cell mainly by transferrin (Tf) via transferrin receptor 1 (TfR1), through the receptor-mediated endocytosis of Tf-TfR1 complex, blockage of this process leads to inhibition of ferroptosis. Recently, it was shown that recycling of TfR1, which normally follows the release of iron ions and the hydrolysis of transferrin from the complex, is inhibited by HSPB1, along with iron concentration reduction [2-4]. Heat shock protein B1 (HSPB1 also known as Hsp27) is an ATP-independent chaperone, which belongs to the family of small heat shock proteins (sHsp). Its expression is increased during heat shock, oxidative stress or stimulation by cytokines, such as tumor necrosis factor and basic fibroblast growth factor [2]. Interestingly, in the amino-acid sequence of HSPB1, the same motif as in heavy chain of ferritin (an iron storage protein) can be found. Therefore, a series of analogues of peptides including this motif were designed to check, if they are able to bind iron ions.

Acknowledgements: Polish National Science Centre, grant UMO-2018/31/D/ST4/02574.

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Fine-tuning the metal ion-binding abilities of bio mimicking peptides by altering the side chains

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Peptides have high metal binding affinity, but both the thermodynamic stability and the coordination geometry of peptide complexes are very much influenced by the amino acid sequence of the ligands. One field of our present research work is the synthesis and investigation of polypeptides containing various side chain donor groups, in which the coordination of side chain donor atoms comes to the front and their sequences serve as the models of different metalloproteins. The histidine imidazole nitrogens are frequent side chain donor groups in these metalloproteins and imidazole nitrogen is one of the most important binding sites of transition metal ions. Such metal ion–protein interaction plays role for example in the function of Cu,Zn superoxide-dismutase enzyme or neurodegenerative diseases.

We synthesized such series of multihistidine peptides in which the systematic change of the amino acid sequence is carried out and the equilibrium, structural and electrochemical parameters of their complexes are determined. These molecules include oligopeptides built up from 4 to 12 amino acid residues containing histidines in different positions and amino acid environments. To understand the specific effects of these side chains lysine, aspartic acid or phenylalanine were systematically inserted into the sequence of the multihistidine peptides: Ac-HDAH-NH₂, Ac-HADH-NH₂, Ac-HXHZH-NH₂ (X, Z = Ala, Phe, Asp, Lys) and Ac-HXHAHXH-NH₂ (X = Asp or Phe). We performed the equilibrium, structural and electrochemical studies of copper(II), nickel(II) and zinc(II) complexes of these multihistidine peptides. The stoichiometry, stability and structure of complexes were studied using pH-potentiometric, UV-vis, CD spectroscopy and ESI-MS techniques. The electrochemical parameters of copper(II) complexes were determined on the basis of CV measurements.

The results clearly show that the stability of the metal complexes significantly depend on the metal ion and the number and position of histidines in the peptide. The metal binding ability of the peptide is, however, affected by the amino acids which are present in the neighbourhood of the histidine amino acids, also. The presence of phenylalanine and lysine side chain reduces the stability, which may be due to steric hindrance of the bulky side chain. On the other hand, the presence of aspartic acid affects the deprotonation of peptide amide nitrogens.

These conclusions strongly suggest that the thermodynamic and structural properties of the peptide complexes could be finely tuned by the change of quality and sequence of amino acids around the side chain donor atoms of coordinating the metal ions. This means, that the systematic planning of the sequence of peptides could increase the metal binding selectivity of peptides as well.

The research was supported by the Hungarian Scientific Research Fund (K115480).

Sulphur-Containing Macrocycles: Promising Chelators for Copper-64 Radiopharmaceuticals

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Among the variety of medically relevant metallic radionuclides, copper has attracted great interest because it possesses several radioisotopes with half-life and emission properties suitable for diagnostic and therapeutic applications. [1, 2] Copper-64 ($t_{1/2}$ 12.7 h) is the most versatile since its unique decay profile, which combine β^+ ($E_{\beta^+, \max}$ 655 keV, I_{β^+} 17%), β^- ($E_{\beta^-, \max}$ 573 keV, I_{β^-} 39%) and electron capture emissions (I_{EC} 43%), makes it suitable for both positron emission tomography (PET) imaging and, potentially, cancer therapy. [1]

To securely deliver copper-64 to tumour cells, the stable complexation through a bifunctional chelator, covalently tethered to a targeting biomolecule, is needed. [3] However, inertness of $[^{64}\text{Cu}^{2+}]$ -complexes *in vivo* is thwarted by the bio-induced reduction of Cu^{2+} to Cu^+ that may bring to demetallation processes. [1] In an attempt to stabilize both copper oxidation states, we have designed and developed a series of *N*-functionalized cyclen derivatives bearing soft sulfur donor arms (Figure 1): 1,4,7,10-tetrakis(2-(methylsulfanyl)ethyl)-1,4,7,10-tetraazacyclododecane (DO4S), 1,4,7-tris(2-(methylsulfanyl)ethyl)-1,4,7,10-tetraazacyclododecane (DO3S), 1,4,7-tris(2-(methylsulfanyl)ethyl)-10-acetamido-1,4,7,10-tetraazacyclododecane (DO3SA_m), and 1,7-bis(2-(methylsulfanyl)ethyl)-4,10-diacetic acid-1,4,7,10-tetraazacyclododecane (DO2A2S). [4]

To evaluate the potential of the proposed ligands as BFCs for $[^{64}\text{Cu}]$ -based radiopharmaceuticals, the thermodynamic, kinetic, structural properties of their cuprous and cupric complexes were explored through a combination of different techniques, such as UV-Visible, Electron Paramagnetic Resonance (EPR) and Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) spectroscopies, X-ray crystallography, and electrochemical methods (potentiometry, cyclic voltammetry and electrolysis). This was supported by Density Functional Theory (DFT) calculations. Radioactive incorporation in several conditions and *in vitro* stability with copper-64 were explored as well.

Overall results indicate the ability of these ligands to coordinate both copper oxidation states firmly. Moreover, a fast and quantitative radiolabelling at room temperature and high stability in human serum were achieved for some of them. These results make cyclen derivatives bearing sulfur donor arms promising candidates for application in copper-based radiopharmaceuticals.

Figure 1. Structure of the ligands investigated in this work.

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Caspase-dependent mitochondrial pathway of apoptosis induced by the Cu^I complex with (P(*p*-OCH₃-Ph)₂CH₂SarGly)) in lung 3D tumour spheroid

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Cancer diseases are one of the mankind biggest problems in recent decades.[1,2] Currently, cisplatin and second-generation Pt(II) derivatives are widely used in cancer chemotherapy. However, intrinsic and/or acquired drug resistance, toxicity and side effects are major disadvantages of Pt(II)-drugs.[3,4] These clinical drawbacks have stimulated an extensive search for other metal-based agents with improved pharmacological properties.[5] Copper, as an essential element, is a crucial component of many metallo-proteins and -enzymes and plays a vital role in electron transfer reactions of many cellular processes.[6] It has been already demonstrated different response of normal and tumour cells to copper ions could be exploited for the development of novel copper complexes endowed with peculiar antineoplastic characteristics.[7,8]

Figure 1 CLSM images of A549 cells incubated with 1-MPSG for 2h at 37°C at 5 μM concentration. Cells are imaged in the blue channel for Hoechst 33342, the green channel for organelle probes (Mito-, ER-, LysoTracker) and the specific pink/violet emission for 1-MPSG. The bright green/yellowish areas in the merged pictures indicate colocalization of 1-MPSG mitochondrial compartments, ER or lysosomes, respectively. Scale bars represent 5 μm in all images.

Phosphonium salt $(p\text{-OCH}_3\text{-Ph})_2\text{P}(\text{CH}_2\text{OH})_2\text{Cl}$ (MPOHC), derived phosphine ligands without and with SarGly (Sarcosine-Glycine) peptide carrier $\text{P}(p\text{-OCH}_3\text{-Ph})_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$ (**MPOH**) and $\text{P}(p\text{-OCH}_3\text{-Ph})_2\text{CH}_2\text{SarGly}$ (**MPSG**), respectively, and two copper(I) complexes $[\text{Cu}(\text{I})(\text{dmp})(\text{MPOH})]$ (**1-MPOH**; $\text{dmp} = (2,9\text{-dimethyl-1,10-phenanthroline})$) and $[\text{Cu}(\text{I})(\text{dmp})(\text{MPSG})]$ (**1-MPSG**) were synthesized.

$[\text{Cu}(\text{I})(2,9\text{-dimethyl-1,10-phenanthroline})\text{P}(p\text{-OCH}_3\text{-Ph})_2\text{CH}_2\text{SarcosineGlycine}]$ (**1-MPSG**), highly stable in physiological media phosphino copper(I) complex, is proposed herein as a viable alternative to anticancer platinum-based drugs. Noteworthy, **1-MPSG** significantly reduced cell viability in 3D spheroidal model of human lung adenocarcinoma (A549). Confocal microscopy and ICP-MS analysis proved that **1-MPSG** effectively accumulate inside A549 cells with a significant colocalization in mitochondria and nuclei. Precise cytometric analysis revealed a predominance of apoptosis over the other types of cell death. This was manifested by the decrease of mitochondrial membrane potential along with the activation of caspases-3/9. Furthermore, the investigated Cu(I) complex presumably induces the changes in cell cycle leading to G₀/G₁ phase arrest in a dose-dependent manner. As the most probably significant pathway responsible for the cytotoxicity was indicated ROS generation, examined by fluorescence spectroscopy, gel electrophoresis and flow cytometry.

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Acknowledgements:

The authors gratefully acknowledge financial support from the Polish National Science Centre (Grant 2016/23/D/ST5/00269).

Silver and zinc complexes with acids derived from pyridine and their biological activity

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Apart from the serious cancer diseases, there is a multitude of medical conditions which threaten human lives every day and are caused by microorganisms. The current COVID-19 pandemic situation proves it. Given that the development of antimicrobials has been on the periphery of the scientific community's interest, there is currently a risk that, just like with the pandemic that has arisen as a result of the coronavirus' lethal effect, a pandemic caused by, for example, pathogenic bacteria may occur. Therefore, scientists are intensively working on developing effective and selective antimicrobials again. For this purpose, it is important to know what natural mechanisms the immune system in our organisms uses and to find approaches to help support this system. One of the ideas of how to aid the immune system in case of acute conditions caused by infection is to combine metal ions with antimicrobial effects (especially Ag⁺, but also Zn²⁺ and Cu²⁺ ions) and effective organic ligands. Many approaches are used to properly design the composition of a ligand to serve its purpose after it binds a metal ion. Some scientists design ligands to serve as antimicrobial metal ion transporters or as carriers that release the metal ion at the site of infection gradually, or to be multifunctional (transporters, carriers, but also antimicrobials and analgesics). In order to serve their purpose, it is important that they form particles with the metal ion which, by their lipophilicity, electrostatic and hydrophobic interactions, and their conformational flexibility, would be able to interact with membrane structures. In combinations of silver ions (as the most antibacterial metal ion) and suitable ligands, N-heterocyclic carbenes and phosphines have so far been most frequently used [1, 2]. In addition, research (along with our results) of carboxylic acid ligands and silver and zinc ions has made a significant contribution.

In the form of a poster, we will present the results obtained by potentiometric measurements of silver and zinc ions with pyridinesulfonic (PS) and pyridinephosphonic acid (PP) in aqueous solution depending on pH. Moreover {[Ag(py-2-SO₃)]}_n (AgPS) complex biological activity will be presented [3].

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Biologically active heterometallic Ir(III)-Cu(II) complexes with phosphines derived from fluoroquinolone antibiotics.

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Antimicrobial resistance is a real challenge for scientists. In recent years, it's increasingly harder to find a successfully effective medicine for microbial infections. Fluoroquinolones are known antibacterial agents whose minor modification could change their biological activity against Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria. [1] Furthermore, they exert also anticancer activity. Cancer is a group of diseases that are count as one of the most life-threatening in the whole world. [2] In accounts of the Global Cancer Observatory is reported that in 2020 there were over 9 million deaths because of cancer and around 19 million new cases. [3] One of the most used metal-based drugs in chemotherapy is the ones that contain Pt(II). However, cancer cells could generate resistance towards them. Moreover, they have been considered to possess not excellent selectivity, which equals with side effects. Due to these disadvantages, researchers have looked for new structures that could be more efficient. It is believed that Ir(III) organometallic complexes could be a new class of antitumor agents. Their advantages over current chemotherapeutics are high stability, anticancer activity, phosphorescent properties, and different mechanism of action in comparison to Pt(II) substances. [4, 5] Besides the Ir(III) complexes, compounds with copper(II) ion are also investigated as potential anticancer drugs. [6] The superiority of these substances is that they are already present in the human body. [7]

Figure 1. Structural formulas of Ir(III)/Cu(II) complexes.

Iridium(III)/copper(II) half-sandwich complexes were synthesized with methyldiphenylphosphine derivatives of fluoroquinolones (IrPNrCu(phen), IrPLmCu(phen)) for the first time. To identify compounds and study their potential antimicrobial and anticancer properties, they were characterized by several physicochemical methods. We used ESI-MS spectrometry, elemental analysis, infrared and fluorescence spectroscopies, X-ray diffractometry, as well as electrochemical techniques. Furthermore, their biological properties were investigated by microbiological and MTT assays. It was proved that they exhibit antimicrobial activity against some of the reference strains (i.e., *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*), where additionally clinical strain of *S. aureus* exhibited intermediate susceptibility for IrPLmCu(phen). The MTT assay proved that IrPNrCu(phen) and IrPLmCu(phen) have better *in vitro* cytotoxicity than cisplatin (reference drug). The measured IC₅₀ values display selectivity of analysing complexes towards human lung adenocarcinoma (A549 cell line). Moreover, Ir(III)/Cu(II) complexes were locked in liposomes (IrPNrCu(phen)_L, IrPLmCu(phen)_L). It improved their solubility in water and also allowed the elimination of organic solvents. For further cytotoxicity studies, we incubated multicellular tumour spheroids of A549 with IrPNrCu(phen)_L.

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Acknowledgements:

The authors gratefully acknowledge financial support from the Polish National Science Centre (Grant 2020/37/N/ST4/02698). The UV-Vis measurements were carried out with the equipment purchased thanks to the financial support of the Polish National Science Centre (Grant 2016/23/D/ST5/00269).

Bioinorganic secrets of histatins

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Histatins are the part of human immune system and belong to the first line of defense in the human oral cavity [1]. They effectively kill bacteria and fungi in the mouth [2]. Although the mechanism of antibacterial action of histatins has been studied for many years, it is still far from being fully understood [3]. Histatin 5 is the major representative of the histatin family of cationic salivary peptides [4]. The saliva contains significant concentrations of Zn(II) and Cu(II) [5]. Cu(II) ions can be bound to histatin 5 by the ATCUN motif (*via* and albumin-like binding), as it contains a free amino group and a histidyl residue in the third position. The Zn(II) ion binding peptide fragment, in turn, lies at its C-terminal end, where there is the His-Glu-Xaa-Xaa-His sequence, which is characteristic of several zinc-containing proteins (Figure 1) [1,6].

Figure 4. Characteristic metal ion binding motifs in histatin 5

We have performed detailed thermodynamic and spectroscopic studies of Cu(II) and Zn(II) complexes of histatin 5 and products of its hydrolysis: (i) the 12 amino acid, C-terminal region of histatin 5 – histatin 8 and (ii) the 12 amino acid, N-terminal fragment, named histatin 5-8.

Histatin 8 forms the most stable complexes with Cu(II) at a molar ratio of 1:1 in the whole studied range of pH. Cu(II) is bound to four nitrogen donor atoms: the N-terminal amine group, two deprotonated peptide nitrogens, and the imidazole nitrogen, forming three fused chelate rings above pH 4. A similar behavior is observed in the case of an excess of Cu(II), while at a molar ratio of 1: 2 (M: L), copper has the greatest affinity for histatin 5. On the other hand, zinc(II) complexes behave differently - Zn(II) has

the highest affinity towards the Hst 5-8 peptide (containing AKRHH motif) above pH 7.5 - both at 1:1 and 2:1 (M:L) molar ratios. This result is undoubtedly influenced by the surprising ability of the Zn(II) ion to induce an α -helical structure, which is not observed in the case of Hst 5-Zn(II) and Hst 8-Zn(II) systems.

While these results still hide secrets and require further biological analysis, they may be a stepping stone to understand the contribution of metal ions to the antimicrobial properties of histatins.

Acknowledgements:

Support of the National Science Centre (UMO2017/26/A/ST5/00364) is gratefully acknowledged.

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FERNANDO PULIDORI AWARDS

Understanding the mechanism of ZinT-mediated metal acquisition: a thermodynamic study

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ZinT is a periplasmic protein found in Gram-negative bacteria. It is involved in cellular metal trafficking and may function as zinc-chaperone for the ZnuABC transporter. There is a general consensus that the three highly conserved histidine residues (His167, His176 and His178) facing the centre of ZinT calycin like-domain and the amino-terminal fragment between residues 24 and 29 (-HXHHXH-) should be effective zinc binding sites [1, 2]. The Zn²⁺-ZinT complex from *S. enterica* can interact with ZnuA forming a ternary complex where both proteins expose their binding pocket to the Zn²⁺ ion and where the His-rich loop of ZnuA functions as a hypothetical metal transfer intermediary between the two proteins [3, 4]. The main aim of this work is therefore to provide insight into the correlation between the metal-binding ability of ZinT and its biological role. The chosen unstructured fragments, which serve as models to simulate the coordination and transport of metal ions in ZinT protein (see Figure 1) from *Escherichia coli* and *Salmonella enterica*, correspond to the 24–29 and 166–178 amino acid sequences and are protected at the amino- and carboxyl-termini: Ac-²⁴HGHSH²⁹-Am and Ac-¹⁶⁶DHIIAPRKSSH¹⁷⁸-Am (*E. coli*), Ac-²⁴HGHHAH²⁹-Am and Ac-¹⁶⁶DHIIAPRKAHFH¹⁷⁸-Am (*S. enterica*). Interestingly, both the metal-binding sites of ZinT from *S. enterica* undergo a Ser-to-Ala substitution (position 28 and 175). A deep investigation of the complex-formation equilibria and coordination chemistry of the formed species has been performed through different experimental techniques, including potentiometry, mass spectrometry and various spectroscopies.

Figure 1. Proposed coordination sphere for Zn²⁺ (left) and Cu²⁺ (right) complexes with ZinT model peptide (166–178 sequence) at acidic pH. Explicit hydrogen atoms are omitted for clarity.

The obtained results highlight novel insight into the mechanism of ZnT-mediated metal acquisition and allow a comparison with other biologically relevant metal-binding systems, such as the antimicrobial peptide calcitermin which can, in principle, participate in human nutritional immunity, competing with ZnT for the metal ion acquisition.

Acknowledgments: Financial support of the National Science Centre (UMO-2017/26/A/ST5/00364 and UMO-2020/37/N/ST4/03165) is gratefully acknowledged. This paper is based upon work from COST Action CA18202, NECTAR – Network for Equilibria and Chemical Thermodynamics Advanced Research, supported by COST (European Cooperation in Science and Technology).

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Highly Stable Silver(I) Complexes with Cyclen-Based Ligands Bearing Sulfide Arms: Towards Silver-111 Labeled Radiopharmaceuticals

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With a half-life of 7.45 days, silver-111 (¹¹¹Ag, β_{\max} 1.04 MeV, E_{γ} 245.4 keV [I_{γ} 1.24%], E_{γ} 342.1 keV [I_{γ} 6.7%]) is a promising candidate for targeted cancer therapy with β^{-} emitters as well as for associated single photon emission computer tomography (SPECT) imaging. [1]

To securely deliver the radioactive silver to the cancer cells a stable complexation with a bifunctional chelator (BFC) conjugated to a targeting biovector, is required. [2] This contribution will highlight the thermodynamic, structural and radiochemical evaluation of a series of sulphur-containing derivatives of 1,4,7,10-tetraazacyclododecane (cyclen), namely, 1,4,7,10-tetrakis(2-(methylsulfanyl)ethyl)-1,4,7,10-tetraazacyclododecane (DO4S), (2S,5S,8S,11S)-2,5,8,11-tetramethyl-1,4,7,10-tetrakis(2-(methylsulfanyl)-ethyl)-1,4,7,10-tetraazacyclododecane (DO4S4Me), 1,4,7-tris(2-(methylsulfanyl)ethyl)-1,4,7,10-tetraazacyclododecane (DO3S), 1,4,7-tris(2-(methylsulfanyl)ethyl)-10-acetamido-1,4,7,10-tetraazacyclododecane (DO3SAm), and 1,7-bis(2-(methylsulfanyl)ethyl)-4,10-diacetic acid-1,4,7,10-tetraazacyclododecane (DO2A2S), as possible ligands for ¹¹¹Ag complexation.

Acknowledgements: This work was financially supported by the ISOLPHARM project of the Italian Institute of Nuclear Physics (INFN).

The presented work has been recently published in *Inorganic Chemistry* (M. Tosato, M. Asti, M. Dalla Tiezza, L. Orian, D. Häussinger, R. Vogel, U. Köster, M. Jensen, A. Andrichetto, P. Pastore, V. Di Marco, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2020, 59 (15), 10907-10919, <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/abs/10.1021/acs.inorgchem.0c01405>).

An 8-hydroxyquinoline–proline hybrid with multidrug resistance reversal activity and the solution chemistry of its half-sandwich organometallic Ru and Rh complexes

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Since the discovery and approval of the chemotherapeutic drug cisplatin a myriad of metal complexes were synthesized to combat cancer [1,2]. Several promising compounds entered into clinical studies or showed cytotoxic or antimetastatic activity *in vitro* and/or *in vivo*. Some candidates with Ru(II) and Ru(III) centres entered to clinical investigations [3]. Based on these promising results, the number of new half-sandwich Ru(II) complexes developed is still increasing [4]. However, one of the most severe problems of traditional chemotherapeutics is still the acquired resistance against a wide range of drugs, which is known as multidrug resistance. Szakács *et al.* showed a group of anticancer compounds including 8-hydroxyquinolines which are more cytotoxic against resistant cancer cells than non-resistant ones [5].

The design, synthesis and complex formation of a new 8-hydroxyquinoline derivative (HQCl-Pro, see in the **Figure 1**) with good water solubility will be introduced. Effect of the combination of this ligand with half-sandwich Ru(II)(η^6 -*p*-cymene), Ru(II)(η^6 -toluene) and Rh(III)(η^5 -C₅Me₅) on the cytotoxicity was assayed. HQCl-Pro and its Rh-complex showed similar selectivity for doxorubicin-resistant cancer cells like the previously published 8-hydroxyquinolines [6] and newly reported oligopyridines [7], while the Ru(II)-arene complexes were not cytotoxic. Cell accumulation studies showed that Ru compound enter to the cell in less extent than the Rh complex.

Their complex formation ($\log K [M(\text{arene})(L)]$), deprotonation of the coordinated water molecule in the complex ($\text{p}K_a[M(\text{arene})(L)]$), the exchange of this water molecule to a chlorido ligand ($\log K' (H_2O/Cl^-)$) and lipophilicity ($\log D_{7.4}$) were also investigated. An interesting finding is that the lipophilicity of the complexes was found to be increased with the increasing chloride ion concentration, which is a result of the formation of neutral $[M(\text{arene})(L)Cl]$ complexes. The Rh-complex showed cell

accumulation in higher extent compared with the Ru analogue which can explain the higher cytotoxicity of this compound.

The Ru(η^6 -*p*-cymene) complex of HQCI-Pro showed decomposition process when excess of bidentate ligand was introduced. This process is called 'arene loss' in which the half-sandwich structure is destroyed. This is the same side-reaction which was found earlier with other 8-hydroxyquinolines [6] and with 2-picolinates [8]. This reaction may result in the less cytotoxic activity of the Ru complexes and the loss of selectivity.

Figure 1. Structure of HQCI-Pro ligand and its half-sandwich complexes.

Acknowledgement: This work was supported by the National Research, Development and Innovation Office-NKFI through projects GINOP-2.3.2-15-2016-00038, FK 124240 and Ministry of Human Capacities, Hungary grant, TKP-2020, and a Momentum Grant of the Hungarian Academy of Sciences.

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ISMEC 2021

International Symposium on Thermodynamics of Metal Complexes

Białystok, June 16th-18th

Acta of the International Symposia on Thermodynamics of Metal Complexes

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President of the ISMEC Group

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Chair of ISMEC 2021

ISMEC GROUP SERIES

VOLUME: 10

YEAR: 2021

SYMPOSIUM EDITION: XXXI

<https://www.ismecgroup.org/ismec-acta/>

ISSN: 2239-2459